

Welcome to the Conference Schedule – In-Person and Hybrid

Hours	Weds.	Thurs. & Fri.	Sat.
Registration	Online 24hrs (through February 15)		
In-person Registration:	8:00am–6:00pm	8:00am–6:00pm	8:00am–4:00pm
Sessions (In-person and Hybrid, all times Eastern)	2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm	9:00am–10:30am 11:00am–12:30pm 2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm	9:00am–10:30am 11:00am–12:30pm 2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm
In-person Book & Trade Fair:		9:00am–6:00pm	9:00am–2:30pm
Virtual Book & Trade Fair	24hr access, February 12-15		

Welcome to the Conference!

Watch recordings post-conference until April 17.

collegeart.org

Join us at the CAA 113th Annual Conference February 12–15, 2025, at the New York Hilton Midtown with Hybrid sessions. This year's program boasts over 300 sessions, workshops, and events with content representing the breadth of our constituent fields.

View the CAA website, mobile App and online Schedule for the most complete and up to date information, including recording status. www.collegeart.org

Please note that most on location sessions are not remotely accessible. Recordings of select events will post after the conference.

Presentation titles are listed after the Session title. Information in this pdf is subject to change.

This content is current as of Friday, February 7, 2025.

Wednesday A.M. (Feb. 12)

- EVENT △ MEETING
- ⊕ HYBRID ◆ WORKSHOP

10:30 AM –11:30 AM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North
On-site Orientation

12:00 PM –2:30 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – New York
△ **Art Journal** Art Journal Open Editorial Board Meeting

12:00 PM –2:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Hudson
△ **Committee on Diversity Practices**

12:00 PM –2:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Green
△ **Committee on Intellectual Property**

12:00 PM –2:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Harlem
△ **Committee on Research and Scholarship**

12:00 PM –2:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Lincoln
△ **Education Committee**

12:00 PM –2:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – East
△ **Professional Practices Committee**

12:00 PM –2:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Holland
△ **Services to Artists Committee**

12:30 PM –3:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – Main Entrance, Hotel Lobby
Gallery Tour - tickets required

Wednesday P.M. (Feb. 12)

■ EVENT △ MEETING
🌐 HYBRID ◆ WORKSHOP

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
**Architecture and the Donor Class:
Philanthropy, Power, and Empire**

Chair: Maura Lucking, Buell Center for the Study of Amer Architecture

Chair Remarks

The Hereafter and the Future: Managing the Temporal Horizons of God's Property, **Yara Saqfalhait**, Columbia University

Isaac Newton Phelps Stokes at the Intersection of Beaux-Arts Aesthetics and Progressive Reform, **Evan Neely**

Kasturbhai Lalbhai and the Funding of a Capitalist Postcolonial Order in Ahmedabad, India, **Daniel Williamson**, Savannah College of Art and Design

Mr. Science, Mr. Confucius, and the YMCA in Shanghai: Public-Private Hygienic Partnerships in Republican Chinese Workers' Housing, 1926–1938, **Y. L. Lucy Wang**, Columbia University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
Bodies in Action, East and West

Chair: Constanze Fritzschn, Fulbright Fellow at GRI

Chair Remarks

The Bodies of the Brighter Future: Alena Čermáková, the Army Art Studio and the Representation of Human Form, **Jitka Sosova**, Academy of Art, Architecture and Design

De-mythologization of the ideal collective body, **Constanze Fritzschn**, Kunsthistorisches Institut Florenz

"Strange Migrations": Bodies and Media in Transformation in Joan Jonas's Sweeney Astray (1994), **Lidia Ferrara**, University of California Los Angeles

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Mercury Ballroom
Boundaries of Sculpture

Chairs: Stanley K. Abe, Duke University; **Michael E. Yonan**, University of California Davis, Department of Art and Art History

Architecture as Sculpture: Replicas of the Santa Casa, **Erin C. Giffin**, Hamilton College

Plastic: Some Observations on the Shape and Form of Eighteenth-Century Terracotta, **Elizabeth Saari Browne**, University of Georgia

Embrace the Egg: Nakanishi Natsuyuki's "Compact Objects" in the World of Assemblage Sculpture, **Dan Adler**, York University

Cloud Gate and the Hertzian Landscape, **Niko Vicario**, Amherst College

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

Camera-derie: Collaborative, Communal, and Collective Practices in Photography

Chair: Alise Tifentale, Kingsborough Community College-CUNY

Discussant: Erina Duganne, Texas State University

A Visual Timeline: Mapping Influences of Pictorialism and Modernism in New York and Seattle Photographic Clubs, 1900–1941, **Thomas Mintz**, CUNY Kingsborough Community College

Joseph Aleksandrovich Schneider: A Case Study in Pornography and Censorship in Soviet Latvia, **Jessica Werneke**, University of Iowa

A Commercial and Educational Pursuit: Venezia '79, the International Center of Photography, and the Traveling Exhibit Circuit, **Nadya Bair**, Hamilton College

Escaping Poverty through Photography: Wendy Ewald, Zana Briski, Nancy McGirr and Their Work with Children, **Hyewon Yi**, SUNY Old Westbury

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Constructions of Indigeneity in Postwar Art of the Americas

Chairs: Shannon Bewley, Boston University; **Chloë L Courtney**, The Institute of Fine Arts, New York University

Rehearsing the Body-Made: Backstrap Looms at Black Mountain College, **Angela Brown**, Princeton University

China Reconstructs: Reception in the Americas of Indigenous Art from China, **Marisol Vilella Balderrama**, University of Pittsburgh

Hippie Entrepreneur Indian Chief: Stewart Brand, the Whole Earth Catalog, and Indigeneity, **Kerry Doran**

Fusing Body Fusing Commodity: Exploring Agency in the Wayward Subjects of Felipe Baeza's Gente del Occidente de Mexico series, **Sydney Barofsky**, University of Illinois Chicago

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

Drawn to Earth: Contemporary Drawing and Environment in the Americas

Chair: Madeline Turner, Harvard Art Museums

"Down into your cunt": Gloria Anzaldúa's Drawings as Queer Feminist Eco-Repair, **Katie Anania**, University of Nebraska-Lincoln

Lúcia, Júlia Pontés, California Institute of the Arts

Globalizing the Disaster Cai Guo-Qiang's The Century with Mushroom Clouds, **Kacper Koleda**, Harvard University

Trade Windings: De-Lineating the American Tropics, **Cecilia Gonzalez Godino**, Museum of Contemporary Art Chicago

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

🌐 Exhibiting Eastern Europe: 'New' Art of the Old Continent

Chair: Marta Zboralska, University of Oxford

Discussant: Ksenia Nouril, The Museum of Modern Art - MoMA

Exhibiting Eastern Europe after 1989, **Magdalena Moskalewicz**, University of Nebraska at Lincoln

Round Table Participant 2, **Agata Justyna Pietrasik**

Round Table Participant 3, **Marta Zboralska**, University of Oxford

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

Geoheritage in the Medieval World

Chairs: Whitney Kite, Columbia University; **Justin Mann**, Dumbarton Oaks Research Lib & Collection

Deforestation, Adaption, and Recycling on Medieval Iceland: Dragons in the Woodshed, **Robyn Barrow**, University of Pennsylvania

The Measure of a Saint: Size, Landscape, and Meaning in St. Olaf Pilgrim Badges, **Cecily Hughes**, Case Western Reserve University

From Harbor to Sacred Space: Coastal Churches and Topography on the Southern Coast of Crete, **Nicolyna Enriquez**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

God Loves Kitsch!

Chairs: Sarah Richter, University of Vermont; **Laura Elizabeth Shea**, Saint Anselm College

Bovine/Divine: Norma "Duffy" Lyon's "Last Supper" in Butter, **Katherine Gregory**, Wake Forest University

"Life is Short...Praise the Groundhog!": Groundhog Day as Modern Spiritual Tradition, **Natalie E. Phillips**, Ball State University

"Let the Little Children Come to Me: Sweet Kitsch and Spreading the Gospel", **Rachel Trusty**

The Power of Mormon Kitsch, **Nathan K. Rees**, University of West Georgia

The Mitred Edge from the Pope to Rihanna to Moira: How Kitsch Enables the Queer Camp, **Christian Gregory**, Saint Anselm College

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon

Identities at Play: Branding, Politics, and Ecology in 20th-Century Visual Culture and Contemporary Art

Chair: Constanza A Robles, Boston University

Chair Remarks

Visibility, Visuality, and Branding in Early Twentieth-Century Ottoman Turkish Periodicals, **Yasemin Gencer**, Wayne State University

Transnational Alliances and Visual Culture at the Ibero-American Exposition (1929), **Constanza A Robles**, Boston University

Exhibition-Making: Feminist Art in Israel from the 70s to the 90s, **Danielle Gorodenzik**

Off-Color: Towards a Color Theory of Ecologies in Crisis, **Katherine Rochester**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite

Material Encounters with Nature, Memory, and Resistance

Chair Remarks

Ocean Intimacies, Sonic Sovereignty: Deep Listening as Radical Care in Transoceanic Art and Activism, **Amber Hickey**, University of Tennessee - Chattanooga

Tracing the Intangible: Thermal Imprints of Memory and Presence, **Bing Wang**, University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

The Contemporary Cyanotype: An Anti-Colonial History through Latin/x American Practices, **Cristina E. Pardo Porto**, Syracuse University

Ocean Gems: Marine Botany and Imagination in Nineteenth-Century Seaweed Albums, **Julia Carabatsos**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

Methods of Engagement in Undergraduate Research

Chairs: **Sue Uhlig**, Purdue University; **Kristen Carter**, Florida Southern College

Discussant: **Peter Haffner**

Fostering Undergraduate Scholarship Through Curator Colab, **Wylie Erin Schwartz**, State University of New York at Cortland

Integrating Film and Television Research in Art and Design Curriculum, **Christopher S. Olszewski**, SCAD

Experimental approaches to engaging undergraduate students in research, **Anne R. Norcross**, Kendall College of Art and Design of FSU

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North

🌐 Personal and Global: Current Directions in Feminist Abstract and Abstractionist Art

COMMITTEE ON WOMEN IN THE ARTS

Chair: **Tanya Augsborg**, San Francisco State University

Reclamation: The Space Between, **Wendy A. Deschene**

Beyond the Gridlines: Possibilities of Loss and Reconstruction in the Abstract Works of Nasreen Mohamedi, Zarina Hashmi, Gargi Raina and Purvai Rai, **Anna Tom**

Reevaluating Theresa Hak Kyung Cha's Abstract Ephemerality as Radical Political Statement, **Ina Choi**, University of Pennsylvania

Weathering: Beverly Buchanan's Environmental Sculpture and Black Bodily Abstraction, **Patricia Ekpo**, Brown University, Pembroke Center for Teaching and Research on Women

Color, Gesture, and Process: Deanna Sirlin's Feminist Abstract Remediations as Social Activism in the Anthropocene Era, **Tanya Augsborg**, San Francisco State University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

Processes of Memory: Digital Practices and Re-Membering Histories

Chair: **Charlotte L. Kent**, Montclair State University

Re-Membering Digital Tools, **Nathaniel Stern**

Insufficient Memory, **Sean Fader**, New York University Tisch School of the Arts

Critical Fabulation for a Benin Heritage: Igun Prototypes, **Minne Atairu**, Columbia University

Glimpse: A Performance on the benefits, harms, and potential of AI, **Amelia Winger-Bearskin**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

Sovereignty, Art, and its Histories

NATIONAL COMMITTEE FOR HISTORY OF ART

Chairs: **C. Jean Campbell**, Emory University; **Caroline Fowler**, Clark Art Institute

Mexican Modernists, the Mineral Frontier, and Subterranean Sovereignty, **Grace Kuipers**, University of California, Berkeley

Seeing Sovereignty in Snow, Salt, and Mold: Ecological Material and the Colonial Condition in the work of Sofia Gallisa Muriente, **Gabrielle Tillenburg**, University of Maryland

The Collective Alternative and the Sovereign Self, **John Zarobell**, University of San Francisco

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite

The State of Central American Art History: Foundations and Future Directions

Chair: **Carlos Rivas**, The Ohio State University

Chair Remarks

The Development of Early Modern Central American Art History, **Carlos Rivas**, The Ohio State University Department of History of Art

Historiography of 19th Century Central American Art: the Cases of Guatemala and Costa Rica, **Leonardo Santamaria Montero**, Cornell University

Contemporary Art and Visual Culture of Central America and the U.S. Diaspora, **Jeannette Martinez**, University of New Mexico

Exhibiting and Collecting Central American Art, **Beatriz Yanes Martinez**, Hood Museum of Art

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse A

The Students and Emerging Professionals Committee's (SEPC) Guide To All Things CAA

STUDENT AND EMERGING PROFESSIONALS COMMITTEE

Chairs: Susan M. Altman, Middlesex College; **Frederica Imani Simmons**, Duke University - Dept of Art, Art Hist & Visual Studies; **Ehryn Torrell**, Bath Spa University

Discussant: Carolyn Jean Martin; **Tyrus R. Clutter**, College of Central Florida; **Li Machado**, Temple University, Tyler School of Art and Architecture; **Elizabeth Schlatter**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West
The “Postsocialist Contemporary:” Passages in Modern-Contemporary Chinese Art

Chairs: Nancy Pai Suan Lin, Cornell University; **Angie Chang Baecker**, The University of Hong Kong

Discussant: Kuiyi Shen, University of California, San Diego

Chair Remarks

The Atomization of the Collective: Legacies of Mass Art Practice in the '85 New Wave, **Angie Chang Baecker**, The University of Hong Kong

Media-topias: Staged Photography and Everyday Drama of the Chinese Contemporary, **Chang Tan**, Penn State University

How Maoist Anxiety Structured the Art of the Beijing Spring, **Jennifer Lee**, School of the Art Institute of Chicago

Realism after Socialist Realism: On-site Art Practice in the 1990s, **Nancy Pai Suan Lin**, Cornell University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

Walled Gardens and Wild Artists

Chairs: Rene Garcia Cepeda, New Media Caucus; **Constanza Salazar**, The Cooper Union

Chair Remarks

harmon_proc post-mortem: selling art on the play store, **Jls L. Gangwisch**, Hartford Art School, University of Hartford

-Making art of and with the influencer, **Sasha Baskin**, Johns Hopkins University Center for Visual Arts

2:30 PM –4:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East

Women Artists and the Politics of Neoclassicism

Chairs: Andrea Morgan, The Art Institute of Chicago; **Megan True**, The Art Institute of Chicago

Marie-Thérèse Reboul Vien and the Emergence of Neoclassicism, **Tori Champion**, University of St Andrews

Marie-Guillemine Benoist (1768-1826): A Neoclassicism of Her Own, **Jennifer G. Germann**, Independent Scholar

La Créatrice in Flux: Women's Artmaking and Ambition in Revolutionary France, **Maura Gleeson**, Valencia College

The Genre Anecdotique and Feminine Historical Consciousness in Early Nineteenth-Century France, **Marina Kliger**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

♦ A Pedagogy Workshop: Building Your Teaching Toolkit – Collaborative Teaching and Learning

Workshop Leader: Jeff Ball, Harford Community College; **Barbara Bergstrom**, Bowling Green State University; **Lauren M. Freese**, University of South Dakota; **Tamryn L. McDermott**, Old Dominion University

Chair Remarks

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
Aberrations in Beauty

Chairs: Delaney Holton, Stanford University; **Claire Chun**, UC Berkeley

Discussant: Vivian Huang

Chair Remarks

Monstrous Beauty: A Placeholder for Someone without a Place, **LaRissa Rogers**, The University of Virginia

Glass Skin: Luminosity, Repair, and Transpacific Ecologies of Beauty and War, **Claire Chun**, UC Berkeley

NECESSARY/USEFUL/PLEASANT, **Rachel Youn**

Body Compositions: Contingent Mattering in the work of Jes Fan and Rachel Youn, **Delaney Holton**, Stanford University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

Afterlives

Chair: Ashley Raghbir, University of Toronto

Visual Hauntologies on Albuquerque's Route 66: Place-Images after the Mother Road, **Madison Garay**, University of New Mexico

The Empire of Oil: Christopher Cozier's Entanglements series (2014-2015) and turbulence (2019-2021), **Ashley Raghbir**, University of Toronto

Coastal Kinstillations: A Case Study of Yamashiro Chikako's Mud Man, **Jiixin Yan**, Penn State University

The Afterlives of Dust: The Spectral Ecologies of Don't Follow the Wind, **Aikaterini Arfara**, New York University Abu Dhabi

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent

Architecture in Repetition

Chairs: Elliott Sturtevant, Columbia University; Ulan Byrne, Columbia University

Chair Remarks

Counterfeit Architecture: Trust and the Architecture of Banking, Philadelphia, Kansas City, Salem, 1876-1891, **Maxwell Smith-Holmes**, Princeton University

Identical, Unspectacular, Unremarkable. The Life and Death of the Political Model of the Italian Single-family House in the 1950s, **Andrea Canclini**, Lancaster University

Repeating for the Extreme: Bayer Post-disaster Houses and their Users, **Asya Uzmay**, Cornell University

Dislocations: Architecture and the Unsettled Geographies of the Railway, c. 1840, **Aleksandr Bierig**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

🌐 Axiological Anchors: A discussion of Indigenous studies ethics, praxis, and methodologies

Chair: Clementine Bordeaux, University of California

An Introduction to Rematriation, **Kendra Greendeer**, Oklahoma State University

Tapak Nowat Aya: Chahta Basketry Across Geographies, **Megan Baker**, Northwestern University

Relational Art Histories of K'é and California: Emma Robbins, **Isabella Shey Robbins**, Yale University

Biskaabiiyang: An Indigenous Art Historical Method, **Taylor Rose Payer**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite

Chemical Intimacies: Thinking with Toxic Media

Chairs: Kevin Hong, Yale University; Siobhan Angus, Carleton University

Chair Remarks

Aerial Intimacies: Edgar Degas's Ironers, Coal Smoke, and Chemicals, **Marni R. Kessler**, University of Kansas

Images of Exposure: Colour and Toxicity at the Filmfabrik Wolfen, **Katerina Korola**, University of Minnesota

Toxic Relations: Stephen Willats and a Participatory Art of the Wasteland, **Christopher Williams-Wynn**, Kunsthistorisches Institut in Florenz – Max-Planck-Institut

Shadow Collection: Chemical Intimacies in the Museum and Archive, **Kirsty M. Robertson**, University of Western Ontario

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West

Cultural Mediations: Identity, Politics, and Representation in Works on Paper

Chair: Wei Wu, University of California San Diego

Chair Remarks

Female Nurses in Winslow Homer's Civil War-era Works on Paper, **Jinze Mi**, Williams College

"A Double Minority": James Van Der Zee's and Lloyd W. Yearwood's Photography of Blacks Jews in 20th Century Harlem, **LaNitra M. Berger**, George Mason University

Shaping a Pre-shaped Public: The Modern Prints Society's Outreach Effort via Kuomintang Institutions, 1934-1936, **Wei Wu**, University of California San Diego

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

Environmental Culture, Urban Artscapes and the Urbanocene

Chairs: Tijen Tunali, Universite Rennes II; Anna Mary Dempsey, University of Massachusetts at Dartmouth

Chair Remarks

Waste Aesthetics in the Urbanocene. On Materiality, Otherness and Spatial Justice., **Marisa Ferreira**, Royal College of Art

New Orleans' Public Art Interventions on the Environment, **Anna Mary Dempsey**, University of Massachusetts at Dartmouth

Killer Buildings, Verticality and Warped Space: the Catastrophic Return(s) of Tower Block Failure, **Leah Modigliani**, Temple University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse A

Hands-On: Critical Connections Between Craft and Pedagogy

Chairs: **Julia Hamer-Light**, University of Delaware;
Olivia Comstock, University of Minnesota Minneapolis

Discussant: **Michelle Fisher**

Chair Remarks

Weaving Without: Arizona Swayney Blakenship's Basket Weaving as Pedagogy, **Rachel Tang**

"Has Education Failed the People?": Margaret De Patta and Pedagogy for the Labor-Conscious Art Student, **Margot Yale**, University of Southern California

An Artisanal Attitude, **Monica M. Amor**, Maryland Institute College of Art

Putting the Technê in Information Tech: Craft and Pedagogy at the Dawn of Personal Technology, **Keyleigh Perkov**, University of California, Davis

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Mercury Ballroom

Heavy Metal: The Artist and the Foundry

Chairs: **Susan Fisher**, Kaish Family Art Project; **Jeffrey Spring**, Modern Art Foundry

Three generations of technical knowledge and skills compared: the Bruni Artistic Foundry in Rome (c. 1880-1982), **Paolo Coen**, Università di Teramo

Origins: The Foundry as Inspiration, **Anne de Villemejjane**

Fifty Shades of Bronze: Gaston Lachaise, his foundries and his legacy in both the 20th century and the 21st, **Paula Hornbostel**

Fabricators in the Foundry: A New Kind of Workshop, **Rex Cassidy**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

In Relation to Art: Community, Collaboration, and Collective Agency in Contemporary Art from East Asia

Chair: **Sohl Lee**, Stony Brook University

Discussant: **Yanhua Zhou**

Chair Remarks

THE PLAY's Art and Borderland Ethics in Okinawa and Hokkaido, **Soyoon Ryu**, The Institute of Fine Arts, New York University

Co-constituting Para-zomia: Amateur Riot's Prefigurative Cultural Practice Against Precaritization in Koenji, **Jason Waite**, Helsinki Collegium for Advanced Studies - University of Helsinki

Difference, Dissonance, Discord? Queer Curatorial Activism in a Harmonious Society, **Maximilian Langefeld**, University of Oxford

From Margins to Mainstream: Listen to the City's Community Engagement and Urban Advocacy, **Minji Chun**, University of Oxford

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Los Angeles during World War II: Art at the Margins

Chairs: **Eileen Costello**, Ellsworth Kelly Foundation;
Joan Pachner, Tony Smith Catalogue Raisonne

Chair Remarks

"As Flat as a Tortilla and as Sleek as a Bugatti": Arts & Architecture Magazine and the Cultivation of the L.A. Art Scene, **Isabel Frampton Wade**, Getty Research Institute

Tony Smith and the Hollyhock House Circle 1943-45, **Joan Pachner**, Tony Smith Catalogue Raisonne

An Art Fundamentally Related to the Machine: The Early Films of John & James Whitney, **Gilles Reginald Heno-Coe**, The University of Texas at Austin

Hans Burkhardt qua Arshile Gorky in Los Angeles Abstraction, **Parker Field**, Arshile Gorky Foundation

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

Materials

Chair Remarks

Fabric to Panel to Fabric: Painting the Materials, Imitating the Techniques, **Olga Yunak**, Graduate Theological Union

Through the Hemlock Trees: Diegesis and Disclosure in Moyra Davey's Video Works, **Rebecca Turner**, Stanford University

Eva Hesse's Synthetic Worlds: Chain Polymers and the Environmental Movement of the 1960s., **Jessica Ziegenfuss**, Texas A&M International University

The Garden of Machinic Delights: José Val del Omar's Techno-Aesthetic Machinescape, **Sangyoung Nam**, Stony Brook University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

Moving the Image: Medieval Diagrams and their Audiences

Chairs: Saskia Quené, University of Tübingen; Meekyung MacMurdie, University of Utah; Carly B. Boxer, Bucknell University

The Late Medieval Diagrammatic Body: A Figural Diagram in the Livre de Propriétés des Choses, Carly B. Boxer, Bucknell University

The Kitab al-Diryaq on the Nature of Knowledge, Meekyung MacMurdie, University of Utah

Measured Movements in the Musica Enchiriadis, Saskia Quené, University of Tübingen

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East
Neoclassicism in the Extended Field

Chairs: Rebecca Yuste, Columbia University; Faraz Olfat, Yale University

Chair Remarks

A Native Transplant: Neoclassicism in post-Ottoman Greece., Nikolaos Magouliotis, ETH Zurich

Adaptive Designs: Neoclassicism and the Cathedral of Nueva Guatemala, 1773–1800, John Sullivan, Northwestern University

The Place de l'Étoile in Beirut and the Crafting of Colonial Neoclassicism, Chantal El Hayek, Pratt Institute

The Stones of Havana: Producing Neoclassical Architecture in a 19th c. Slave Society, Dante Furioso, Princeton University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton South
Plant(S) Matter

Chair: Lindsay Wells, UCLA

Chair Remarks

The Greening of Critique: Plants as Radical Other and Dadaist Hannah Höch's Reinterpretation of the Vegetal in Germany, 1935–1942, Christy Wahl, Independent Scholar

Graphic Ecologies: Empire, Environment, and Botanical Art in British India, Lindsay Wells, Independent Scholar

Private Devotion, Public Display: Situating the Enclosed Gardens of Mechelen within the Context of Women's Miniaturist Traditions, Meredith Vigan-Wilbur, University of South Florida

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

Reframing Landscape: 50 Years after New Topographics

Chairs: Rachel Hutcheson, Columbia University; Maur Dessauvage, Columbia University

Dismantling New Topographics, Mark Rawlinson, University of Nottingham

Stephen Shore's Landscape Photography of Everything, Tracy Stuber, Mapping Color in History

Whose Topographics? Race and Postwar Landscape Photography, Kale Serrato Doyen, University of Pittsburgh

New Topographics: Oil and the End of Landscape Photography, Kirsten J. Swenson, University of Massachusetts, Lowell

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

Relearning to Learn: New Methods for Art History

Chair: Alexandra Sheeler, Rocky Mountain College of Art & Design

Chair Remarks

Reintegrating the Kanon: Classical Proportions and Contemporary Pedagogical Strategies, Joshua Jacobo, New Masters Academy

Early Modern Simulacra in Heavy Metal Visual Culture, Alexandra Sheeler, Rocky Mountain College of Art & Design

Back to the Drawing Board: González, Gego, and the Problem with "Drawing in Space", June Scalia, Washington University in St Louis

After labor, oil, and sand extractivism: Dele Adeyemo's "A Dance of Mangroves", Dale Hudson

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

System Failure: How to Survive and Thrive in Today's Art and Design Higher Education

Chairs: Amelia G. Jones, USC; Benjamin Nicholson, University of Colorado, Boulder

What? Is? Art?, Lindsey White

let them eat plastic!, Fidelia Lam, OCAD University

Call and Response: In Which I Pose Institutional Questions Without Answers, Leslie Foster, California State University San Marcos

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North
🌐 **The Photographer and the Folk: Picturing the Rural Subject in 20th-century Central Europe**

SOCIETY OF HISTORIANS OF EAST EUROPEAN, EURASIAN, AND RUSSIAN ART AND ARCHITECTURE

Chair: Joanna Szupinska, University of California, Los Angeles

Discussant: Andres Mario Zervigon, York University

Chair Remarks

The Dybbuk Haunting Jewish History: Solomon Iudovin's Photographs from the Pale of Settlement, **Benjamin Martin Kersten**

In Women's Hands: The Gendered Dimensions of Social Photography in Central Europe, 1928–1948, **Julia Secklehner**, Constructor University

Zofia Rydet, Pseudo-Ethnographer, **Joanna Szupinska**, University of California, Los Angeles

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman
🌐 **This Old Text and Taxonomy: Renovating Art Historical Documentation**

CATALOGUE RAISONNÉ SCHOLARS ASSOCIATION

Chair: Abigael MacGibeny, Joan Mitchell Catalogue Raisonné

What is a "Critical Response": Recasting Authority in Museum Cataloguing Practice, **Bailey Placzek**, Clyfford Still Museum

A Racial Reckoning: Cataloguing Romare Bearden, **Camara D. Holloway**, Wildenstein Plattner Institute

Language of Landscape: The Frederic Edwin Church Digital Cataloguing Project, Cooper Hewitt, Smithsonian Design Museum, **Casey Monroe**, Cooper Hewitt, Smithsonian Design Museum

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West
Towards a "Pacific Turn" in American Art History

Chairs: Hyeongjin Oh, University of Minnesota, Twin-Cities; **Abi Lua**, James A. Michener Art Museum; **Sienna Weldon**, California State Parks

Art (History) in the Shadow of America's Pacific Empire, **Alicia Volk**, University of Maryland

The View From the Levee: Transpacific Material Culture of Chinese American Temples, **Elizabeth Fair**, University of California - Berkeley

Vortices: Reading Fish Story from the Engine Room to the Deck of Cargo Ship, **Hyeongjin Oh**, Independent Scholar

4:30 PM –6:00 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite
Transgresoras: Mail Art and Messages

Chairs: Zanna Gilbert, Getty Research Institute; **Elena Shtromberg**, University of Utah

Chair Remarks

Cecilia Vicuña's Saborami and the Archiving of Waste, **Eva Caston**

Communication Breakdown: Yani Pecanins' Un viaje en Zeppelin (1988), **Madeline Turner**, Harvard Art Museums

To Be Wrinkled and Thrown Away: Disposability and Absence in Liliana Porter's Mail Art Exhibitions, **Rachel Vogel**, Addison Gallery of American Art-Phillips Academy

Virginia Errázuriz and Alternative Solidarity Networks in Chile during the Pinochet Dictatorship, **Alexandra Schoolman**, Temple University

6:00 PM –7:30 PM WEDNESDAY, FEB. 12

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom East
🌐 ■ **Convocation**

Thursday A.M. (Feb. 13)

Hours	Weds.	Thurs. & Fri.	Sat.
Registration	Online 24hrs (through February 15)		
In-person Registration:	8:00am–6:00pm	8:00am–6:00pm	8:00am–4:00pm
Sessions (In-person and Hybrid, all times Eastern)	2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm	9:00am–10:30am 11:00am–12:30pm 2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm	9:00am–10:30am 11:00am–12:30pm 2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm
In-person Book & Trade Fair:		9:00am–6:00pm	9:00am–2:30pm
Virtual Book & Trade Fair	24hr access, February 12-15		

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View the CAA website, mobile App and online Schedule for the most complete and up to date information, including recording status. www.collegeart.org

Please note that most on location sessions are not remotely accessible. Recordings of select events will post after the conference.

Presentation titles are listed after the Session title. Information in this pdf is subject to change.

This content is current as of Friday, February 7, 2025.

■ EVENT △ MEETING
⊕ HYBRID ◆ WORKSHOP

9:00 AM –11:00 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Hudson
△ **The Art Bulletin Editorial Board Meeting**

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

A Case Study of a Rediscovered Artist: Benjamin Wigfall, a University, a Community, and a Legacy

Chair: Reva J. Wolf, State University of New York at New Paltz

Round Table Participant, Drew Thompson

Round Table Participant, Sarah Eckhardt, The Virginia Museum of Fine Arts

Round Table Participant, Richard Frumess

A Case Study of a Rediscovered Artist: Benjamin Wigfall, a University, a Community, and a Legacy, Anna Conlan, SUNY New Paltz

Round Table Participant, Zachary Bowman, SUNY New Paltz

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite
Anxieties of Divine Representation in the Pre-Modern World

Chairs: **Alexander Ekserdjian**, Yale University;
Charlotte Gorant, Columbia University

Material Theologies of Artemis Ortheia, **Daphne Martin**

Figural and Aniconic Representations of Mother Goddesses in Roman Gaul, **Gretel Rodríguez**, Brown University

What were correct forms for ancient Egyptian gods?,
Jordan Miller

Now You See Me, Now You Don't: Divine (De)Materialisations in Greek Vase Painting, **Müge Arseven**, Columbia University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman
Art, Its History and Institutions in the Age of AI and Posthumanism

INTERNATIONAL COMMITTEE

Chairs: **Mar Morosse**, Baruch College; **Uranchimeg Tsultem**, Herron School of Art and Design, Indiana University Purdue University Indianapolis

Chair Remarks

Distorted Reflections: Digital Technology, Human Representation, and the Future of Art History, **Mallory Wilson**, Pacific Northwest College of Art

Dissolving Boundaries: The Creative Agency of the 'Double Brain', **Natia Ebanoidze**, Independent researcher

BOB and the Moderna Museet collection: A case study on the challenges of AI art and contemporary museum practices in Sweden, **Anna Orrghen**

Presence and Praxis: The Future of Online Art Exhibitions, **Thomas Haiver**, Alba.art

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
Asian and Asian Diasporic Art in Comparative Perspectives

Chairs: **Michelle Yee**, Virginia Commonwealth University;
Boreth Ly, University of California, Santa Cruz

Chair Remarks

Revisiting 'ur': Tamil Geographies in the Settler Colony through the Work of Joshua Vettivelu, **Kaitlin Emmanuel**, Cornell University

Echoes of the Sea: Mediating the Diasporized Memory of the Tanka in Ballad on the Shore, **Evelyn Char**, University of California, Santa Cruz

To Whom Do We Belong? Photography and Asian Adoptees in Diaspora, **Ashley Duffey**, University of Minnesota

Modernism in the Mahjar: Arab-Argentine Painter Bibi Zogbé's Diasporic Legacy Between Latin America, West Asia, and Beyond, **Caroline "Olivia" M Wolf**, Loyola University Chicago

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

Chinese Art Headed "South": Histories, Practices and Models in the 20th-21st Centuries

Chair: **Kathy Yim King Mak**, The Hong Kong Polytechnic University

Discussant: **Aida Yuen Wong**, Brandeis University

Chair Remarks

Between Two Souths: Entanglements Across the South Seas and the American South in China, ca. 1945,
Christine I. Ho

Realigning with the South: Mural Resurgence and National Independence in Mao-China National Painting,
Kathy Yim King Mak, Hong Kong Polytechnic University

Zhang Daqian in South America: Misunderstandings of an Artistic Exchange, **Guilherme Gorgulho**, University of Campinas

Following the New Silk Road to a History of Contemporary Art, **Peter R. Kalb**, Brandeis University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

Current Research in Pacific Visual Studies

PACIFIC ART ASSOCIATION

Chairs: **Maggie Wander**, Santa Clara University; **Nicole Furtado**, University of California Santa Cruz

Chair Remarks

Mata Aho – Weaving and Empowering Female Narratives, **Jacqueline Charles-Rault**

Mapping Race or Nation in the Kingdom of Hawai'i,
Stacy Kamehiro, University of California, Santa Cruz - History of Art and Visual Culture Department

Community Workshops, Environmental Justice, and Installation Art in Oceania, **Maggie Wander**, Santa Clara University

Hawaiian Futurisms: Mixed-Media Mediums as Generating Anti-Colonial Art, **Nicole Furtado**, University of California Santa Cruz

Fale, Tapa, and Fala: The Past and Future of Samoan Heritage Arts, **Anne Allen**

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West
Design for Health and Wellbeing: Innovative Approaches in Design Education and Practice

Chairs: Ting Zhou, University of Connecticut; Helen Sanematsu

Chair Remarks

Zuri: A mHealth Application with Animation and Gamification to Support Sexual Self-Efficacy among Black Adolescent Girls, Ting Zhou, University of Connecticut

Design for Health: Empowering Design and Architecture Students through Innovative Pedagogy, Kimberly Marie Mitchell

Bringing Up Babies: From Education to Application in Service Design for Health and Hospitals, Helen Sanematsu

Participatory Design for Patients with Dementia and Their Caregivers, Aaron Ganci, Herron School of Art and Design, Indiana University Indianapolis

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

Gender, Sexuality, and Non-Pristine Nature in Northern European Art and Material Culture, ca. 1350-1750

HISTORIANS OF NETHERLANDISH ART

Chairs: Sarah Walsh Mallory, The Morgan Library & Museum; Anna-Claire Powell Stinebring, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

Chair Remarks

Bathing Outside: Sex Workers, Cleanliness, and the Extra-Urban World in Sixteenth-Century Germanic Art, Sarah Caitlin Rosenthal

Vertumnus as an Old Woman in Hendrick Goltzius's Vertumnus and Pomona (1613), Sandra Racek, Northwestern University

Cleanliness, dirtiness, and the contamination of genders in Seventeenth-century Netherlandish Painting, L Rochard, Université de Poitiers

Darkness, Dirt, and Excess: Picturing Nightwalkers in 17th-century Dutch Art, Nicole Elizabeth Cook

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

Indigenous Manuscripts of Early Modern Latin America

BIBLIOGRAPHICAL SOCIETY OF AMERICA

Chair: Jeanne-Marie Musto, New York Public Library

Discussant: Dana Leibsohn, Smith College

Poetry vs Poetic Expressivity: "Cantares Mexicanos" and the Alterity of Artistic Production, Gema Valencia-Turco, University of Pennsylvania

Medieval Spanish Literature in the Illustrations of Guaman Poma's New Chronicle, George Thomas, California State University San Bernardino

The Diving God Ceremony: Zelia Nuttall's revival of an Aztec ceremony culled from Mexican Pictorial Manuscripts, Seonaid Valiant, Arizona State University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Mercury Ballroom

Magical Realism, New Objectivity, and the Return of Representation: A Reevaluation

Chairs: Joe Bucciero, Princeton University; Joseph Henry, Graduate Center, City University of New York

Discussant: Adrian V. Sudhalter, Merrill C. Berman Collection

Metaphysics and Politics: De Chirico between Dada and New Objectivity, Ara Merjian, New York University

Trieb: Schad's Freud, Sabine T. Kriebel, University College Cork

What the Eye Does Not See, Megan Luke, Kunsthistorisches Inst der Univ Tubingen

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

META+PHYSICS OF BLACK ARTMAKING

Chairs: Alessandra Raengo, Georgia State University, School of Film, Media & Theatre; Lauren Cramer, University of Toronto

"There is a Mystery": Esotericism and Experimentation in the Film As Told to G/D Thyself, Michele Prettyman, Fordham University

Image Enhancement & Neon Green: Seeing & Sensing in Sandra Mujinga's "Spectral Keepers", Kyëra Sterling

The Flash and Flesh of the Spirit: Thompson and Benjamin, Amelia Ames, Princeton University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North

⊕ Moving Out: David Smith & The Outdoor Migration of Sculpture

Chairs: Suzanne Ramljak, Frederik Meijer Gardens and Sculpture Park; Jennifer Field, Estate of David Smith

Chair Remarks

From Depicted to Embodied Landscape: Preparing the Ground of Smith's Fields, Christopher Leslie Lyon, Lyon Artbooks

David Smith: And/In Landscape, Karen Wilkin

David Smith's Bolton Landing: Fields, Water, Sky, **Paula Wisotzki**, Loyola University Chicago

David Smith Takes to the Air, **Dawna L. Schuld**, Texas A&M University

Weaving the Cultural Character of Landscape, **Elyse D. Speaks**, University of Notre Dame

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

New Directions in British Art and Architectural History

HISTORIANS OF BRITISH ART

Chairs: **Monica Anke Hahn**, Historians of British Art; **Laurel Peterson**, Yale Center for British Art

Cartographic Traces of Privateers: The Illusive Archive of Drake's Caribbean Raids and Sea Networks, **Miranda Elston**, Coastal Carolina University

Out of the Shadows: Re-envisioning Simeon Solomon, **Roberto C Ferrari**, Columbia University and **Sophie Lynford**, Delaware Art Museum

Reimagining Minimalism: Kynaston McShine's Contributions to Mid-1960s British Art and Architectural Narratives in 'Primary Structures', **Sarah Kleinman**, Virginia Commonwealth University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East

Process-Generated Networks: Craft and Sociality in Feminist Art

Chairs: **Sara Blaylock**, University of Minnesota Duluth; **Katerina Korola**, University of Minnesota

Chair Remarks

Caring with or for? Reappraising dynamics of care in Liza Lou's craft-centered communities, **Jennifer Way**, University of North Texas

A Letter From We to You: The Epistolary Community in Sharon Hayes' In My Little Corner of the World, Anyone Would Love You (2016), **Bridget Fleming**, University of Rochester

Stitching together: Extended possibilities of collectivity in Chilean Arpilleras, **Chloë L Courtney**, The Institute of Fine Arts, New York University and **Lee Sessions**, El Museo del Barrio

Photo Femmage: A History of Women and Feminist Photo Montage, **Fiona Rogers**, V&A

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

Reading Bodies of Information: Inventive Feminist Approaches to Women Artists in the Archive

Chairs: **Aliza R. Edelman**, Alison Poe, Fairfield University

Hiding in Plain Site: Mapping Female Agency Across the Archive, **Rachel Middleman**, California State University, Chico, **Anne Monahan** and **Katharine J. Wright**

Nonlinear Feminist Art History and the Difficulty of 'We' in Feministische Kunst Internationaal (1978–81), **Julia Alting**, University of Groningen

If Not Now, When? Generations of Women in Sculpture in Britain, 1960–2022, **Anna Douglas**, University of Leeds and **Kerry Harker**, University of Leeds

Trina Robinson: Archival Bodies Out of Focus, **Lucas Williams**, Stanford University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite

Reconstructing the Electronic Superhighway: Radical Media Art and Techno-Community at the Margins of the Global Village

Chairs: **Kelly Donahey**, University of California, Irvine; **Erin Gordon**, The University of Texas at Austin

Unhampered by Our Polluted Earth: "Nationless Neutrality" in Nam June Paik's Broadcast Television Works, **Amy Kahng**, Stony Brook University

When social became digital: New media art and politics in Italy in the 1980s and 1990s., **Valeria Federici**, Center for Advance Study in the Visual Arts

Computational Love Letters during the AIDS Crisis, **Helena Shaskevich**, Kennesaw State University

The Everse Encounter: Embodiment and Agency in New Media Art, **Atanur Andic**, Özyeğin Üniversitesi and **Eser Selen**, Özyeğin Üniversitesi

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

Situated Knowledges and Trans-disciplinarity: Positionality and Embodiment in Methodologies of Art History and Visual Culture

CAA-GETTY INTERNATIONAL PROGRAM

Chair: **Cali Buckley**, College Art Association

Chair Remarks

Initial Construction of a Cross-National Art Histories: ASEAN Symposium on Aesthetics (1989), **Sarena Abdullah**, Universiti Sains Malaysia

When Museums Take a Stance: Refugee Crisis in Greece and the Practices of MOMus-Thessaloniki Museum of Photography, **Iro Katsaridou**, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki

Against the Extractivist Researcher: Feminist and Queer Readings from Latin America, **Georgina G Gluzman**

Preserving Egypt's Cultural Heritage Amidst Urban Development: A Situated Perspective on the Historic Cairo Cemetery, **Ali Mahfouz**, FalconViz

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton South
🌐 **Strategies of Camouflage Among Women Artists of Diversity**

Chairs: **Ayelet Zohar**, Tel Aviv University; **Miryam Sas**, UC Berkeley

Discussant: **Hanna Rose Shell**

Chair Remarks

Blur/Haze/Emergence: Japanese Women Photographers of the 1960s-1970, **Miryam Sas**, UC Berkeley

Lynette Yiadom Boakye's Monochrome Paintings as a Mode of Camouflage, **Ariel Rom**, Tel Aviv University

The Right to be 'Opaque': Camouflage in the Work of Joiri Minaya, **Federica Stevanin**, University of Padova

Coloration, Choirs and Camouflage: Revisiting Yamashiro Chikako's "Chorus of Melodies", **Ayelet Zohar**, Tel Aviv University

9:00 AM –10:29 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse A

🌐 **Vantage Point: Artist Panel 1**

Chairs: **Elyse Longair**, Chair, Services to Artists Committee, CAA; **Matthew L. Conboy**, George Mason University

Chair Remarks

Rachel Portesi, **Rachel Portesi**, Rachel Portesi Photography

Ana Kapodistria, **Ana Kapodistria**, Ana Kapodistria

Christina Yao, **Christina Yao**, Alberta University of the Arts

Randy Matusow, **Randy Matusow**, RANDY MATUSOW PHOTOGRAPHY

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
Visions of Ancestral Spirits

Chair: **Sarah Stolte**, Edgewood College

Chair Remarks

Cauleen Smith's Egungun: Ancestor Can't Find Me (2017), **Ola Wlusek**, John and Mable Ringling Museum of Art

Visualizing Ancestry Through Restorative Design, **Omari Souza**

For the Benefit of all Sentient Beings, **Peter Makela**, Edgewood College

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
What Lies Ahead for Later Nineteenth-Century French Art

Chair: **Michelle Foa**, Tulane University

Chair Remarks

How Many Ways Can You Exploit a Maid, **Todd Cronan**

Enacted biography and the melancholy of 'last paintings' from the Romantic age to the Fin-de-siècle, **Marc Gotlieb**, Williams College

Dredging the Waters of Empire in Paul Signac's Ports, **Kelly Presutti**, Cornell University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

🌐 **WOMEN ART DEALERS AND COLLECTORS PROMOTING NON-WESTERN ARTS: THE CASE OF PRE-COLUMBIAN ART AND THE INDIGENOUS ARTS OF NORTH AMERICA**

THE INTERNATIONAL ART MARKET STUDIES ASSOCIATION

Chair: **Caterina Toschi**

Chair Remarks

Inés Amor and the Early Years of the Galería de Arte Mexicano, **Eréndira Derbez**

Mrs. Freyer at home and abroad: Introducing America to colonial Peru, **Kathryn Santner**, Denver Art Museum

The Scholar-Collector: Elizabeth Easby, **Jennifer A. Jolly**, Ithaca College

Fiamma Vigo and the promotion of Latin American art in Italy between the 1950s and 1960s: The case of Peruvian art., **Biancalucia Maglione**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

10 Years of ADVA Journal: Hindsight, Insights, Futures Thinking

DIASPORIC ASIAN ART NETWORK

Chairs: **Alice M. Jim**, Concordia University; **Alexandra Chang**, Rutgers University Newark State University of New Jersey

Discussant: **Marissa Largo**, York University

In Relation to Asian American, **Tom Wolf**

Okinawan Diaspora Indigenous Solidarities and the Shimanchu Hajichi Tattoo Revival, **Laura L. Kina**, DePaul University

In Relation to Ocean Worlds, **Thomas Looser**, New York University

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite
Art Beyond Games: Critical and Creative Approaches in New Media Art

Chairs: Victoria E. Szabo, Duke University; **Joyce J. Rudinsky**, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Deus in Machina: Bill Viola's Night Journey, **Ronald R. Bernier**, Wentworth Institute of Technology

Controller Effect: Teleporting into the Game Art as Virtual Citizen, **Bowie Bo Gyung Kim**, Stony Brook University

Simema: Radical Passivity in Freudenheim's Schema, **Douglas Stark**, University of Texas at Arlington

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North
Art History and the Apocalypse

SERVICES TO HISTORIANS OF VISUAL ARTS COMMITTEE

Chairs: Carmen Ripolles; **Chanhee Choi**, University of New Mexico; **Jenna Ann Altomonte**

Discussant: Sabrina De Turk, University of Maine; **Kirstin Ringelberg**, Elon University

Chair Remarks

Embodied Engagement as a Response to Global Crises, **Susannah Kite Strang**, Arrupe College of Loyola University Chicago

On the Rocks: Shipwrecks & Art History, **Justin Wolff**, University of Maine

No Art History on a Dead Planet, **Kirstin Ringelberg**, Elon University

Art History and the Apocalypse: A Decolonial Re-Oriented, **Colin Tucker**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

Artists' Legacy Stewardship: field-building efforts

Chair: Solana Chehtman, Joan Mitchell Foundation

Discussant: Rachel Middleman, California State University Chico

Grief, Memory, Legacy: Field-building through partnerships, **Daisy Holman**, The Estate of Elizabeth Murray

Sustaining a Legacy: Modeling Creative Legal Structures for Artist Estates, **Yayoi Shionoiri**, Powerhouse Arts

Creating Community Through Discussion Groups, **Julia Schwartz**, Julia Schwartz Fine Art Services

Bay Area Women Artists' Legacy Project: A Roadmap through 50 Years to Shape Artists' Legacies, **Jan Wurm**, Berkeley Art Project

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

Circulations: Questions in Global Visual Culture

Chair Remarks

The Ethiopian Story of Mary and Its Pictorial Program, **Jutta Sperling**, Hampshire College

A Counterfeit Infinity: Bay Area Video Art and the Digital Aesthetic, **Kaitlin Forcier**

(Non) Resident Alien: Global Visual Cultures and the Biography of a Hindu God in Nineteenth-Century Britain and America, **Ujaan Ghosh**, The Ohio State University

The "Pictorial Turn" in Ilkhanid Iran: Jami al-Tawarikh's illustrations as a dialogue to Global pictorial history, **Xinyu Liang**, Rice University

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse A

Collective Work: Funding and Collaborating on International Projects and Research

STUDENT AND EMERGING PROFESSIONALS COMMITTEE

Chairs: Yizhuo Li, Universität Wien; **Ehryn Torrell**, Bath Spa University; **Sarena Abdullah**, Universiti Sains Malaysia

It's Always Nice to Meet People: The Gästeatelier Krone Aarau and Switzerland's Evolving Arts Scene of International Collaboration, **Shramona Maiti**, School of Arts and Aesthetics and **Wenzel Haller**, Arbeitsgruppe Gästeatelier Krone / artists in residence ch

Realities of Research: Working with The Society of Ambiance Makers and Elegant Persons (La SAPE) in Kinshasa, Democratic Republic of the Congo, **Kristen Laciste**, Fashion Institute of Technology

Enhancing Climate Resilience through Collaborative Innovation: The NicaAgua App, **Qiuwen Li**, Santa Clara University

Rethinking Funding and Collaboration Through Digital and Media Arts, **Sharifa Lafon**, University of Colorado Boulder

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman

🌐 **Critical AI Literacy in Art and Design Education and Practice**

PROFESSIONAL PRACTICES COMMITTEE

Chairs: Leigh-Ann Pahapill, Bowling Green State University; Charles Kanwischer, Bowling Green State University; Michael Grillo, University of Maine

Chair Remarks

Remystification and Demystification, Zhenzhen Qi, University of Connecticut - Digital Media & Design Department

The transformative power of AI gaze in art-making: creativity and ethics, Daniel Raffini

Critical AI Literacy in Design Education: Navigating Ethical Integration and Collaborative Creativity, Danilo Ljubomir Bojić, Winona State University

Emergent Phenomena in AI and its Implications in Art Pedagogy, Niloofer Gholamrezaei, Regis College

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite

🌐 **Decolonial Jewish Practice in Art and Visual Culture After Gaza**

Chairs: Nicholas Mirzoeff, New York University; Jill H. Casid, University of Wisconsin-Madison

Nightmares, Gil Hochberg, Columbia University

Roundtable discussion, Alexandra Juhasz, The MIT Press

Roundtable discussion, Zoé Samudzi, Clark University

Arab Jews, British India, and the Family Archive, Amanda Shubert, University of Wisconsin - Madison

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

🌐 **Divine Senses: Exploring Sensorial Experiences in Religious Contexts throughout the Premodern Iberian World**

SOCIETY FOR IBERIAN GLOBAL ART

Chairs: Hannah Maryan Thomson, University of California Los Angeles; Teresa Martínez Martínez, University of Padova

Una Confusión Devota: Soundscapes of Late Colonial Mexican Festivals, JoAnna Reyes, Arizona State University

Embodied Devotion and Pilgrimage: The Sensorial Experience of the Virgin in Thirteenth-Century Castile and Aragon, Cristina Aldrich, The Institute of Fine Arts, New York University

Sacred Touch: Pilgrimage Tokens and Seals as Apotropaic Conduits for Divine Transformation in Ireland and Spain in the Middle Ages, Laura McCloskey Wolfe, The University of West Georgia

The Empire of the Sun: How the Incan Worship of Nature Continued After Catholic Conversion, Emi Higashiyama

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

🌐 **Enchantments, Transmissions, Infections: A Poetics of Knowledge by Latin American Women Artists**

Chairs: Gabriela Aceves-Sepúlveda, Simon Fraser University; Claudia Pederson

Discussant: Maria Fernandez

The “Bichi Project”, materiality, immaterialities, realities, intelligence, and data., Pat Badani, ISEA International

Exploring Biopolitical Landscapes through Multispecies Collaboration in Alexandra Gelis’ Work, Analays Alvarez Hernandez

Throwing a stone in the techno artistic pond (or some notes on the dialogue between art, technology and living matters in Latin-America), Mariela Yeregui, Rhode Island School of Design

Intuition, Modern Technologies, and Incommensurability in Lourdes de la Riva’ Work., Marivi Veliz

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

🌐 **Envisioning Feminist Media Archaeology**

Chair: Gillian Young, Wofford College

Chair Remarks

Crafting Media History from the Mundane, Christina Corfield, University at Buffalo SUNY

The Religious Media Archaeology of Belkis Ayón, Benjamin O Murphy, Case Western Reserve University

Virtual, By Other Means: Cao Fei’s Nova, Tung Chau, Yale University

Fluid Histories: A Feminist Alternative to Media Archaeology, Jessica Bardsley, New York University

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Mercury Ballroom

🌐 **Gender, Class, and Empire: Women's Roles and the Representation of Animals in 18th and 19th c. Art**

Chair Remarks

THE SHEPHERDESS IN THE COLONIES: YOUNG WOMEN IN THE PASTORAL MODE, **Patricia Johnston**, College of The Holy Cross

Bridging Relationships: Pet Animals as Connectors in Eighteenth-Century British Portraiture, **Luba Stephanía Kozak**, University of Regina

Vincent van Gogh, Jules Michelet, and Working-Class Women, **Christa Rose DiMarco**, New College of Florida

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton South
🌐 How Has Decolonizing Art History Worked for You?

ART HISTORIANS OF SOUTHERN CALIFORNIA

Chair: Meggie Morris, San Diego Miramar College

Chair Remarks

Decolonizing Art History: An HBCU Case Study, **Elizabeth C Hamilton**, Fort Valley State University

Naawsidoong Mino Nawendiwin (Building Good Relationships): Decolonized Teaching and Student Mental Health, **Lesley Thornton-Cronin**, Humber College

From Binarism to Dispersal Histories: Contemporary art from the Middle East, **Azadeh Sarjoughian**

Decolonizing Art History in Israel-Palestine, **Ronit Milano**, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev and **Nissim Gal**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

♦ Images made by Post-Secondary Teachers of Painting

Workshop Leader: Morgan T. Paine, Florida Gulf Coast University

Chair Remarks

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East
On Crip Time

Chair: Zsafia Valyi-Nagy, Getty Research Institute

Chair Remarks

The Slow Productivity of Crip Advocacy in the Arts & Media, **Ashley Couto**, Travel+Leisure

Crip Vitae: Navigating Crip Feelings and Time as an Art Educator in Neoliberal Ableist Academia, **Eunkyung Hwang**, State University of New York at New Paltz

In the museum: Crip time as/is care time., **JoAnn Purcell**, Seneca

Madness and the Unromantic Road: a Non-Linear Artist Talk, **Catie Burrill**, School of the Art Institute of Chicago

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
On Other Media in Nineteenth-Century French Art

Chair: Hollis Clayson, Northwestern University

Chair Remarks

Printmaking at the Forefront in Nineteenth-Century France, **Laurel Garber**, Philadelphia Museum of Art and **Ashley E. Dunn**, Metropolitan Museum of Art

Collective Labors: Collaboration as Motif and Method in Pissarro's Prints, **Jillian Kruse**, Case Western Reserve University

Applied Art, Decoration and Design in the Nineteenth Century, **Amy F. Ogata**, University of Southern California

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Reimagining British Art: The Contributions of Transnational Artists in the 1950s, 60s, and 70s

Chair: Jessica Braum, Temple University

Chair Remarks

Temporalities in Conflict: Leopoldo Maler's Archive and the Reframing of British Art History, **Agustin Diez Fischer**, Independent Scholar

Imaginative Rediscovery: Destruction in Art and the Work of Rita Keegan, **Katherine Jackson**, Utah Valley University

Who's Afraid of Frank Bowling? Painting For and Against Anti-colonialism, **Artie Foster**, University of Illinois at Chicago

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite
Still Defining Roman Art

Chairs: Peter D De Staebler, Pratt Institute; **Anne Hrychuk Kontokosta**, NYU

Chair Remarks

The Art of Adaptation: Making Roman Gods in the Late Republic, **Alexander Ekserdjian**, Yale University

Still arguing for the Roman provinces, or how I learned to worry about victory monuments and love portable art, **Kimberly B. Cassibry**, Wellesley College

"Roman" Sarcophagi from the eastern Mediterranean and the "Art" of "Rome", **Sarah Madole Lewis**, CUNY - BMCC

Redefining Roman Imperial Portraiture in the Third Century, **Bailey Benson**, Boston University

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

The Case for Trans Visual Studies

Chair: Ace Lehner, University of Vermont

You Gotta Keep Fighting Girly: Trans Art Now, **Cyle Michalka Metzger**, Stanford University

Pressing On: Visual Narratives of Black Trans Activists' Fight for Existence, **Joshua Rashaad McFadden**, Rochester Institute of Technology

TIL WE ARE FULL, **Claudia Hermano**, University of New Mexico

On T4T as an Analytic, **Dylan Volk**, University of Michigan

Performing Glitter in Contemporary Trans Art, **Jason Le trans art beyond the figure**, **Emmett Ramstad**

*The Greatest Love: Vocal Confluence as Trans*Queer Resilience*, **Lorenzo Triburgo**, Oregon State University (Remote, LA-based) and **Sarah Van Dyck**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West

The Medical Gaze: Art, Corporeality, and Technology

Chairs: Elisabeth Sherman, International Center of Photography; **Sonia Epstein**, Museum of the Moving Image

Beyond Brain Imagery as Portraiture in Art: A Case for the Embodied and Relational Mind, **Cristina Albu**, University of Missouri-Kansas City

The Art of Medicine: Probing the Landscape Beneath the Skin, **Patricia J. Olynyk**, Washington University in St. Louis

An Invisible Pain: Migraines, Medical Imaging, and the Artistic Challenge to the Medical Gaze, **Hannah Forsythe**, The University of Texas at Austin

Looking Patiently: Donald Rodney Confronts the Medical Gaze, **Anna R Lovatt**, Southern Methodist University

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent

The Politics of the Archive: Reimagining the Histories of the Asian Diaspora

Chairs: Stephanie Kang, Rocky Mountain College of Art and Design; **Eunice Uhm**, San Diego State Univ

Chair Remarks

Alternative Albums of Asian America: Group Photographs Within the Archive, **Paulina Choh**, Stanford University

Zarina Bhimji and the Afterlives of Decolonial Aesthetics, **Priyanka Sen**, Cornell Department of Architecture

Fugitive Traces, Fugitive Bodies, and the Figure of Afong Moy, **Caitlin Meehye Beach**, The Graduate Center, CUNY

Archives of Counterinsurgency, **Ekan Hou**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

Unearthing Black History within Animation: A Conversation with The Hidden Critique

Chairs: Krystle Lemonias, Rowan University; **Marlon Wilson**, North Central College

Researcher, **Robby Gilbert**

Researcher Dr. Barbara Collinshttps://caa.confex.com/caa/2025/generalcomplete/extra/index.cgi?username=23071&EntryType=Paper&password=*cookie, **Barbara Collins**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

Vantage Point: Artists Panel 2

Chairs: Gina T. Washington; **Alexander Bostic**

Chair Remarks

Takeisha Jefferson, **Takeisha Jefferson**, Takeisha Art

Nina Hamberg, **Nina Hamberg**, Artists Thrive

Natalie Waldburger, **Natalie Waldburger**, Ontario College of Art & Design

Emergence, **Nadine Valcin**, Sheridan College Institute

12:00 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – 2nd Floor Promenade

"I Wish to Say" performance by Sheryl Oring

Panelists: **Sheryl A. Oring**, Wayne State University

12:00 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – 2nd Floor Promenade

△ Open Hours with CAA Publications

12:00 PM –8:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

Offsite – RSVP

Vantage Point: CAA Services to Artists Committee Exhibition

SERVICES TO ARTISTS COMMITTEE

Chair: **Elyse Longair**, Chair, Services to Artists Committee, CAA

Artist, **Nina Hamberg**, Artists Thrive

Artist, **Ana Kapodistria**, Ana Kapodistria

Artist, **Nadine Valcin**, Sheridan College Institute

Artist, **Christina Yao**, Alberta University of the Arts

Artist, **Rachel Portesi**, Rachel Portesi Photography

Artist, **Randy Matusow**, RANDY MATUSOW PHOTOGRAPHY

Artist / Performance Artist, **Natalie Waldburger**, Ontario College of Art & Design

12:30 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rotunda
Bryn Mawr College Department of History of Art Reception

Reception Contact: Margaret Kelly, Bryn Mawr College

12:30 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

Offsite – Columbia University Department of Art History and Archaeology Judith Lee Stronach Center, Room 825 Schermerhorn Hall

COLUMBIA UNIVERSITY DEPARTMENT OF ART HISTORY RECEPTION

Reception Contact: Faith Batidzirai, Columbia University; Zainab Bahrani, Columbia University

12:30 PM –2:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Hudson
△ Committee on Design

12:30 PM –2:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Lincoln
△ Committee on Women in the Arts

12:30 PM –3:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Main Entrance, Hotel Lobby

Gallery Tour - tickets required

12:30 PM –2:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Holland
△ International Committee

12:30 PM –2:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Green
△ Museum Committee

12:30 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse C

SBU Alumni & Friends Reception

Reception Contact: Barbara Frank, State University of New York Stony Brook; Mayurakshi Das

12:30 PM –2:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Harlem
△ Services to Historians of Visual Arts Committee

12:30 PM –2:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – East
△ Student and Emerging Professionals Committee

1:00 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East
△ Association for Latin American Art - Business Meeting

1:00 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

△ Association of Historians of American Art - Business Meeting

1:00 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse A

◆ CAA 114 submissions workshop with the Annual Conference Committee (ACC)

ANNUAL CONFERENCE COMMITTEE

Chair Remarks

1:00 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

△ Design Studies Forum - Business Meeting

1:00 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

△ Diasporic Asian Art Network - Business Meeting

1:00 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
△ Exploring Methodological Approaches in Art Market Studies - TIAMSA Business meeting

THE INTERNATIONAL ART MARKET STUDIES ASSOCIATION

The Primacy of Primary Market Data: Reading Archives in the Digital Age, **Amy Whitaker**, New York University

A Multitude of Consequences: Adopting a Performativity Approach in Art Market Studies, **Guy Schwegler**, University of Lucerne

1:00 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

△ Historians of British Art - Business Meeting

1:00 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West
△ **Historians of Islamic Art Association -
Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman
△ **Public Art Dialogue - Business Meeting**

2:00 PM –3:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – New York
■ **CAA Meet and Greet I**

Living Memorial: Exploring Tensions Between House and Museum, **Hui-Yi Yang**, Royal Danish Academy

OPEN HOUSE: Contemporary Artist's Interventions and Exhibitions at the Nineteenth Century Artist's Home and Studios of Thomas Cole, **Kate Menconeri**, Thomas Cole National Historic Site

New Eyes on Alice Austen, **Zoë Tirado**, Alice Austen House and **Karen D. Shelby**, Baruch College, City University of New York

An Artist's House Museum Behind Barbed Wire: the Mary Nohl House, Fox Point, Wisconsin, **Erin Hazard**, Illinois Institute of Technology

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

1975-2025: Revisiting 1970s Art and Feminism in Latin America and Eastern Europe

Chair: Agata Jakubowska, University of Warsaw

Chair Remarks

1975: Women Artists in Latin America Between Recognition and Revolution, **Andrea Giunta**, Universidad de Buenos Aires

The American Women Artists Project and the Silent Reception of Feminist Art in Brazil, **Talita Trizoli**

1975: A Women's Year in Art in the Socialist Yugoslavia Between Anti-Statism and Anti-Elitism, **Vesna Vukovic**, Independent Scholar

Women Artists among "Women of the Whole World" (WIDF Magazine), **Agata Jakubowska**, University of Warsaw

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West

ARTS + ARCHIVES TEACHING PARTNERSHIPS: FOSTERING ARTS STUDENTS' TRANSFORMATIVE USES OF SPECIAL COLLECTIONS AND ARCHIVES

ART LIBRARIES SOCIETY OF NORTH AMERICA

Chair: Jessica Pigza, Yale University

Discussant: Jessica Pigza, Yale University; **Heather Topcik**, Bard Graduate Center; **Julia Weist**; **Karolina Karlic**, University of California, Santa Cruz

Chair Remarks, **Jessica Pigza**, Yale University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
Art, Occultism, and Science in the Time of Hilma af Klint

Chairs: Fay Brauer, University of East London; **Linda Dalrymple Henderson**, The University of Texas at Austin

Re-evaluating Madge Gill: Mediumship, Music, Marconi and Mars, **Vivienne Roberts**, Vivienne Roberts

Juliette Bisson and the Art of Ectoplasm, **Serena Keshavjee**, University of Winnipeg

Invisible in Plain Sight: The Esoteric Content in Leonara Carrington's Oeuvre, **Susan Louise Aberth**

Images of the Spirit. Art, Science, and Occultism in the Visual Works of Carl Gustav Jung, **Sébastien Mantegari Bertorelli**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite

Beyond Utility: Rethinking the Value of Exhibition Photos in Art Historical Research and Curation

Chair: Lisa Gavell

Chair Remarks

Panelist - Archivist & Digital Preservation Specialist, **Michael Satalof**, Bard Graduate Center

Panelist - Archivist, **Ana Marie**, The Museum of Modern Art - MoMA

Panelist - Senior Digital Asset Specialist, Digital Asset Management, **Stephanie Post**, Metropolitan Museum of Art

Panelist - Keith Haring Director of Education and Public Engagement, **Alethea Rockwell**, New Museum of Contemporary Art

Panelist - Arts Librarian for Research Services, **Tess Colwell**, Yale University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

Artists' Sanctuaries: Engaging with House Museums

Chairs: Carolyn Loeb, RCAH, Michigan State University; **Andreas Luescher**, Bowling Green State University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

Brownness In Plain Sight / Brownness as Practice

Chairs: **Philomena Lopez Rivas**, Whittier College; **Kate Palmer Albers**, Whittier College

Discussant: **Danny Jauregui**

Chair Remarks

The Bronze Thrill, **Richard J. Powell**, Duke University

Refuge, **Nassem Navab**, City College of New York

Transformative Possibilities of Sensory Investigations: Raphael Montañez Ortiz's Immersive Events in 1967, **Ana Cristina Perry**, Oberlin College

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

🌐 Everyday and the Expression of Modernity: 19th-Century Architecture and Urbanism in the Islamic World

HISTORIANS OF ISLAMIC ART ASSOCIATION

Chairs: **Samira Fathi**, Michigan State University; **Maryam Heydarkhani**, University of Oxford, The Khalili Research Centre

Everyday Expectations: How a Sufi Revolutionist, Unknown Artists, and the King Envisioned a Modern House in Nineteenth-Century Iran, **Zeinab Tamassoki**

Claiming Space: Women Gathering Water in Modern Egypt (1895-1960), **Alexandra Schultz**, NYUAD

Word on the Street: Western-Language Signage in turn-of-the-century Egypt, **Stéphanie Hornstein**, Concordia University, Montréal

Visual Convergence: European Prints and Everyday Modernity in 19th-Century Qajar Architecture, **Fatemeh Tashakori**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

♦ Instagram for Scholars, Curators, and Art Historians

Workshop Leader: **Robin Cembalest**, Robin Cembalest Editorial Strategies

Chair Remarks

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
Natural Disasters and Artistic Innovation in Colonial Peru, 1650-1700

Chair: **Katherine Anne Mills**

Discussant: **Michael J. Schreffler**, University of Notre Dame

Chair Remarks

Rebuilding Cuzco: Local Stonemasons in the aftermath of the 1650 Earthquake, **Katherine Anne Mills**

Sacralizing the Collapse. The Birth of the Franciscan Cult to Our Lady of Miracle after the 1650 Earthquake., **Lucila Iglesias**, Universidad de Buenos Aires

Reforming the Cusco Bishopric: Manuel de Mollinedo y Angulo's Artistic Patronage (1675-1700), **Andrés De Leo**

Surviving the Earthquake: The Ceiling of the San Pedro Apóstol Temple in Andahuaylillas, **Diana Castillo Cerf**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton South

🌐 Open Session for Emerging Scholars

ASSOCIATION FOR LATIN AMERICAN ART

Chairs: **Gina McDaniel Tarver**, Texas State University-San Marcos; **Luis J. Gordo Peláez**, Society for Iberian Global Art

Chair Remarks

Potosí's Silver Age, an Age of Wind: The Wayrachina as an Icon of Indigenous Technology and Global Extractivism, **Nicole Jozwik**, Tulane University

Extractive Enterprises: The Spectral Spectacles of Tlachiquero Subjectivity in Mexican Photography, **Joshua Gomez**, University of Illinois Chicago

On Blackness and the Everyday: René Peña's Photographic Explorations of Race in Cuba, **Chasitie Brown**

(Re)Mapping Social Histories in Sandy Rodriguez's Codex Rodriguez-Mondragón, **Angela Pastorelli-Sosa**, University of California, Berkeley

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

Queer Listening and Sonic Arts

Chair: **Caitlin Woolsey**, Clark Art Institute

Susan Silton's Voice, **Natilee Harren**, University of Houston

Miss Communication: Identity, Voice, and Queer Conversation in the work of Wu Tsang and Fred Moten, **Thea Ballard**, Duke

Queer Recoding of Asian American Stereotypes in TT Takemoto's Semiotics of Sab (2011), **Kate Korroch**, Visual Studies, Ind. Scholar

Beating: Sound Installation as Queer Methodology, **Charles Eppley**, Arizona State University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Reconceptualizing Narrative and Representation in Figurines

Chair: Alan Rauch, UNC Charlotte

Chair Remarks

The Figurinae of London: Images for the Million, **Alan Rauch**, University of North Carolina at Charlotte

Misrepresentations, Miniaturization, and Maulings: Reconsidering Staffordshire Potteries The Death of Monrow, **Alyse Muller**, Columbia University

Figurative Anxieties: Saint-Cloud Cane Handles, Chinoiserie, and "Things", **Emily Walz**, New York Public Library

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

Reframing Fashion Photography: Between the Magazine Page and the Gallery Wall

Chairs: Kaitlin Booher, Museum of Modern Art; **Sasha Whittaker**, Princeton University

Discussant: Elspeth Brown, University of Toronto

Consumerism, Copyright, and Publicity in Thérèse Bonney's 1920s Fashion Photographs, **Caroline M. Riley**, University of California, Davis

Fashion Photography in Modern Japanese Department Store Magazines, **Nozomi Naoi**, Yale-NUS College

Fashion, urbanity, and a new era: Han Youngsoo's street photography and the postwar South Korea, **Boyoung Chang**, Independent Scholar

From Peripheral to Central: The changing status of fashion photographs within the V&A, **Susanna Brown**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East
Reframing Madness: Arts at the Intersection of Mental Health and Mad Studies

Chair: Velebita Koričančić, Anahuac University Mexico / National Autonomous University of Mexico

Chair Remarks

From Data to Art: Exploring Mental Health Narratives of Asian Americans through Disaggregated Data and 3D Printed Sculptures, **Chanika Svetvilas**, Artist

Madness, Aesthetics, and Politics: Challenging Primitivism with Tosquelles and Fanon, **Elena Vogman**

Democratic Therapy, **W. J. T. Mitchell** and **Valérie Rousseau**, American Folk Art Museum

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

Revivalism, Labor, and Discourses on Craft in Indigenous Arts of Southwest Asia and North Africa: Then and Now

Chairs: Nancy N.A. Demerdash, College For Creative Studies; **Lacy A Murphy**, Washington University in Saint Louis

Discussant: Sara Rahnama

Chair Remarks

Crafting Colonial Identity at the General Exhibition of the Centenary of Algeria (1930), **Lacy A Murphy**, Washington University in St. Louis

Algerian Weaving Workshops and Women's Agency under French Colonialism, **Maureen G. Shanahan**, James Madison University

Weaving Resistance in Ait Hichem: Amazigh Carpet Workshops and Algerian Political Activism, **Cynthia Becker**, Boston University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North

The Form of Immortality: Painting and Calligraphy in Fifteenth- to Eighteenth-Century China

Chairs: An-Yi Pan; **Yuhua Ding**, Wellesley College

Discussant: Kathleen Ryor

Birthday Celebration and Immortal Paintings in the Imperial Court of the Ming Dynasty, **Kayi Ho**, The Chinese University of Hong Kong

Color as a Holistic Medicine: Lan Ying's Boneless Landscape, **Ying Zhu**, Kress Foundation Department of Art History at the University of Kansas

Female Beauty, Wine, and Antiquarianism: Temporal Transformation of the Immortal Magu, **Yuhua Ding**, Wellesley College

Engraving for Eternity: The Qianlong Emperor's Brushstrokes on Stone, **Gillian Zhang**, Boston University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

The Form of the Thing: Word and Image and the Scholar

INTERNATIONAL ASSOCIATION OF WORD AND IMAGE STUDIES

Chair: Tilo Reifenstein, International Association of Word and Image Studies

Researching the Afterlife of Slavery: Interweaving Art and Scholarly Practice in the Writings of Saidiya Hartman and Christina Sharpe, **Lea Weckert**, University of Siegen

Ornament, OrLand: Radical Profanations, **Ruo Jia**, IfWorks

Beyond explanation and description : What can poetic evocation contribute to the ethnography of a place's social imaginaries ?, **Pavel Kunysz**, Université de Liège

To imagine a microscopic worm crawling through the pores of your arm, **Maria Fernandez Pello**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

The Ongoing Life of Refuse in Art

AMERICAN INSTITUTE FOR CONSERVATION OF HISTORIC AND ARTISTIC WORKS

Chair: Rebecca Anne Rushfield

Discussant: Andrea Kirsh

Chair Remarks

Conservation Lost and Found: Preservation Strategies for the Art of Trash, **Caitlin Gozo Richeson**, Museum of Modern Art

Conservation in/as Decay: On the Perverse Continuity of Daniel Spoerri's Tableau-pièges, **Josephine Ellis**, Bern University of the Arts

Conserving and Analyzing Canned Waste: Piero Manzoni's Merda d'artista (1961), **Sophia Maxine Farmer**, University of Kentucky

Michael Heizer's Effigy Tumuli: Autodestructive Land Reclamation Sculpture, **Shannon Bewley**, Boston University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Mercury Ballroom

The Urgency and Challenges of Academic Freedom, hosted by The Art Bulletin

PUBLICATIONS COMMITTEE

Chair: Halle O'Neal, University of Edinburgh

Roundtable Participant George Agbo, **George Emeka Agbo**, Edinburgh College of Art, University of Edinburgh

Roundtable Participant; Editor in Chief, The Art Bulletin, **Christy J. Anderson**, University of Toronto

Roundtable Participant Wenshing Chou, **Wenshing Lucia Chou**, Hunter College

Roundtable Participant Ünver Rüstem, **Ünver Rüstem**

Roundtable Participant from; The Art Bulletin Editorial Board, **Maria Taroutina**, Brown University, Dept. of Slavic Studies

Roundtable Participant; The Art Bulletin Editorial Board, **Elizabeth Dospel Williams**, Museum of Fine Arts, Boston

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite

The visible and invisible in secular and religious art

ASSOCIATION FOR TEXTUAL SCHOLARSHIP IN ART HISTORY

Chairs: Liana Cheney, Association for Textual Scholarship in Art History; **Tina Waldeier Bizzarro**

Chair Remarks

Aeneas's Vision, Envisioned by Raphael, **Charles Burroughs**

Carthusian Visions: Pontormo at the Florentine Certosa di Galluzzo, **Lynette Bosch**

Color in Michelangelo's Doni Tondo and Pontormo's Deposition, **Thomas MacPherson**

The Young Degas and the Sea: A Dantean Journey, **Vasile Ovidiu Prejmerean**, University of Fribourg

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman

What Is Public Art For?

PUBLIC ART DIALOGUE

Chairs: DeWitt A. Godfrey, Colgate University; **Rachel Boate**, Colgate University, Department of Art & Art History

Conundrum of Permanence in Public Art, **Jennifer McGregor**, McGregor Consulting

Past, Present, and Future: Public Art in Atlanta, **Monica M. Obniski**, High Museum of Art

Serving Democracy in East Germany – A Public Art Student Project, **Alessa Paluch**

De-Designing Public Art, **Adam Frelin**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Women and Letters

Chair: Isabel Mehl, Freie Universität Berlin

'A very important event!': the role of the letter in Gwen John's artistic practice, **Helena Anderson**, University of Bristol

My Dear Lover: Sharon Hayes' Letters to an Unnamed You, **Ksenia M. Soboleva**, The New School

Intertwining Outer and Inner Worlds: The Visual Letters of Chantal Akerman and Fiona Tan, **Ariane Noel de Tilly**, Savannah College of Art & Design

2:30 PM –4:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

Women Artists in Modern Movements

WILLIAM MORRIS SOCIETY IN THE UNITED STATES

Chair: Lauren McCardel, Ursinus College--Berman Museum of Art

Free Wheeling: Women Artists and the American Print Renaissance, **Cora Chalaby**, University College London

Lois Mailou Jones: International Artist of the Harlem Renaissance, **Dana Hogan**, Duke University

Mediating Cross-cultural Dialogue in the Works of Eileen Gray (1878-1976) and Pan Yuliang (1895-1977), **Sandy Ng**, Hong Kong Polytechnic University

Doubly Transgressive: New Figuration and Pop Women in Brazil and Argentina, **Carolina Vieira Filippini Curi**, University of Campinas

3:00 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

Offsite – Sotheby's Institute of Art - 570 Lexington Ave

Vantage Point: Performance by Natalie Majaba Waldburger

Chair: Elyse Longair, Chair, Services to Artists Committee, CAA

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North
🌐 **"The Incomplete" in the Long Nineteenth Century**

INTERDISCIPLINARY NINETEENTH-CENTURY STUDIES

Chair: Nancy Rose Marshall

Chair Remarks

Gathered Cloth and Paper Fragments: Scrapbooks, Disability, and the Piecework of Self-making, **Mariah Kupfner**, Penn State Harrisburg

Drugs, Dyes, and Delicacies: An Expansive Disability Studies Approach to Raphaele Peale's Still Life Paintings, **Phillippa Pitts**, Boston University

A Lost "Mirror of Slavery:" Black Geographies and the Antebellum American Landscape, **Rachel Burke**

Incomplete Representations: Iran's Pavilion in the 19th-century world fairs, **Maryam Heydarkhani**, University of Oxford, The Khalili Research Centre

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite
(Re)making Sacred Matter: Recycling and Repurposing in the Material Lives of Icons

Chair: Rachel Saunders, Princeton University

Discussant: Halle O'Neal, University of Edinburgh

Chair Remarks

Transmitting Tradition: The Premodern Preservation of the Takao Mandara, **Miriam Chusid**, University of Washington

The Portraits of Shōkū Shōnin, **Daniel Borengasser**, University of Massachusetts Boston

Birds, Flowers, and Buddhist Botany in Edo Japan, **Rachel Saunders**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
Anna Mahler, Sculptor: Vienna, London, Los Angeles, and Spoleto.

Chair: Matthew Stephenson, The Estate of Anna Mahler

Discussant: Diane V Silverthorne

Anna Mahler, Artist in Exile – the Vienna-London years and beyond, **Diane V Silverthorne**

Unveiling the Anna Mahler Photographic Archive, **Michele Drascek**, The Estate of Anna Mahler

Anna Mahler by Marina Mahler. 'In-conversation' with Marina Fistoulari Mahler, daughter of Anna Mahler. A Personal View., **Marina Mahler**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West
Art as Shifting Knowledge?: Histories of Science, Medicine, and Sinophone Art

Chairs: Yizhuo Li, University of Vienna; Jiaqi Kang, University of Oxford

Chair Remarks

Chevreul, Color Juxtaposition, & the 'Flat Tints' of Chinese Painting, **Delanie Joy Linden**, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Painting for medicine: works created for the provisioning of healthcare in Ming China, **Chansol Park**, New York University

Art for Medical Knowledge? Illustrated Materia Medica Books in Late Ming China, **Ruiying Gao**, Wake Forest University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

Art Factories, Community-led Cultural Centers, and Third Spaces in Repurposed Buildings

Chair: Sabir Khan

Chair Remarks

Arts In Rem: El Bohio Community and Cultural Center 1978-2001, **Elise Armani**, Stony Brook University

Toma Cultural; Radio Verdura and the Power of Collective Creativity, **Robin Garcia**, University of Virginia

Resistance in Chronotopical bodies at "Dar Jacir" Cultural Center and in Basel Abbas and Ruanne Abou-Rahme's Until We Became Fire and Fire Us, **Asia Benedetti**, Ca' Foscari University of Venice

Outside Barcelona, **Arnau Pascual Carreras**, Universitat Politècnica De Catalunya (UPC)

Space and Visual Culture in American Hackerspaces, **Ben Jameson-Ellsmore**, University of Virginia

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite
Artificial Suns: Photography and Alternative Illumination

Chair: Isabelle Lynch, University of Pennsylvania

Chair Remarks

Fantastical Capture: Surveillance and Light in 1840s America, **Sarah Parsons**, York University

Feng Li's White Night and the History of Electricity in China, **Ye Chen Zhao**, Art Institute of Chicago

The Problem of Two Prints: Photographing Depth in the Cave and the Mine Shaft, **Jenna Marvin**, Cornell University

Alternate Illuminations: Electricity, Darkness, Visualization, **Ted Hiebert**, Toronto Metropolitan University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

Building Futures: Art, Architecture, and Social Visions Across Time and Place.

Chair Remarks

Socialist Futurism(s): Utopian Art and Design in Yugoslavia and Beyond, **Cindy Torgesen**, Southern Utah University

Tracing A Type: Isfahan's Legacy and Early Qajar Palace Architecture, **Samira Fathi**, Michigan State University

Architectures of Improvement: Housing the Malaria Eradication in Venezuela, 1958-1965, **Piergianna Mazzocca**, Cornell Department of Architecture

Baked in the Sun and Hiding in Plain Sight: Native American Public Art in Phoenix, **Danya Epstein**, Northern Arizona University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Building the Belle Époque

Chairs: David Bijan Sadighian, Harvard University; **Juan Pablo Pekarek**, Université Paris I - Panthéon-Sorbonne

Chair Remarks

Darker than A Nocturne: Whistler's Aesthetics of Pollution, **Noam Gonen**, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev

The National Bavarian Museum: Historicity and the Politics of Nationhood, **Faraz Olfat**, Yale University

Maison Carlhian in Buenos Aires. Decorating and building hôtels particuliers in the global Belle Époque., **Juan Pablo Pekarek**, Université Paris I - Panthéon-Sorbonne

The Architecture of French Imperialism in Ottoman Jerusalem, **Adi Meyerovitch**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton South
Civic Gestures in Contemporary Cuban Art

Chair: Guillermina De Ferrari, University of Wisconsin - Madison

Chair Remarks

Revisualizing the Russian Axis in Cuban Visual Arts, **Jacqueline Loss**

Havana's Stray Dogs, **Esther Whitfield**, Brown University, Department of Comparative Literature

Reynier Leyva Novo's Minor Gestures, **Guillermina De Ferrari**, University of Wisconsin - Madison

The Art of Giving: The General Economy of Cuban Art and New Virtual Communities **Mailyn Machado**, **Mailyn Machado Mayea**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
Complicating Perception: Re-Coding Time and Place

Chair: Anna Stielau, California Institute of Technology

Chair Remarks

Probing the Nature of Existence: Joan Brassil's Kinetic Materialization of Time and Light, **Jessica Braum**, Temple University

The Mountain and the Mandala: Paul Pfeiffer's Fragment of a Crucifixion (After Francis Bacon) and the Chakrasamvara Mandala, **Caroline Picard**, University of Oxford, Faculty of Asian and Middle Eastern Studies

Here But Not Yet Now: Re-Presenting the Khoisan in South African Art and Visual Activism, **Anna Stielau**, California Institute of Technology

Precarious Encounters & Connoting Ephemera of Trauma: An Examination of Interwar Sapphic Portraiture, **Lily F. Scott**, Temple University

4:30 PM –6:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom East

■ **Distinguished Scholar Session**

Chair: Lisa E. Farrington, John Jay College, City University of New York

Panelists: Jack Flam; Deborah Cullen-Morales, Mellon Foundation; Jennifer Farrell; Julie H. Reiss, Independent Scholar; Linda Serrone, Artist; CITYsized Murals; John Yau

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

Encounters with Medium: Art, Travel, and Identity Formations in Twentieth-Century China

Chairs: Amanda S. Wangwright; Yang Wang, University of Colorado Denver

Discussant: Juliane Noth, Freie Universität Berlin

Chair Remarks

Discovering Media and Meaning in Wartime Artistic Expeditions throughout China's Rural Interior, Amanda S. Wangwright

Visions of Tibet: Tensions between Artistic Experimentations and Constructing State Narratives, Yi Yi Mon (Rosaline) Kyo, University of California, Santa Cruz

Meeting Jiangnan: The Chang'an School's Engagement with Ink Painting Through the Southern Tour, Yang Wang, University of Colorado at Denver

Beijing to Hangzhou: Maryn Varbanov and the Significance of Mixed Media in Post-Mao China, Keyu Yan, The Ohio State University Department of History of Art

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

Future Imaginaries: Indigenous Art, Fashion, Technology

Chairs: Suzanne Fricke; Amy Beth Scott, Autry Museum of the American West

Chair Remarks

New Terrain: Indigenous Futurism and the City of Angels, Amy Beth Scott, Autry Museum of the American West

Future is Land: Visual Indigenous Critiques of Settler Capitalism, Kristen Dorsey, UCLA

Steel Medicine: Indigenous Eco Knowledge in Contemporary Art Practice, Margaret Jacobs, Margaret Jacobs

Riff, Ground, Dream: New Ideas in Indigenous Futurisms, Suzanne Fricke

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

On Titles

Chairs: Alexandra Letvin, Princeton University Art Museum; Sarah Cash, National Gallery of Art

Manet's Woman with a Cigarette from 1883 to 2025, Alexandra Letvin, Princeton University Art Museum

Re-introducing the Subject: Retitling at the Baltimore Museum of Art, Virginia Anderson, Baltimore Museum of Art

Sargent and Spain and the Roma People, Sarah Cash, National Gallery of Art

Titles and Public-Facing Narratives, Ginia Sweeney, Art Institute of Chicago

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

Once Upon a Queer Time: Speculative Histories in the Work of 2SLGBTQ+ Artists

Chair: Genevieve Flavelle, Queens University-Kingston

Chair Remarks

Unearthing the Polish Lesbian: Speculative Lesbian Histories in Liliana Zeic's "Sourcebook", Aleksandra Gajowy, University College Dublin

Dream-Work as Form: Looking at Looking for Langston, Louis Shankar, University College London

Black Trans Feminist Memories in Tourmaline's "Atlantic is a Sea of Bones", Jordan Mason Mayfield, Columbia University

Threading Archives: Philipp Guffler's Textile Speculations, Simone Stirner, Vanderbilt University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

Race and the Shape of Revolutionary Art: Between Avant-Garde and Early Soviet Visual Cultures

Chair: Olivia Crough, Harvard University

Discussant: Olivia Crough, Harvard University

Chair Remarks

Goncharova's Primitivism: A Search for the Native Body, Mina Magda, University of Michigan

From the Black Square to the Black Belt Thesis: On the Blackness of Black in Malevich's Painting, Jonathan Flatley

Blackness in Constructivism, **Christina H. Kiaer**, Northwestern University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

Restitution Beyond Repatriation: Rethinking African Art and the Question of Decolonizing Museums

Chair: Clement Akpang, Cross River University of Technology

From Africa Palace to AfricaMuseum: Decolonizing King Leopold's Museum of the Congo Free State, **Karen D. Shelby**, Baruch College, City University of New York

Ethical Retail Sourcing and Manufacturing Framework: A Strategic Approach to Cultural Restitution of African Heritage Objects, **Nasozi Kakembo**

Reimagining Ethnographic Objects: Moving Beyond Repatriation in Decolonizing Museums, **Nicole Crawford**, University of Wyoming Art Museum

Decolonial Curatorship in African Museums: Repatriation and a Reimagining of the Museum, **Danielle Becker**, Rhodes University

Troubling Missionary Legacies in the Contemporary World: African Objects Owned by Christian Congregations in Dutch Ethnographic Museums, **Yang Hu**, Universiteit Utrecht

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East
Space Art in the Anthropocene

Chair: Katarzyna Balug, Florida International University

Chair Remarks

The Moon Rocks of New Jersey: Ecocritical Art and the Legacy of Lunar Exploration, **Andrew Vielkind**, Ithaca College

en el radar: ground-based observations in Arecibo, Puerto Rico., **Yazmín Crespo Claudio**, University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign

Souvenirs of Earth: Catastrophe and Hope in the Art of Dawn DeDeaux, **Allison K. Young**, Louisiana State University

Revisiting the "Pillars of Creation", **Caleb Allen**, University of Minnesota, Twin Cities

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman

☉ Sustaining Legacy: The Elisabet Ney Museum's Engagement into the 21st century

Chair: Jacquelyn McDonald, University of Texas at Dallas

German- American salonnière Elisabet Ney: Berlin, München, Austin, **Jacquelyn Delin McDonald**

Sursum! The Evolution of the Elisabet Ney Museum's Programming and Community Outreach Initiatives, **Lindsay Barras**

Ney's Legacy Experienced Through the Work of Contemporary Artists, **Jade Walker**

The Bathing of the Sphinx, **Renee Lai and Rosa Nussbaum**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse A

☉ The Hydra: The Many Approaches to Generative AI in the Art and Design Classroom

Chair: Mary F. Zawadzki, University of Mississippi

Brushstrokes and Bytes: Evolving a Limited AI Use Policy in Art Appreciation Courses, **Ansley Simmons**, Albany State University

Art History by Bot?: Grading Generative A.I.'s Notetaking, Researching, and Writing Skills, **Kris K. Belden-Adams**, University of Memphis

Exploring UX Design Trainees with Generative AI: A Pedagogical Perspective, **Yi-Fan Chen**, Farmingdale State College - SUNY

Generative AI Goes to the Historical Society, **Gretchen R. Sinnett**, Salem State University

First Things First: Scaffolding assignments to foster creativity and critical thinking around generative AI, **Jennifer Kowalski**, Lehigh University

Staging Irishness: Stereotype, Identity, and Generative AI, **Judith M Stapleton**, University of Notre Dame

Unleashing Creativity and Precision: AI Tools in Graphic Design Education, **Golnoush Behmanesh**, Georgia State University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

Ungovernable Bodies

Chair: Shing-Kwan Chan, Princeton University

Chair Remarks

Illustrating Women in the Tales of the Prophets in Sixteenth-Century Islamic Manuscripts, **Ozlem Yildiz**, Temple University

Obsession, Opium, and the Otherworld: Tactical Morality as a Way of Depicting Male Same-Sex Desire in Nineteenth-Century Chinese Art, **Shing-Kwan Chan**, Princeton University

Photography Without the Prick of Desire: Wolfgang Tillmans' i didn't inhale (1997) and the Post-Psychoanalytic Subject, **James Michael Levinsohn**, University of Toronto

Eccentric Bodies: Decolonizing Female Corporeality in Latin American Women's Outsider Art, **Velebita Koričančić**, Anahuac University Mexico / National Autonomous University of Mexico

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

◆ Unraveling Accessibility: Deaf and Disability Arts"

Workshop Leader: Fran Flaherty, Anthropology of Motherhood

Chair Remarks

4:30 PM –6:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Visibility and Visuality after 'the Transgender Tipping Point'

Chair: Dylan Volk, University of Michigan

If a trans person walks into the room and no one recognizes them, do they make a sound?, **Kirstin Ringelberg**, Elon University

The Fog of (Gender) War, **Chelsea Thompto**, Virginia Tech

Black Transmasculinity +, **Cecilio M Cooper**, Science History Institute

Ways to Endure, **Sky Maggiore**, The University of Kansas

5:30 PM –7:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Holland
Alfred University School of Art & Design / New York State College of Ceramics

Reception Contact: Lauren Lake, Alfred University

5:30 PM –7:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Harlem
Boston University History of Art & Architecture Alumni Reception

Reception Contact: Cynthia Becker

5:30 PM –7:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West Foyer
Center Alumni Reunion

Reception Contact: Olivia Yardley, Center for Advance Study in the Visual Arts; **Peter Marshall Lukehart**, National Gallery of Art

5:30 PM –7:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

Offsite – The Smith Midtown - 956 2nd Avenue
Cranbrook Academy of Art Alumni Reception

5:30 PM –7:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rotunda
Edinburgh College of Art Alumni and Networking Reception

Reception Contact: Vivienne Clark

5:30 PM –7:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – New York
Harvard Alumni Reunion

Reception Contact: Hilary Field

5:30 PM –7:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Green
Museum Professionals Networking

Reception Contact: Monica Andrews, Harvard Graduate School of Education

5:30 PM –7:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse C

The Department of Art & Archaeology at Princeton University Reception

Reception Contact: Jennifer Loessy, Princeton University

5:30 PM –7:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Lincoln
Univ. of Wisconsin Art History Centennial Reception

Reception Contact: Anna Andrzejewski

5:30 PM –7:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Hudson
USC Dornsife Department of Art History and the Visual Studies Research Institute Reception

Reception Contact: Tracey Marshall

5:30 PM –7:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – East
Yale University, Department of the History of Art Reception

Reception Contact: Nicole M. Chardiet, Yale University

6:00 PM –7:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

Offsite – Wagamama Midtown - 100 W 55th St
**Northwestern University Department of Art
History Reunion/Reception**

Reception Contact: Mel Keiser, Northwestern University

6:00 PM –8:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

Offsite – 317 E 52nd St – Trygve Lie Gallery
**Opening reception for 'in the wild rush of
Spring'**

6:00 PM –8:00 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

Offsite – Sotheby's Institute of Art - 570 Lexington
Ave

**Vantage Point: CAA Services to Artists
Committee Exhibition Reception**

Chair: Elyse Longair, Chair, Services to Artists
Committee, CAA

7:00 PM –9:30 PM THURSDAY, FEB. 13

Offsite – Private Location

**Historians of German, Scandinavian, and
Central European Art and Architecture
(HGSCEA) Members' Reception and Dinner**

Reception Contact: Jenny Anger, Grinnell College;
James A. Van Dyke, University of Missouri

Friday A.M. (Feb. 14)

Hours	Weds.	Thurs. & Fri.	Sat.
Registration	Online 24hrs (through February 15)		
In-person Registration:	8:00am–6:00pm	8:00am–6:00pm	8:00am–4:00pm
Sessions (In-person and Hybrid, all times Eastern)	2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm	9:00am–10:30am 11:00am–12:30pm 2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm	9:00am–10:30am 11:00am–12:30pm 2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm
In-person Book & Trade Fair:		9:00am–6:00pm	9:00am–2:30pm
Virtual Book & Trade Fair	24hr access, February 12-15		

Visit the CAA113 Book and Trade Fair!

New York Hilton Midtown
Rhineland Gallery or online.

On location hours:

Thursday 9 a.m.–6 p.m.
Friday 9 a.m.–6 p.m.
Saturday 9 a.m.–2:30 p.m.

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View the CAA website, mobile App and online Schedule for the most complete and up to date information, including recording status. www.collegeart.org

Please note that most on location sessions are not remotely accessible. Recordings of select events will post after the conference.

Presentation titles are listed after the Session title. Information in this pdf is subject to change.

This content is current as of Friday, February 7, 2025.

■ EVENT △ MEETING
⊕ HYBRID ◆ WORKSHOP

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East
Activating Community through Collaboration
WOMEN'S CAUCUS FOR ART

Chair: Rachel Epp Buller

Big Pages from the Heresies Collective – Transferring Feminist Journalism to an Exhibition Space, Tatjana Schaefer, Courtauld Institute of Art

Madre Tierra Press: A Chicana Collaboration, Emma Oslé, Rutgers University-New Brunswick

You are [Always] in Native Space: grappling with legacies of colonization through sound, Sarah E. Kanouse, Northeastern University

Acting on Climate One Step at a Time, Sheena Wilson, University of Alberta

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

Affective Encounters & Sonic Possibilities for “Imagining Otherwise”

Chair: Marcella Ernest

Chair Remarks

Remixing the Archive, **Marcella Ernest**

Healing Extractivist Environments Through Noise, **ANA Alonso-Minutti**

“Imagining” With Deep Domains of Indigenous Film, **Nancy Marie Mithlo**

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite

Automation, Authorship, and Authenticity: What does Art Have to Say about AI?

Chairs: **Gerui Wang**, Stanford University; **Miguel Novelo**, Stanford University

Discussant: **Shane Denson**, Stanford University

Tomorrow's Problems: Art and Labor at Automation House, **Nina Wexelblatt**

The Tangible Turn: Reintroducing Materiality to Assert Creativity in AI Art, **Ziru Chen**, University of Oxford

AI's Anxiety in Representation: Machine Learning, Ink Art, and the Multivalent Images, **Gerui Wang**, Stanford University

Two Handfuls of Silver Dust, **Rhonda Holberton**, San Jose State University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

♦ Bad advice for teachers

EDUCATION COMMITTEE

Workshop Leader: **Emily Elizabeth Goodman**, Transylvania University; **Alysha Meloche**, Villanova University; **Francesca Molly Albrezzi**, UCLA

Chair Remarks

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North

🌐 Contemporary Artists Using AI: A Paradigm Shift for Art Historians

Chair: **Leda Cempellin**, South Dakota State University

Discussant: **Melissa Geiger**; **Amelia Winger-Bearskin**

Compression/Generation: Realism, Modernism, and AI, **Lev Manovich**

Art in the Age of AI: Gains, Losses, and Illusions, **Ahmed Elgammal**, Rutgers University New Brunswick

Not Touched By Human Hands: The Notion of AI Sentience and the Power of Images, **Kurt Ralske**, Sch of the Museum of Fine Arts at Tufts Univ

AI's Unseen Borders: Crafting a Pluriverse Future, **Linda Rebeiz**

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

Contemporary Black Abstraction: Confluence and Resonance

Chairs: **Klare Scarborough**, Museum and Arts Consultant; **Berrisford Boothe**, Lehigh University

Discussant: **Berrisford Boothe**, Lehigh University

Black Abstraction, Social Media, and the Marketplace, **Enise Carr**

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

Creative Practice, Research, and Teaching Intersections

NATIONAL ART EDUCATION ASSOCIATION

Chair: **Dr. Ilayda Altuntas Nott**, The University of Arizona

Chair Remarks

Intermedia Journaling & Poetic Inquiry as Artist/Researcher/Teacher, **Tamryn L. McDermott**, Old Dominion University

A Forager's Guide to Art, **Lillian Lewis**, Virginia Commonwealth University

Exploring Cultural Ecosystems through Embodied Forms of Research, **Carissa DiCindio**

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

Curatorial Practices in Latin America: Challenges and Discourses in the Age of Global Neoliberalism

Chairs: **Florencia San Martin**, Lehigh University; **Joselyne Contreras Cerda**, Goldsmiths, University of London

Chair Remarks

1992: Latin American Art and the New Global Order, **Sara Garzon**, Cornell University

MESÓTICA II: Toward the Regeneration of Contemporary Art in Central America, **Lesdi Goussen Robleto**, Museum of Fine Arts Houston

Decoloniality is a Metaphor: Exhibitions of Ecuadorian Modern Art, **Anamaría Garzón Mantilla**, University of Essex / Universidad San Francisco de Quito

Curatorial Practices and the Sensitive Turn: How to Challenge the Neoliberal Machine in Latin America, **Joselyne Contreras Cerda**, Goldsmiths, University of London

Indigenous protagonism and curatorial practice in contemporary art of Brazil, **Claudia Mattos Avolesse**, Tufts University

Faceless Figuration: A Safavid Kilim in Munich, **Lyla Halsted**, Davidson College

Riveting Encounters: Mounted Ceramics in the Oeuvre of John Hoffman (fl. 1577–1600), Stranger Silversmith in Elizabethan London, **Fosca Maddaloni-Yu**, Brown University

Warm Hearts: Colonial Inuit Design and the Black Atlantic, **Bart C Pushaw**, University of Tennessee at Chattanooga

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite

Design and Decoration of Libraries

Chair: **Diana Gisolfi**, Pratt Institute, Pratt in Venice

From Urbino to the Vatican City and back: the Library of Federico da Montefeltro, as it was, where it was., **Grazia Maria Fachechi**, University of Urbino

Skin: The Renaissance Library and the Archive of the Animal, **Kim S. Sexton**, 1149 N Waneetah Ave

An Armenian Library in Venice, **Annalise Welte**, The Institute of Fine Arts, New York University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

🌐 Design and Disability: Changing Perspectives and Opportunities

Chairs: **Hannah Duffew**, University of Edinburgh; **Craig Martin**, University of Edinburgh; **Emma Gieben-Gamal**, Edinburgh College of Art, University of Edinburgh

Chair Remarks

Teleconferencing in Deaf Space: Appropriation, ASL and Shifting Communication Infrastructure, **Sabrina Ward-Kimola**

Reimagining Access in HCI: Critiquing Affordance Theory through the Lens of Disability and Design Justice, **Hrittika Bhowmick**, BITS Pilani, Hyderabad Campus

Co-Envisioning Adaptive Ecologies: Collaborative Workshops with Crip Designers for Future Climate Architecture, **Taline Frantz** and **Trisha Mehta**

For Example: Ramps and Other Objects, **Atanas Bozdarov**

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

Emblematic Encounters: Cross-Cultural Objects and Material Agency in the Early Modern World

Chairs: **Fosca Maddaloni-Yu**, Brown University; **Lyla Halsted**, Davidson College

Chair Remarks

New Money in the Early Modern Eastern Mediterranean, **Katherine Calvin**, Kenyon College

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite

Expanding Archives: Drawing, Documentation, and Democratic Impulse

Chairs: **Kara Braciale**, Corcoran School of the Arts & Design; **Matthew J Westerby**, National Gallery of Art

Drawing is a Residue of Time; tracing a future in the Pictures Collection, **Claire Greenshaw**, York University

Archiving Political Resistance - Woman Life Freedom, **Neda Moridpour**, SMFA at Tufts University

The Legibility of the Stack, Artists in the Archive, **Meg Rotzel**, Harvard Radcliffe Institute for Advanced Study

Model Plants, Modelling and Memory, **Sonia Ralston**, Northeastern University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

Figuring the Individual/Figuring the Group: Transnational Exchanges in Interwar Art

Chair: **Juan Gabriel Ramirez Bolivar**, Institute of Fine Arts, NYU

Discussant: **Francesca Ferrari**, New York University

Socialist Realism across Turkey and the Soviet Union: Abidin Dino, the Socialist Body, and Stalinist Happiness, **Özge Karagöz**, Northwestern University

George Hoyningen-Huene's Photographs of Bathers in the Shadow of French Empire, **Sasha Whittaker**, Princeton University

Indigenous or Spanish? The Mexican and Colombian Pavilions at the Ibero-American Exposition of Seville, 1929, **Juan Gabriel Ramirez Bolivar**, New York University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman

🌐 Innovation by Necessity: Problem Solvers and Museum Futures

MUSEUM COMMITTEE

Chairs: **Kari Samantha Sigmon**; **Martina Tanga**, Museum of Fine Arts, Boston

Chair Remarks

The Mandeville Art Gallery at UC San Diego:
Generating New Futures, **Ceci Moss**, University of California, San Diego

Volunteer and social service programs in the art museum as an educational space for its participants,
Erika Perez Armenta

Strike the Museum: Collective Imaginaries on the Picket Lines of US Art Museums, **Amanda Ripley**, The Ohio State University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

Is there anybody out there? UFOs, UAPs, and American Art

ASSOCIATION OF HISTORIANS OF AMERICAN ART

Chair: Robert Cozzolino

Chair Remarks

Is there anybody out there? UFOs, UAPs, and American Art, **Robert Cozzolino**

Excessive Traces, **Amanda Nedham**, Rice University

Budd Hopkins's Circles, **Joe Bucciero**, Princeton University

In Search Of... UFO Art at the Margins, **Nicole LaBouff**, Los Angeles County Museum of Art

John McCracken's Remote Viewing: Minimalism and Advanced Beings, **Erika Doss**, The University of Texas at Dallas

"UFOs are not Photogenic": The Phenomenon, Photography, and Testimony, **Michelle Smiley**, Library of Congress

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
Learning and Unlearning Photography

THE PHOTOGRAPHY NETWORK

Chair: Brendan Fay, Eastern Michigan University

Chair Remarks

That Which is Boundless: The Legacy of Apeiron Workshops, 1970 – 1982, **Krystle Stricklin**, Smithsonian American Art Museum

Reframing Appalachia: Foxfire's Rural Pedagogy, **Jesse Dritz**, Boston University

Rehearsing Views: Pedagogical Toolkits for Visual Literacy, **Katie Giritlian**, Artist

Identity and Self-Representation in the East Harlem Community Resource Center's Photo Workshop, **Adam D. Jolles**, Florida State University and **Josh Ellenbogen**, University of Pittsburgh

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

Navigating the changing terrain of fair use in the digital world

STUDENT AND EMERGING PROFESSIONALS COMMITTEE

Chairs: Nicole Emser, Temple University; **Epiphany Knedler**, Northern State University; **Yuha Jung**

Discussant: Katherine de Vos Devine, Implement Legal; **Susan J. Douglas**, University of Guelph; **Frank J. Martinez**; **Nick Pozek**

Chair Remarks

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Taking and Making: Artistic Reckonings with Cultural Property Theft in the Long Nineteenth Century

ASSOCIATION OF HISTORIANS OF 19TH-CENTURY ART

Chair: Nancy Karrels, Independent Scholar and Curator

King Cophetua and the Stolen Gold: Edward Burne-Jones's Reflections on Looting, **Tara Contractor**, Philadelphia Museum of Art

Centering Native American Belongings in Settler Paintings, c. 1900, **Emily Burns**

Looted Northern European Collections and the Transformation of French Portraiture, **Jennifer W. Olmsted**, Wayne State University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

The Posthuman Personhood of the Dead in the Ancient Mediterranean

Chairs: Savannah Marquardt, Yale University; **Nathaniel Barrett Jones**, Washington University in St. Louis

Chair Remarks

Entanglements Between Human, Non-Human, and Posthuman in the Graves of Argos, **Cicek Beeby**, Brown University, Classics Department

Intimacy between Living and Dead on Classical Marble Lekythoi, **Carolyn Laferriere**, Princeton University

Grounding the Grave of Agamemnon, **Savannah Marquardt**, Yale University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West
Transhistorical Art History

Chair: Maggie M. Cao, University of North Carolina-Chapel Hill

Chair Remarks

Beuys vs. the Goldsmiths: Symbolic Meltdown and the Kronschnelzaktion (1982), **Allison Stielau**, University College London

Astronauts in the Rainforest: How an Emberá Silver-Coin Necklace and pre-Conquest Metallurgy from the Colombia-Panama Borderlands Defy Colonial Gravity, **Juliana Ramírez Herrera**, University of Toronto / Gardiner Museum of Ceramic Art

Polaroid's Expanded Times: Patrick Nagatani and Andrée Tracey's Atomic Theaters, **Kevin Hong**, Yale University

The Life and Times of Charles Bird King's Black Hawk, **Dina Murokh**, Williams College

9:00 AM –10:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton South
Who's Afraid of Mimicry? Contemporary Art and New Culture Wars

Chairs: **Gediminas Gasparavicius**, University of Akron; **Maia Toteva**, Texas Tech University

Discussant: **Tom C. Williams**, Belmont University

Chair Remarks

Overidentification, Decolonization and Genderqueer Activism in Contemporary South Africa, **Matthias Pauwels**, North-West University

Mimesis and Mimicry: Contemporary Art, Commodification, and (Post)Critique, **Steyn Bergs**

Mimicry and Irony in Internet Memes – Friends or Foes?, **Vera Mevorah**

Who's Afraid of Post-Internet Mimicry?, **Konstantinos Stafylakis**

10:00 AM –11:30 AM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Americas Hall
CAA Portfolio Review and Industry Advice for Artists (Session 1)

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Alexander Bostic**

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Vladimir Cybil Charlier**

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Lauren McCardel**, Ursinus College--Berman Museum of Art

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Amanda L. Lechner**, Virginia Tech

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Wanda Yvette Raimundi-Ortiz**, George Mason University

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Elyse Longair**, Chair, Services to Artists Committee, CAA

11:00 AM –1:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Hudson
caa.reviews Editorial Board Meeting

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

A Roundtable on American Art

ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH INSTITUTES IN ART HISTORY

Chair: **Caroline Fowler**, Clark Art Institute

Discussant: **Mindy A. Besaw**, Crystal Bridges Museum of American Art; **Amelia A. Goerlitz**, Smithsonian American Art Museum; **Erica Wall**, Colby College Museum of Art

A Roundtable on American Art, **Caroline Fowler**, Clark Art Institute

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

Alternative Alternatives: Sites and Audiences Outside the Artworld Today

Chair: **Jeffrey Abt**, Wayne State University

Discussant: **Mary Anne Staniszewski**, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Chair Remarks

Bringing the Gown to Town: Chale Wote Street Art Festival in Ga Mashie, Accra, Ghana, **Colleen Foran**, Boston University

In the Trenches: PlantBot Genetics and the ArtLab, **Jeff M Schmuki**, Georgia Southern University

"A Rat Came to Your Art Party": On Starting a Gallery in a Pay Phone at a New York City Bus Stop, **Marin Kosut**, Purchase College

Art in the Cracks: Finding Creative Space in the Domestic Environment, **Céline Browning**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite
Artistic Responses to the Ongoing Genocide in Gaza: Exploring Palestinian Narratives and Resistance through Visual Culture

Chair: **Clark Stoeckley**

Eighteen times: from the river to the river, **Pierre S. Taminiaux**, Georgetown University

Sliman Mansour and Beautiful Acts of Resistance, **Sue Uhlig**, Purdue University

Palestine in Venice: Representation and Dissent, **Sabrina De Turk**, University of Maine

Poetry, Image, Landscape: Documentary Forms and Arab Apocalypse, **Atefeh Ahmadi**, University of Wisconsin Madison

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

Brazilian & U.S. Art in Exile: Transnationalism, Migration, and the Politics of Being “Latin American” in the United States and Brazil

Chairs: Daria Jaremtchuk; Abigail Lapin Dardashti, University of California Irvine

Discussant: Mariola V. Alvarez, Tyler School of Art Temple University

Chair Remarks

Art & the Poetics of Exile, Daria Jaremtchuk

Paul Lester Wiener, an architect tied to the American Government and his connections and projects in Brazil (1938-1945), Rafael Urano Frajndlich, Unicamp

Portuñol Newyorkaise, Aimé Iglesias Lukin

Mapping Jewish-Latin American Consciousness: Race and Space in the Art of Anna Bella Geiger, Abigail Lapin Dardashti, University of California Irvine

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman

🌐 Crossing Borders: Bringing Mediterranean Studies to a Wider Audience

Chairs: Kathryn B. Gerry, Bowdoin College; Barbara Crostini, Newman Institute

Crossing Borders: A Western Medievalist's Viewpoint on Fitting France and Spain into the Mediterranean World, Kathryn B. Gerry, Bowdoin College

Crossing Borders: A Curatorial Viewpoint on Making the Mediterranean Accessible, Andrea Mari Achi

Crossing Borders: The Viewpoint of an Historian on the Power of Objects, Dawn Hayes

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Design History as Labor History

Chair: Danielle Aubert

Chair Remarks

The Labors of Eugene Winslow: Racial Politics in the Midcentury Design Industry, Christopher James Dingwall, Washington University in Saint Louis

Graphic Design and AI: Perspectives from the History of Automation, J. Dakota D Brown, University of Illinois Chicago

Lessons from Labor Organizing in Design Education, Arden E. Stern and Casey Anderson

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North

🌐 Design Incubation Colloquium 11.2: Recent Research in Communication Design

DESIGN INCUBATION

Chairs: Camila Afanador-Llach, Florida Atlantic University; Heather Snyder Quinn, DePaul University and Design Incubation

Discussant: Jessica Barness, Kent State University; Daniel J. Wong, Design Incubation; Cat Normoyle, East Carolina University

Chair Remarks

Design History Data: A Snapshot of US-based Undergraduate Programs, Augusta Rose Toppins, Washington University in St. Louis

Editorial Infographics: Bridging the Gap Between Complexity and Clarity in Design Education, Teresa Trevino, University of the Incarnate Word

The Bayou at y.our Doorstep: Integrating Environmental Education in Graphic Design, Natacha Poggio

Collaborative Creativity and Digital Identity: Reimagining Authorship in the Digital Age, Feixue Mei, James Madison University

Designing Inclusive Engagements in Neighborhood Design Projects, D.J. Trischler, University of Cincinnati

Service Design for Digital Tours: The Rixing Type Foundry Case, Ting Han Chen, Play Design Lab

Enhancing Design Education: Students Skill Development through Technology in Blended Learning Environments, Danilo Ljubomir Bojić, Winona State University

Black Space Protocols: On Anti-Racist Placemaking and Urban Design, Nekita Thomas, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite

Digital Methods for Difficult Hidden Art Histories

DIGITAL ART HISTORY SOCIETY

Chairs: Paul B. Jaskot, Duke University; Mark J.V. Olson, Duke University - Dept of Art, Art Hist & Visual Studies; Victoria E. Szabo, Duke University - Dept of Art, Art Hist & Visual Studies

Chair Remarks

Hidden Histories of the Holocaust: “Guided Modeling” as a Critical Digital Humanities Method, Hannah L Jacobs, Paul B. Jaskot, Duke University - Dept of Art, Art Hist & Visual Studies and Mark J.V. Olson, Duke University - Dept of Art, Art Hist & Visual Studies

History in Extended Reality (XR): Encountering Hidden Worlds of Nineteenth-Century Rome and Istanbul, **Burcak Ozludil**, **Louis Hamilton**, New Jersey Institute of Technology and **Ersin Altin**, Pratt Institute

Virtual Black Charlotte: Reconstructing and Representing the Lost Brooklyn Community, **Victoria E. Szabo**, Duke University - Dept of Art, Art Hist & Visual Studies and **Augustus Wendell**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

◆ Empowering Professionals: Discovering the Impact of Coaching in Creative Fields.

Workshop Leader: Les Joynes, Columbia University and Renmin University of China

Chair Remarks

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East

Exploring Research Methods in Art Appraisal: Techniques and Case Studies

AMERICAN SOCIETY OF APPRAISERS

Chair: Guillermo Ortiz de Zarate, American Society of Appraisers

Chair Remarks

Exploring Research Methods in Art Appraisal: Techniques and Case Studies, **Maria Tarrence**, Capital Art Group LLC

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

Hair Power: Culture, Materiality, Politics of Hair in Contemporary Art

Chair: Rosemary M. Meza-DesPlas, Independent

Skeena Reece, "Access Granted": Hair as Site of Identity, Violence, Kinship, and Power, **Cassandra Smith**, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

In Relation to Whiteness: Anne Wilson's Disrupted Linens, **Lisa S. Wainwright**, School of the Art Institute of Chicago

Embodied Resistance: Bodily Autonomy in Iran Augmented by Art and Technology, **Rashin Fahandej**, Emerson College and **Azadeh Tajpour**, Lesley University

Subversive Strands: Hair as a Medium in Seung-taek Lee's Art, **Joon Hye Park**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite Haptic Histories: The Politics of Paper & Its Industrial Entanglements

ASSOCIATION OF PRINT SCHOLARS

Chairs: Aleisha Elizabeth Barton, University of Minnesota; **Shane Morrissy**, Duke University - Dept of Art, Art Hist & Visual Studies

Discussant: Christina Michelon, Museum of Fine Arts, Boston

Didactic Tools or Harbingers of Chaos: Konstantin Gribanov's "Geographical Cards of Russia.", **Liliya Dashevski**, Yale University

Political Promises and Pictures: How Victorian socialists used print ephemera to engage children in political action, **Emily Cadger**, University of British Columbia

Only Between Times: Gender, Satire, and the Postcard of the Early 20th-Century, **Erika Piola**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

🌐 Healing and the Museum: Critical Perspectives in 21st Century Art

Chair: Megan Voeller, Tyler School of Art & Architecture, Temple University

Chair Remarks

Racial Injury and Ancestral Healing in the Photographic Archive, **Megan Voeller**, Temple University, Tyler School of Art and Architecture

Collective Healing Through Confrontation in Safety: Grace Ndiritu's The Healing Pavilion, **Janice Li**, Wellcome Collection

'The Problem Is Power': Navigating Museums' Wellbeing Turn from a Feminist Perspective, **Kirsten Lloyd**, University of Edinburgh

Mother Molds: Art and Reproductive Health Justice in the Academic Museum, **Melanie Nguyen**, Rollins College and **Michelle V. Moncrieffe**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Mercury Ballroom

Language and Text in Feminist Art Part II: Latin America and the Caribbean, Latinx diasporas

Chair: Monika Fabijanska, Independent Art Historian and Curator

To Cheat Language: Feminist Critique Through Play in Magali Lara's Series "Sielo", **Jeronimo Duarte-Riascos**, Columbia University

Language to express issues on gender violence and racial discrimination: The work of four Andean and Amazonian contemporary women artists, **Gabriela Germana**, Independent scholar

Deborah Castillo: Disfiguring and Reconfiguring the Verbal and Corporeal Language of Patriarchy, **Karen Cordero**, Universidad Iberoamericana (retired)

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

Law in Art and Art in Law: Charting a New Course for Society

Chairs: **Aviva A. Rahmani**, INSTAAR University of Colorado at Boulder; **Gale Elston**

Chair Remarks

Saving the Appearances, **Rebecca Zorach**, Northwestern University

Art, Law and Artistic Collaborations, **Sharon Hecker**

Creative Interventions into Injunctions, **Madalen Benson**, University of California, Santa Cruz - History of Art and Visual Culture Department

Forensic Architecture and the construction of a legal truth, **Blessy Augustine**, University of Western Ontario

The political activist as patron, **James McConnell**, University of Minnesota Minneapolis

Preserving the Commons Via Art, **Ellen K. Levy**, CAA

Color's Legal Limits, **Steven Bleicher**, Coastal Carolina University

Personhood of the Sun, **Elizabeth Shores**, MPIP and **Vikram Patel**

Lines and Loopholes, **Rae Root**, University of Oregon

A couple bad ideas for a survivable future, **Eliza Evans**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

Pedagogy as Art: Possibilities and Constraints in Institutional Transformation

Chairs: **Noni Brynjonson**, University of Indianapolis; **Izabel Galliera**, University of Missouri-Kansas City

To Let the Art Do Its Job, **Laura Raicovich**

Smoke and Mirrors at the Zimmerli Art Museum, **Amanda Cachia**, The University of Houston

Transformative Pedagogies in Chinese Socially Engaged Art, **Meiqin Wang**, California State University Northridge

Throwing Stones at the Wall: Pedagogical Art and the Immovability of Museums, **Allison Rowe**, University of Iowa

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West Reaching Out: An Other-Focused Academic Approach to the Visual Arts

SECAC

Chair: **Melissa Geiger**

Discussant: **Leda Cempellin**, South Dakota State University

Beyond the Studio: Navigating the IRB Process in Artistic Research, **Jinyoung Koh**, Towson University and **Boram Kim**, University of Massachusetts Amherst

Healing through Grief: processing hardship and uniting communities through social practice art, **Renée Lynn Reizman**, University of California, Irvine

The Indigo Project: A Social Study in Compassion, Collaboration, and Community, **Salena Fehnel**, Drew University, Caspersen School of Graduate Studies

Toward an Expanded Classroom: how students come to know their space through creativity, **Michael O'Malley** and **Joel Parker**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton South Rethinking the Theory and Methods Art History Course

NORTHERN CALIFORNIA ART HISTORIANS

Chairs: **Rachel Miller**; **Mya B. Dosch**

Chair Remarks

Methods by Mascot: Shared Investment in Theory and Methods, **Saskia R. Beranek**, Illinois State University

Professional Methods as Curricular Intervention, **Rebecca Peabody**, Getty Research Institute

Reimaging Art History Education: Integrating Theory and Methodology into Introductory Art History Courses, **Anya Shulman**, CSU Sacramento

Student Perception of Value and Engagement with Theory, **Tyler Edward Ostergaard**, University of Wisconsin-Platteville

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

The Art of Porous Borders from Eurasian Antiquity to the Mongol Era

Chair: **Petya Andreeva**, Vassar College

Discussant: **Petya Andreeva**, Vassar College

Chair Remarks

Assemblageing Art in the Middle Ground: untangling the entanglement of visual cultures in contact along the Great Walls frontier, **Bryan Miller**, University of Michigan

A Center on the Border: Migration and Artistic Innovation of Fifth-Century Pingcheng, China, **Fan Zhang**, Tulane University

The Türk Building Plan, **Nancy Steinhardt**

The Porosity of Mongol Borders: Contributions of the Ilkhanids, Golden Horde and Chaghtayids to the Development of Tilework., **Bernard O'Kane**, American University in Cairo

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

The Warring Face of Realism: Cross-media Approach to Japanese War Art, 1931-1945

Chairs: **Sung Ji Park**, The Courtauld Institute of Art; **Kimihiko Nakamura**, Universitaet Heidelberg, Institut fuer Kunstgeschichte Ostasiens

Discussant: **Akihisa Kawata**, Chiba Institute of Technology

Takai Teiji's "North Advancement" and the Manchuria-Mongolia Settlement Youth Volunteer Corps, **Kimihiko Nakamura**, Universitaet Heidelberg, Institut fuer Kunstgeschichte Ostasiens

Propagandistic Realism: Lies Camouflaged by Photographic Truth in Japanese Reportage Photography, **Sung Ji Park**, The Courtauld Institute of Art

The War Dead in Japanese Wartime Films: Fiction and Documentary, **Woojeong Joo**, Nagoya University Bungaku

"Truth" and Intermedia at the China Incident Holy War Exposition, 1938, **Kari L. Shepherdson-Scott**, Macalester College

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Troubling the Archive: Reassessing Women's Artistic Production in the Long Nineteenth Century

Chair: **James McCabe**, Rice University

Hidden Identities: Analyzing the Transatlantic Influence in American Visual Culture by Examining Subversive Forms of Representation of Women of Color in the Nineteenth Century, **Allison Springer**, Rice University

Unobservable: Eunice Newton Foote and Photographic Evidence, **Victoria Kenyon**, University of Delaware

Julie Looks at Laure and Laure Looks Back: The Issue of Reproducing Édouard Manet's Olympia in Julie Manet-Rouart's Copies, **James McCabe**, Rice University

Unraveling Materiality: Anna Lea Merritt's The Weaving Shed and the Transatlantic Textile Industry, **Lauren Lovings-Gomez**, Rice University

11:00 AM –12:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
Women and the Global Historiography of Photography, 1840-1940

Chair: **Karen Fraser**, University of San Francisco

Chair Remarks

Ottoman Quest for Women in Photography: The Case of Elisa Zonaro (1863–1945), **Alev Berberoğlu**, Bibliotheca Hertziana – Max Planck Institute for Art History

Birding with a Camera while Female: A Researcher's Dilemma, **Karla McManus**, University of Regina

Onna Shashinshi: Female Studio Photographers in Early Twentieth Century Japan, **Haely Chang**, Dartmouth College - Hood Museum

11:30 AM –1:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Americas Hall
CAA Portfolio Review and Industry Advice for Artists (Session 2)

SERVICES TO ARTISTS COMMITTEE

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Matthew L. Conboy**, George Mason University

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Matthew L. Conboy**, George Mason University

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Gina T. Washington**

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Megan Arney Johnston**, Minnesota State Colleges & Universities

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Lara Corona**, Universitat Internacional de Catalunya

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Maya Wilson-Sanchez**

Portfolio Reviewer / Offering Industry Advice, **Julian Jason Haladyn**, OCAD University

12:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – 2nd Floor Promenade

"I Wish to Say" performance by Sheryl Oring

Panelists: **Sheryl A. Oring**, Wayne State University

12:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

■ **CAA Annual Business Meeting**

Chair Remarks

12:00 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – 2nd Floor Promenade

△ **Open Hours with CAA Publications**

12:00 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

Offsite – RSVP

Vantage Point: CAA Services to Artists Committee Exhibition

SERVICES TO ARTISTS COMMITTEE

Chair: Elyse Longair, Chair, Services to Artists Committee, CAA

Artist, Nina Hamberg, Artists Thrive

Artist, Ana Kapodistria, Ana Kapodistria

Artist, Nadine Valcin, Sheridan College Institute

Artist, Christina Yao, Alberta University of the Arts

Artist, Rachel Portesi, Rachel Portesi Photography

Artist, Randy Matusow, RANDY MATUSOW PHOTOGRAPHY

Artist / Performance Artist, Natalie Waldburger, Ontario College of Art & Design

12:30 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

Offsite – The Museum of Modern Art

A Close Look at Joan Mitchell with Conservator Jen Hickey and Art Historian Karli Wurzelbacher

12:30 PM –3:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Main Entrance, Hotel Lobby

Gallery Tour - tickets required

12:30 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – New York **SAIC Alumni & Faculty Reception**

Reception Contact: Trisha Fischer

12:30 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West Foyer

Smithsonian American Art Museum Annual Alumni Reunion

Reception Contact: Judith Hollomon, Smithsonian American Art Museum

12:30 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rotunda

The Clark Art Institute and Williams College Graduate Program in the History of Art Reception

Reception Contact: Caitlin Woolsey, Clark Art Institute

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West

△ **Association for Critical Race Art History - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

△ **Association of Historians of 19th-Century Art - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

🌐 △ **Catalogue Raisonné Scholars Association - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

△ **Community College Professors of Art and Art History - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

△ **Design Incubation - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

🌐 △ **Italian Art Society - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

△ **Leonardo Education and Art Forum - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite

△ **New Media Caucus - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

🌐 △ **SECAC - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

△ **Society of Contemporary Art Historians - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
△ **The Feminist Art Project - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East
△ **The Photography Network - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
△ **The Queer Trans Caucus for Art - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West
△ **Women's Caucus for Art - Business Meeting**

Friday P.M. (Feb. 14)

■ EVENT △ MEETING
⊕ HYBRID ◆ WORKSHOP

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

"Foreigners Everywhere!": Art and Refugee Identification

Chairs: Gwyneth Jane Shanks, Colby College; Sean Metzger

Baggage/Luggage: Material and Symbolic Meanings in Displacement Experiences, **Fabiola R. Delgado**

"DYN" in Mexico City: Aesthetic Possibility and Abstraction in Exile, 1939-1944, **Megan Kincaid**, Institute of Fine Arts, NYU

Promoting Arab Immigrant Integration in the German Community through Exhibits and Programs at the Neues Museum in Berlin, **Said Ahmed**, The Grand Egyptian Museum

Staging Statelessness and The Right to Have Rights, **Noit Banai**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

"The Space Between" The Lasting Influence of Archibald J. Motley, Jr.

Chair: Amy M. Mooney, Columbia College Chicago

Chair Remarks

The Space Between: Candida Alvarez, **Candida Alvarez**, School of the Art Institute of Chicago

The Space Between: Nicole Awai, **Nicole D. Awai**, John Jay College of Criminal Justice, CUNY

The Space Between: Deborah Jack, **Deborah M. Jack**

The Space Between: Cecil McDonald, **Cecil McDonald**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

A War for Our Age: Genpei War Images and Social Movements

Chairs: Kit Brooks, Princeton University Art Museum; Mark K. Erdmann, University of Melbourne

Chair Remarks

No Country for Young Men: Heike Paintings and Warrior Identity in Post-Warring States Japan, **Mark K. Erdmann**, University of Melbourne

The Genpei War's Apparitional Spaces in Tsukioka Kōgyo's Nōgaku hyakuban (One Hundred Noh Plays), **Elizabeth Oyler**, University of Pittsburgh

Absurd Atrocities: Masculinity and Ridicule in Takeda Hideo's Genpei, **Kit Brooks**, Princeton University Art Museum

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – East

Affiliated Societies Meet and Greet with CAA Executive Director

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

Can You Teach Creativity? The Role of the Arts Across Disciplines.

Chair: Jonathan Fineberg, Rowan University

Chair Remarks

Panelist - Susan H. Gordon, **Susan Gordon**, Independent scholar and author

Panelist - Eugene Hughes, **Eugene Hughes**, Artgym

Panelist - Frank Machos, **Frank Machos**, School District of Philadelphia

Panelist - Patricia Salkin, **Patricia Salkin**, Touro University

Panelist - Zach Savich, **Zach Savich**, Cleveland Institute of Art

Panelist - Buzz Spector, **Buzz Spector**, Washington University in St Louis, Sam Fox School of Design and Visual Arts, College of Art

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite
Collaboration as Art Historical Practice

Chairs: Nancy A. Um, Getty Research Institute; Susan Elizabeth Gagliardi, Emory University

Collaboration, Creativity, and the Public Humanities, **Meredith S. Martin**, New York University

De-Hierarchising Impressionism Studies via UK/US Collaborations, **Alexis Clark** and **Claire N. Moran**

Collaboration in wood identification: the interdisciplinary work of writing of art histories and conservation methodologies for Congolese heritage objects in Belgian museums., **Vu Horwitz**, Yale University and **Sofie Dierickx**, Royal Museum for Central Africa

The Apotropaic Collective: Kinship and Care as Knowledge-Practice, **Amy J. Bowman-McElhone**, Carlow University and **Jennifer A Baez**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

🌐 Crip Time: Disabled Spacemaking in the Work of Queercrip Artists

THE QUEER TRANS CAUCUS FOR ART

Chairs: Halo Starling, USC School of Cinematic Arts, Department of Media Arts + Practice; Libby Paloma

Crip Publishing Manifestx: Crippling Journal Editing, **Ela Przybyło**, Illinois State University, **Mae Howard**, **Lam Jen (Bom)**, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, **Halo Starling**, USC School of Cinematic Arts, Department of Media Arts + Practice and **Libby Paloma**

Disabled Erotics, **Mae Howard**

Crip Art Residency: Reimagining Access, Community, and Queercrip Artistic Expression in Hong Kong, **Lam Jen (Bom)**, The Chinese University of Hong Kong, **Cheng Man Yuet** and **Siu Fong Yeung**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West

Critical Race Art History Roundtable: Doing the Work

ASSOCIATION FOR CRITICAL RACE ART HISTORY

Chairs: Jacqueline Francis, California College of the Arts; Camara D. Holloway, Association for Critical Race Art History

Roundtable Participant Kymberly Pinder, **Kymberly Pinder**, Yale University School of Art

Roundtable Participant Lily Cho, **Lily Cho**, York University

Roundtable Participant Elizabeth Hutchinson, **Elizabeth Hutchinson**, Columbia University

Roundtable Participant Marci Kwon, **Marci Kwon**, Stanford University

Roundtable Participant Tatiana Flores, **Tatiana E. Flores**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent

Cyberfeminist Legacies in New Media Art

NEW MEDIA CAUCUS

Chair: Irina Aristarkhova, University of Michigan Ann Arbor

Discussant: Maria Fernandez

Chair Remarks

Maintenance Work in a Smart Nation, **Margaret Tan**

Alchemies of birth; Or, the black purposes of assisted reproductive technologies., **Nathanael Mengist**, University of Washington

Terms and Conditions, **Hyla Willis**, Robert Morris University

subRosa Art and Tactical Media, **Irina Aristarkhova**, University of Michigan Ann Arbor

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Design Education Futures

COMMITTEE ON DESIGN

Chairs: Andrea Lyn Hempstead, Texas A&M University-Corpus Christi; Delana Gabbard, Southeast Missouri State University

Chair Remarks

Redefining Design Education for Generation Z: From Anxiety to Empowerment, **Lilian Crum**, Lawrence Technological University

Renewing our Graphic Design Program: Challenges, Opportunities, and Strategies for Growth, **Trysh Wahlig**, University of Louisville

Advancing Design Education through Hybridity and Communication, **Sana Khan Hussaini**, San Francisco State University and **Ellen Christensen**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Mercury Ballroom

Dialogue and Artistry: Exploring the history, canon and critical reception of artist books

COLLEGE BOOK ART ASSOCIATION

Chairs: Peter J. Tanner, University of Utah; Levi Sherman, University of Wisconsin - Madison

Chair Remarks

Artist Books and Asemic Writing as Decoloniality Vehicles, **Gaby Hernández**, University of Arkansas

Binding queer networks: FILE magazine and the mass produced artist book, **Chris Reeves**

Reframing contemporary narratives: Celeste Rojas Mugica's Inventario Iconoclasta de la Insurrección Chilena, **Alejandra Lopez-Oliveros**, Rutgers University

Gauchito Querido: A Case Study on Contemporary Interdisciplinary Artist Books, **Amparo Baquerizas**, American University of Sharjah

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North

🌐 Examining the Legacies of the New Deal Era for Indigenous Arts

Chair: Kara Heitz, Kansas City Art Institute

Discussant: Alicia Lynn Harris, University of Oklahoma

Chair Remarks

Indigenist Muralism from Santa Fe to Aztlán, **Davidá Fernandez-Barkan**, University of Arkansas

Land of Enchantment: Reframing Agency of Woody Crumbo's Subjects, **Kathryn Florence**

Reclaiming Indigenous Artistry: Potawatomi Bead Workers and the WPA in Kansas, **Kara Heitz**, Kansas City Art Institute

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
Generative AI on the Dissecting Table

Chairs: **Caroline A. Jones**, Massachusetts Institute of Technology; **Huma Gupta**

Discussant: **Ji-hoon Kim**

Chair Remarks

Thresholds of the Frontier, **Katherine Lambert**, California College of Arts and **Christiane Robbins**, MAP Studio (Metropolitan Architectural Practice)

Matthew Ritchie, Panelist, **Matthew Ritchie**

Trevor Paglen, panelist, **Trevor Paglen**, Trevor Paglen Studio

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

ISLAA-ALAA Encuentro for Latin American and Latinx Art at CAA

INSTITUTE FOR STUDIES ON LATIN AMERICAN ART (ISLAA)

Chair: **Blanca Serrano Ortiz de Solórzano**, Institute for Studies on Latin American Art (ISLAA)

Discussant: **Ana M. Franco**; **Lesley Wolff**, The University of Tampa

Of Objects, Politics, and Ideas: The Material Cultures of Independence, **Natalia Majluf**, Independent art historian and curator

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton South
🌐 PST and Other Art/Sci Models for the Future

LEONARDO EDUCATION AND ART FORUM

Chairs: **Ellen K. Levy**; **Termeh Rassi**, Leonardo

Discussant: **John D Talasek**

Chair Remarks

Complexity, **David Familian**

Discussion of "PST ART: Art & Science Collide: Vibrations", **Victoria Vesna**, UCLA Art Sci center

Curiosity, **Stephanie Dinkins**, State University of New York Stony Brook - Department of Art

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

Reproducing Renaissance Italy in the Long Nineteenth Century

Chairs: **Geraldine A. Johnson**, University of Oxford; **Jacqueline Marie Musacchio**, Wellesley College

Chair Remarks

Photographing Tuscan Renaissance Art: French Expeditions to Mid-Nineteenth Century Florence, **Michele Amedei**

Neo-Renaissance Style: Early Modern Dress Adaptation in 19th Century Fashion, **Lane Eagles**, University of Washington

Reframing the Renaissance for Political Gain: Siena's Sala del Risorgimento, **David Wilkins**, Duquesne University

"More than mere ordering from price-lists": a material history of acquiring The Metropolitan Museum of Art's plaster casts, **Hannah Kinney**, Yale Center for British Art

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Sculpture as a Collective Practice in the Long Nineteenth Century

Chairs: **Apolline Malevez**, Ghent University; **Marjan Sterckx**, Ghent University

Caring for the Studio, **Apolline Malevez**, Ghent University

Paulin Tasset (1839-1921), the main practitioner-reducer at the time of "medaillomania", **Katia Schaal**, Université de Poitiers

Recasting History: The 1893 Columbian Liberty Bell and Peace Plow, **Ellery E. Foutch**, Middlebury College

Gender and collaboration in sculpture in late nineteenth century France and United-Kingdom., **Eva Belgherbi**, Université de Poitiers

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman
🌐 The Achaemenid Body: Making and Reflecting on Achaemenid Art and Fashion Histories

Chairs: **Neville McFerrin**, University of North Texas; **Alexander Nagel**, Fashion Institute of Technology State University of New York

Chair Remarks

When Dacians became Persians in Renaissance Architectural Theory, **Braden Scott**, University of Manitoba

Thinking Through Achaemenid Ornament, **Breton Adam Langendorfer**, Princeton University

The Achaemenid-Style Open-Ended Bracelet with Animal Head Terminals: An Emblematic Object of Achaemenid Imperial Power, **Laleh Javaheri-Saatchi**

Sogdian bodies through the Achaemenid lens, **Fiona Kidd**

Working Clothes for Ancient Miners. The Salt Mummies from Chehrābād and their Textiles, **Karina Grömer**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East

The Art of Collaboration in the Long Eighteenth Century

HISTORIANS OF EIGHTEENTH-CENTURY ART AND ARCHITECTURE

Chairs: **Yasemin Diba Altun**, Duke University - Dept of Art, Art Hist & Visual Studies; **Tori Champion**, University of St Andrews

Layers of Collaboration: The Making of toiles de Jouy, **Melissa Percival**, University of Exeter

Beyond the Inner Chamber?: The Making of Female "Elegant Gathering" Paintings in Late Eighteenth-century China, **Michelle Tian**, Princeton University

Materials as Collaboration in Eighteenth- and Nineteenth-Century Philadelphia, **Cambra Sklarz**, UC Riverside

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

The Art Students League: 150 Years of "American" Art

Chairs: **Ksenia Nouril**, The Museum of Modern Art - MoMA; **Stephanie Cassidy**, The Art Students League of New York

George B. Bridgman, Rodin, Quick Poses and the Modernization of American Life Drawing, **Jeffrey Fontana**, Austin College

Georgia O'Keeffe's Boarding House and What It Reveals, **Linda Maria Grasso**

Yes, the People!: Social Realism and the Art Students League, 1948–51, **Daniel Belasco**, AI Held Foundation

Politics, Aesthetics, and the Art Students League in Helen Levitt's Turn to Color Photography, **Rebecca Zurier**, University of Michigan and **Deborah Dash Moore**, University of Michigan, Frankel Center for Judaic Studies

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

The Case for Working Together, Collaborating Together

COMMUNITY COLLEGE PROFESSORS OF ART AND ART HISTORY

Chair: **Susan M. Altman**, Middlesex College

Discussant: **Monica Anke Hahn**, Historians of British Art

Collections and Collaborations: Studio Art and Art History Students in Dialog with the work of the Royal Chicano Air Force (RCAF), **Mya B. Dosch**, California State University, Sacramento and **Summer Ventis**, California State University Sacramento

Advocating for (Unusual) Faculty Learning Communities, **Maya Jimenez**, BMCC, CUNY and **Cheryl Hogue Smith**

Fostering Success in the classroom, one Google Arts and Culture story at a time, **Sarah Liberatore**

Collaboration as an Entrepreneurial and Intellectual approach to art making, **Adam B. Fung**, TCU

The Case For Fostering Student Collaboration, **Ash Dahlke**, Cochise College

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite

Up in Arms: Aesthetics of Resistance and Solidarity in Contemporary Art

Chairs: **Maximilian Langefeld**, University of Oxford; **Felicia F. Leu**, Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM)

Everyone's East Lake: Artistic Activism and Public Environmental Discourse, **Xinrui Zhang**, The Courtauld Institute of Art

Virtual Empathy: Transforming Design and Social Change through VR, **Marjan Khatibi**, San Jose State University

EPIC DOMESTIC: TOWARDS AN AESTHETIC OF CELEBRATION, ENGAGEMENT, COMMUNITY & CARE, **Clara Zarza**, IE University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

Using Artificial Intelligence proactively as a creative tool in the classroom

Workshop Leader: **Micol Hebron**, Chapman University

Chair Remarks

4:00 PM –5:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Hilton Boardroom

△ Council of Field Editors Meeting

4:00 PM –5:30 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rotunda
ISLAA-ALAA Encuentro for Latin American and Latinx Art at CAA

Reception Contact: JoAnna Reyes, Arizona State University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
AI in Art: Practices, Processes, Doubts, and Revelations

Chairs: Paul Catanese, Columbia College Chicago; Mat Rappaport, Columbia College Chicago

Chair Remarks

AI Interventions with Artist-Made Datasets, Jennifer Lyn Karson, UVM Art + AI Research Group

Feet, Face, Yellow Card, Barbara Rauch, OCAD University

4:30 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom East

🌐 ■ **Annual Artist Interviews**

Panelists: Martha Rosler, Artist; Wendy Red Star, Julia Bryan-Wilson, Columbia University; Josh T. Franco, Archives of American Art, Smithsonian Institution; Charlotte Ickes, National Portrait Gallery, Smithsonian Institution

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite
Art History's Graphic Intelligence

Chairs: Nicholas Robbins, University College London; Allison Stielau, University College London

Discussant: Zeynep Celik Alexander

The Diagram of Shapes and Modern Conceptions of Painted Pottery, Milette Gaifman

Ornament and the Epistemologies of Victorian Graphic Design, Christine Olson

Patterns of Perception, Barbara Jaffee, Northern Illinois University

Amorphous Clouds – Representations of 'Visual Similarity' in Digital Art History, Ellen Charlesworth, Durham University

Louis Marin's graphic imagination, Jérémie Koering, University of Fribourg

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite
Art in Action: Identity, Resistance, and Performance since the 1960s

Chair: Hsin-Yun Cheng, University of Rochester

We are the "pueblo": Art, Solidarity, and the Hispanic Identity in Spain and Cuba during the 1960s., Claudia Grego March, University of California, Santa Barbara

The Subject of Exile: Tehching Hsieh's One-Year Performances, Hsin-Yun Cheng, University of Rochester Library

Co-Producing Cultural Resistance in Orbán's Hungary: The Art Institutional Boycott ofTranzit.hu and Off-Biennale, Izabel Galliera, UMKC

Blood on your hands? Teresa Margolles' "Sobre la sangre" and the Audience as Witness, Felicia F. Leu, Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM)

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

Body As Surface (Landscape)

Discussant: Kristina Kryscynski, University of Washington

Chair Remarks

Hendrick Goltzius's Travel, (Dis)ability Identity, and Artistic Reinvention in Early Modern Europe, Or Vallah Gabaev, University of Washington

The Politics of Labor, Performativity, and Cure in Hi Red Center's Cleaning Event, Tamane Takehara, School of Art Institute of Chicago

Bodily Awareness: Skin as Surface, Trace and Memory, Vanessa Schuster, IDSVA

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Borderlands: Craft Between Cultures

Chair: Amanda Thompson

Chair Remarks

Striking the Common Wind: Ornamental Wrought Iron and the Craft Commons in New Orleans, Hampton Des Smith, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Threads of Identity: Textiles in the Guatemalan Traveling Avant-garde, Andrea García-Rodríguez, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México

Appropriations '76: Florida Native Seminole Patchwork in the Quilting World, Amanda Thompson

John Hitchcock Blanket Songs, Sarah Stolte, Edgewood College

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

Challenges of Teaching: What, Why, How, and Solutions for Right Now

STUDENT AND EMERGING PROFESSIONALS COMMITTEE

Chairs: Susan M. Altman, Middlesex College; Nicole Emser, Temple University; Emma Wingfield, Texas A&M University

Chair Remarks

Challenges Make Us Stronger: Using an Inclusive Art & Design Framework, Beatrice Carey Carter, Rowan University

From Algorithms to Art: process, creation and perception of students using Artificial Intelligence in post-secondary art making, Twyla Exner

Imagining an Inclusive Art History Classroom: Experiential, Team, and Project-Based Learning, Karin Christiaens

Restorative Design: Transforming Practice Through Empathy, Inclusivity, and Justice, Omari Souza

Teaching Introduction to Global Art History Part I: Addressing Challenges in Course Design, Austen Leigh LaRocca, University of Wisconsin - Stevens Point

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

Cross-Cultural Conversations in Visuality and Textuality

Chair: Sheyda Aisha Khaymaz, University of Texas at Austin

Chair Remarks

"Where There is No Vision, the People Perish": A Baldwinian Approach to Black Artistic Love and Liberation, Tiffany Pennamon, University of Florida

Verses on 'Alam: Qur'ānic inscriptions on Shī'a Metal Finials, Zeinab Vessal, GTU-Berkeley

Constructing Ancient India in Nineteenth-Century Japan: Visual and Textual Rhetoric in the Five Hundred Arhats, Zhuolun Xie, Princeton University

Zardazgheneb: Motion, Chaos, and Pathos in the Furigraphy of Hawad, Sheyda Aisha Khaymaz, University of Texas at Austin

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

♦ Digital Art History and the Web: An Introduction to Web Archive Data Analysis

Workshop Leader: Karl Blumenthal, Internet Archive; Sumitra Duncan, Frick Art Research Library

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North

🌐 Expanding Scholarship in Collections of Asian American Artists

Chair: Anna Truxes, CUNY, GC

Chair Remarks

Beyond Asian American Art: Private Practices & An Archive of Becoming, Susette S. Min and Lena Chen, UC Berkeley

Solace in Painting: Questioning "Conflict Art" through the Life and Work of Keisho Okayama, Fletcher Coleman, University of Texas, Arlington

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman

🌐 Gender Violence in Art in the Classical World and Beyond

Chair: Cicek Beeby, Brown University, Classics Department

Chair Remarks

"I carried off ... anything desirable in his palace:" Implications of gender-based violence in Assyrian Palace Reliefs, Megan Cifarelli, Manhattanville College

How the modern myth of sexual dimorphism has impacted the study of Hermaphroditos, Phoebe Mock

Re-contextualizing Gender Violence Panels of Sebasteion at Aphrodisias, Onur Öztürk, Columbia College Chicago

Stroking the Whispering Reeds: Ovid and "Heroic Rape" in German Neo-Idealist Art, Samantha Small, The Graduate Center City University of New York

Teaching Strategies for Addressing Gender Violence in Ancient Greek Art, Cynthia S. Colburn and Ella Gonzalez, Johns Hopkins

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent

Goddess Redux: Feminism and Spirituality in Contemporary Art

THE FEMINIST ART PROJECT

Chairs: Kathleen M. Wentrack, Queensborough Community College, City University of New York; Connie Tell, The Feminist Art Project

Roots of Resistance: The Woman-Tree, Political Activism, and Feminist Spirituality in Ibero-American Art, Diana Angoso De Guzmán, Universidad Complutense de Madrid

Gaia's Return: Earth-Goddesses in Contemporary Indigenous Eco-Activism, Jordan Troeller, Leuphana University Lüneburg

Contemporary Goddesses in Irish art: the work of Jesse Jones and Breda Lynch, Fiona Barber, Manchester Metropolitan University

African Matrilineal Models of Empowerment in the Art of Tabita Rezaire and Josèfa Ntjam, **Monique Kerman**, Western Washington University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Mercury Ballroom

Gran Fury: Activism, Art and Design

Chair: John Lindell, D.A.P. Distributed Art Publishers

Chair Remarks

Gran Fury: Activism, Art and Design, **Richard E. Meyer**, Stanford University

Gran Fury: Activism, Art and Design, **Tom Kalin**, Columbia University

Gran Fury: Activism, Art and Design, **Robert Vazquez Pacheco**, D.A.P. Distributed Art Publishers

Gran Fury: Activism, Art and Design, **Kyle Croft**, Visual AIDS

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

⊕ How do you throw a brick through the window...: Expanding Publics and Embodiments

Chairs: Laurel Vera McLaughlin, Tufts University Art Galleries; Tanya Gayer, John Michael Kohler Arts Center

Chair Remarks

Para-Protest Practices and Restoring Affinity, **Mev Luna**, Parsons School of Design/The New School

Archive, Image, Asylum: contemporary installation art in former psychiatric hospitals, **Sarah Pollman**, Montserrat College of Art

(Dis)Embodied Activism, Precarity, and Contemporary Visual Art, **Stefanie Snider**, Ohio University, University of Wyoming, Lindenwood University, Columbus College of Art and Design

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

Institutional Fatigue in the Twenty-First Century

Chair: Colby Chamberlain, Cleveland Institute of Art

Discussant: Alexander Alberro

Inciting Confrontations: Following Institutional Critique Behind the Museum Wall, **Samuel Shapiro**, Princeton University Department of Art & Archaeology

Institutional Critique in illiberal times, **Ellen Feiss**, Providence College

Art work, art labor: museum problematics and calls to decolonize the art world from inside the house, **Brianne Chapelle**, Hunter College

"Hanging Out at Angela Davis Park: Regina Agu and Gabriel Martinez's Collective Space Making", **Philip Kelleher**, Berea College

The Im/practicability of Institutional Critique, **Luke A.C. Skrebowski**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Liberatory Practices and Black Memory Work

Chair: Michele y Washington, FIT

Discussant: Michele Washington

Chair Remarks

Radical Preservation and Generative History, **Jerome Haferd**, City College of New York

Erasure, Renewal and the Monumental Everyday, **Nina Cooke John**, Studio Cooke John Architecture and Design

Making Space: Centering our Youth and the Future of Black Liberation Care Practices, **Peter Robinson**, Cornell Department of Architecture

"Land as Story." How does land—be it understood as place, territory, or imaginary—tell and hold stories?, **Curry Hackett**, City College of New York

Liberatory Practices and Black Memory Worker, **Michele y Washington**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

Narratives of Exile, Migration, and Movement in Contemporary Art

SOCIETY OF CONTEMPORARY ART HISTORIANS

Chair: Sarah Kleinman, Virginia Commonwealth University

'she walked in reverse': Forced Migration, Diaspora, and Indo-Caribbean Identities in Suchitra Mattai's installations, **Nicole F. Scalissi**, California State University San Bernardino

Hiram Maristany's 'Island in the City': Envisioning Insularity in El Barrio, **Serda Yalkin**, Duke University

Shifting Sands/Shifting Identities: Anh-Thuy Nguyễn's "Thuy & Sand", **Olivia Murphy**, University of Oklahoma

Aesthetic Conversions in the US/Mexico Borderlands: Artist Collective COGNATE and the Work of Migration, **Paloma Checa-Gismero**, Swarthmore College

Manaf Halbouni's Mobile Monument, Mobilistan and Multi-Directional Migration, **Peter M. Chametzky**, University of South Carolina

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

New Technologies and the Re-visualization of Italian Renaissance Art

Chair: Arnold Victor Coonin, Rhodes College

Chair Remarks

Digitally Re-animating the Renaissance, **Eric Hupe**, Lafayette College

Modeling the Present to Illustrate the Past: LiDAR, Photogrammetry, and Reality Capture in Florence, Italy, **George Bent**, Washington and Lee University

The late Renaissance Venetian palace façades: a computational eye on the dialectic of "mediocritas" and "novitas", **Paul Guhenec**

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

Subversive Bodies: Womyn Performing Blackness in the Caribbean and Caribbean Diaspora

Chairs: Hilary R. Whitham Sánchez, Independent Scholar; **Stephanie Gibson**, Hollins University

Chair Remarks

Belkis Ayón and Sikán: Black Sirens, **Gwen A Unger**, Columbia University

"It is a kind of national dress": Creole Women and the Politics of Fashion in Postemancipation Suriname, **Justin Brown**, Boston College

Embodied Ethnography: The Radical Performance Practices of Hurston, Dunham, and Primus in Afro-Caribbean Contexts, **Quiana M. Jackson**, The Pennsylvania State University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

The "Work" of Art in American Culture from the New Deal to Now

Chairs: Mary Okin, Living New Deal; **Jody Patterson**, Ohio State University

Discussant: Warren Carter, The Open University

Chair Remarks

Artistic use of the FSA's Duplicate File, **Phoebe E. Wolfskill**, Indiana University

Preserving 'La Villita': NYA Arts & Craft Training as Labor Opportunity for San Antonio's Mexican-American Youth, **Stephanie Gray**, Duquesne University

Dam Democracy: TVA Architecture and Design at MoMA and Labor Politics in the New Deal, **Schuyler Black-Seitz**, Ohio State University

Printmaking as Labor: Images of Industry from the WPA-Sponsored Fine Print Workshop in Philadelphia, **Joanna Platt**, Temple University

Laboring Through Indians at Work, **Jason Weems**, University of California Riverside

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

Trajectory in Art: Toward a Horizontal Art History of Styles

Chair: Julie Codell, Arizona State University

"The Matrix of Historical Moments: Experimenting with Multivalent Geographies and Styles", **Allison Leigh**, University of Louisiana at Lafayette

Localized Abstraction: Fred Kabotie, Formalist Pedagogy, and Visual Ethics at Hopitutskwa, **Julia Silverman**, Harvard University

Clash of Curatorial Departments: Overcoming Essentialism of Styles, **Kyunghee Pyun**, Fashion Institute of Technology SUNY

Cultural Metabolism: The Trajectivities of Architecture in Denmark c. 1600, **Maria Fabricius Hansen**, University of Copenhagen

4:30 PM –6:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

Unboxing the Long Eighteenth Century

AMERICAN SOCIETY FOR 18TH CENTURY STUDIES

Chairs: Dani Rebecca Ezor, Kenyon College; **Jennifer G. Germann**

Machines for Naturalization: The Cajones of the Spanish Botanical Expeditions, **Rebecca Yuste**, Columbia University

Unveiling the Trans-regional Journey of Red Ginseng: Joseon Korea's Commercial Expansion in the Eighteenth Century, **Jeffrey C Youn**, College of Charleston

"Wat men veerst haelt, dat smaeket soetst": The pomander as a miniature cabinet of curiosities, **Jasper Martens**, University of California Santa Barbara

5:00 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

University of Pennsylvania - History of Art Department Reception

Reception Contact: Gwendolyn Shaw

5:30 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

Brown University History of Art & Architecture Reception

Reception Contact: Carina Haden, Brown University/ Department of the History of Art and Architecture

5:30 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Harlem
Duke University Department of Art, Art History & Visual Studies On-Site Reception CAA 2025

Reception Contact: Paul B. Jaskot, Duke University

5:30 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

Offsite – 11 E. 61st – Lubin House - Syracuse University

Historians of Netherlandish Art Reception

Reception Contact: Ashley West, Temple University, Tyler School of Art & Architecture

5:30 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

Offsite – James B. Duke House, 1 E 78th St
Institute of Fine Arts, NYU CAA Reception

Reception Contact: Denali Elizabeth Kemper, Institute of Fine Arts, NYU

5:30 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West Foyer

J. Paul Getty Trust Reception

Reception Contact: Julie Viereck

5:30 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – New York
Stanford University - Department of Art and Art History

Reception Contact: Diana Vasquez, Stanford University

5:30 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Lincoln
The University of Chicago Department of Art History Reception

Reception Contact: Taiah Wilson

5:30 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – East
WashU AHA Reception

Reception Contact: Brad Parton, Washington University in St. Louis

6:00 PM –7:00 PM FRIDAY, FEB. 14

Offsite – RSVP

Private tour of Krishna Reddy: Heaven in a Wildflower, an exhibition on view at Print Center New York

Saturday A.M. (Feb. 15)

Hours	Weds.	Thurs. & Fri.	Sat.
Registration	Online 24hrs (through February 15)		
In-person Registration:	8:00am–6:00pm	8:00am–6:00pm	8:00am–4:00pm
Sessions (In-person and Hybrid, all times Eastern)	2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm	9:00am–10:30am 11:00am–12:30pm 2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm	9:00am–10:30am 11:00am–12:30pm 2:30pm–4:00pm 4:30pm–6:00pm
In-person Book & Trade Fair:		9:00am–6:00pm	9:00am–2:30pm
Virtual Book & Trade Fair	24hr access, February 12-15		

Upcoming

Opportunities

Keep the momentum going—scan the QR code to explore opportunities, connect with CAA members, and support the field!

collegeart.org

Join us at the CAA 113th Annual Conference February 12–15, 2025, at the New York Hilton Midtown with Hybrid sessions. This year's program boasts over 300 sessions, workshops, and events with content representing the breadth of our constituent fields.

View the CAA website, mobile App and online Schedule for the most complete and up to date information, including recording status. www.collegeart.org

Please note that most on location sessions are not remotely accessible. Recordings of select events will post after the conference.

Presentation titles are listed after the Session title. Information in this pdf is subject to change.

This content is current as of Friday, February 7, 2025.

■ EVENT △ MEETING
⊕ HYBRID ◆ WORKSHOP

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

Anarchist Currents in Contemporary Art

Chair: Allan Antliff, University of Victoria

Chair Remarks

The Discursive Anarchy of John Cage's "Writings through the Essay: 'On the Duty of Civil Disobedience'", **Sandra Skurvida**, Fashion Institute of Technology State University of New York

Siah Armajani's Anarchitectural Monuments, **Eli S Zadeh**, State University of New York

From Phenomenon to Trace: Anarcho-Daoism in Korean Art Activism, **Sooran Choi**, University of Vermont

Anarchism by the Brick: Marcel Broodthaers, Provo, and Happenings in Belgium, c. 1966, **Stefaan Vervoort**, Ghent University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman

🌐 **Art History Fund for Travel to Special Exhibitions: Sharing Stories**

ART HISTORY FUND FOR TRAVEL TO SPECIAL EXHIBITIONS

Chair: Cali Buckley, College Art Association

Chair Remarks

Donatello: Sculpting the Renaissance, **Daniel M Zolli**, Pennsylvania State Univ

Theories and Practices of Conservation in Paris, **Lindsay S. Cook**, Penn State University Deptment of Art History & School of Visual Arts

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse A

🌐 **Artists' Roundtable hosted by Services to Artists Committee**

SERVICES TO ARTISTS COMMITTEE

Chairs: Julian Jason Haladyn, OCAD University; **Amanda L. Lechner**, Virginia Tech

Discussant: Paul Catanese, Columbia College Chicago; **Dianne Smith**, Dianne Smith Art Corp; **Everlena Zoë Charlton**, George Mason University

Chair Remarks

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton South

🌐 **Building Undergraduate Research Skills in a Subject-Led Curriculum**

Chair: Elissa Graff, Kentucky College of Art + Design

Setting the Stage: Reinforcing artistic technical skills while concurrently developing postmodern approaches in studio art foundations, **Damon Arhos**, Kentucky College of Art + Design

General Education as a Foundation for Holistic Development in Art Students, **Bailey Moorhead**, Kentucky College of Art + Design

Synthesizing ideas and research: The Library as integral to the subject and the research, **Sara Franks**, Kentucky College of Art + Design

Research as the Basic Building Block to a Successful BFA Thesis, **Andrew Cozzens**, Kentucky College of Art + Design

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

Calling all art historians! The Isthmo-Colombian Area, the Amazon, and the Antilles in Ancient American Art

Chair: Juliana Ramírez Herrera, University of Toronto / Gardiner Museum of Ceramic Art

Chair Remarks

The Shape of Tairona Time: Art, Technologies, Ecologies, **Eric Mazariegos**, Columbia University

Frog Objects and Images in the Interactive Antilles, **Lawrence Waldron**, CUNY Queens College

Monuments and monumentality in Ancient American rock art: the case of engraved snakes from the middle and upper Orinoco river, **Natalia Lozada-Mendieta**, Universidad De Los Andes

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East

Comparative Diaspora in Art History: Revisiting Diaspora and Visual Culture

Chairs: Gabriel Chazan, University of Wisconsin-Madison; **Benjamin Martin Kersten**

Discussant: Nicholas Mirzoeff; **Anna Evangeline Arabindan-Kesson**

Chair Remarks

Looking for Mildred: Black Queer Feminist Errantry in Mildred Thompson's Abstraction, **Alexandra Thomas**, Fordham University

What Is Diaspora in Palestine?, **Sascha Crasnow**, Drake University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

Connecting In and Out: Toward "Regional" Approaches to Chinese Art

Chairs: Lucien Sun, University of Chicago; **Qinxin He**, Leiden University

The Canonization of Huang Quan: Rethinking the "Typical Style" of Sichuan Painting during the Tang-Song Transition Period, **Qinxin He**, Leiden University

General, Deity, and Filial Son: The Print of Guan Yu from Khara-Khoto and a Visual Schema in Southern Shanxi under the Mongol Rule, **Lucien Sun**, University of Chicago

Pit Tombs and Wooden Coffins: Elite Burials From a Regional Perspective, **Aurelia Campbell**

Shi Lu's Invention of a Socialist Northern Landscape Mode, **Juliane Noth**, Freie Universität Berlin

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite

Designated Assembly Points: Connecting the Dots in Art Administration

NATIONAL COUNCIL OF ART ADMINISTRATORS

Chairs: **O. Gustavo Plascencia**, New World School of the Arts; **Elissa C. Armstrong**, VCU School of the Arts

Discussant: **Paige Williams**

Reflections On Teaching Social Engagement, **Daniel Oliver Tucker**, Arts In Society/Common Ground Research Networks

At your service: Carp and the new curators of Los Angeles, **Homer Charles Arnold**, University of California, Riverside

Adjunct Betterment (what can we do?), **Christopher T Kaczmarek**, Montclair State University

Using Your Community to Bridge the Gap in Experiential Learning Opportunities, **Stephanie R. Thulin**, VCU School of the Arts

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

DHS-Sponsored Panel: New Directions in Teaching Design History

DESIGN HISTORY SOCIETY

Chair: **Sally-Anne Huxtable**, Design History Society

Chair Remarks

Revising The Design History Reader for a Second Edition, **Grace Lees-Maffei**, University of Hertfordshire and **Rebecca D. Houze**, Northern Illinois University

Teaching Graphic Design in/of the Arab World, **Yasmine Nachabe Taan**, Lebanese American University

How the DHS Supports Design History Writing, **Elli Young**, Middlesex University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

Expanding the Practice of Research: Transdisciplinarity in Art and Art History

COMMITTEE ON RESEARCH AND SCHOLARSHIP

Chairs: **Emily Walz**, New York Public Library; **Brian Campbell**, University of North Texas

Discussant: **Jessica Braum**, Temple University

Chair Remarks

Not art, not an essay: the role of annotated drawings in transdisciplinary research, **Kelly Chorpening**, University of Nevada, Reno

Pretend it's a Painting! Meaning in Materiality and the Reading of Paintings as Paintings, **Hannah De Corte**, FRS-FNRS, Université de Namur (Belgium)

Unruly Collaborations: Rethinking Agency and Ethics in Artist-Researcher Partnerships, **Krista Bailie**, UBC Department of Art History, Visual Art and Theory

Tearing up Vogue and Mining the Detritus, **Ehryn Torrell**, Bath Spa University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

Forms of Friendship: An Educator's How-To For a Socially Engaged Classroom

Workshop Leader: **Arthur Russell**, Johns Hopkins University; **Suzanne Gold**, Johns Hopkins University; **Carly Schnitzler**, Johns Hopkins

Chair Remarks

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

Highlights in Undergraduate Art & Design Research (Session 1)

STUDENT AND EMERGING PROFESSIONALS COMMITTEE

Chairs: **Emma Wingfield**, Texas A&M University; **Nicole Emser**, Temple University

Chair Remarks

Sifting Wheat and Shifting Meanings: Interpreting Gustave Courbet's Les Cribleuses de Blé as a Political Allegory, **Aine Powers**

Barbara Walker: Progress in the Form of Figuration, **Walker Harris**, Fordham University

A Cautionary Tale: The Paradox of Afro-Argentine Visibility and Exclusion in Post-Abolition Urban Scenes, **Mia Jodorcovsky**, Concordia University

Exploring Japanese Prints: A Collaborative Investigation into Japanese Prints within the Art Museum of WVU, **Kelsey Clodfelter**, West Virginia University

Looked Through: Edward Orme's Transparent Prints and Aesthetics of Transparency, **Benet Ge**

Sargent's Silk and Steel: Beauty, Investment, and Innovation, **Lauren Wood**, Fordham University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North

Imaging Identity: The Moving Image, Identity Politics, and the Long 1990s

Chair: **Jessica Bardsley**, New York University

Chair Remarks

Illness as Identity in Gregg Bordowitz's Fast Trip, Long Drop, **Carolyn Bailey**

Networked Bodies: Identity and the Internet in Shu Lea Cheang's Brandon, **Megan Driscoll**, University of Richmond

Sexuality, Race, and Performance in the 1990 film works of Jack Waters and Peter Cramer, **Louis Chavez**, George Eastman Museum

Ayoka Chenzira and Intersectionality as Generational Praxis, **Liz Kim**, Texas A&M University-Kingsville

Teaching weaving to computer scientists: Analog craft processes for STEM students, **Sasha Baskin**, Johns Hopkins University Center for Visual Arts

Academic Office Gallery: Fostering Creativity and Community through Artist Collaborations, **Sarah Newlands**, Portland State University

The Breathe Project, **Deborah Johnson**, Pratt Institute

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

Indigenous Art Exhibitions In and Out of the Americas. Are We Learning to Listen?

Chairs: **Camilla Querin**, Ohio Wesleyan University; **Paulina Pardo Gaviria**, California State University Long Beach

Chair Remarks

An Inclusive Gesture: Peru's Participation in the 14th Bienal de São Paulo (1977), **Katerina Valdivia Bruch**

Curating with the Earth: Indigenous Material Practices and the Reimagining of Art, **Maria Camila Montalvo-Senior**, Universidad Nacional de Colombia

Denilson Baniwa's Nakoada: Ancestral Responsibility and the Modern Art Week, **Nayla Ramalho**, University of Southern California

Sacred Stitches: The Culture and Curation of Métis Beadwork, **Gabrielle Patrone**, Rhode Island College

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Lincoln
△ National Committee for History of Art - Business Meeting

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
Next Now: Studio Art Foundations
FOUNDATIONS IN ART: THEORY AND EDUCATION

Chairs: **Niberca Lluberés**, Parsons School of Design/The New School; **Meredith Starr**, Foundations In Art: Theory & Education; **Jaime Carrejo**

Chair Remarks

Transcending the Instructor's Lens: Reimagining Studio Foundations through Digital Fluency and an Inclusive Art Future, **Derek G. Brueckner**, University of Manitoba

Channelers: AI, authorship, mysticism and meaning making in creative practice and pedagogy, **Anna Huff**, Hamilton College

Learning to Explore: How the darkroom serves as more than a space for making photos, **Will Haggart Jacks**, Troy University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Race in South Asian Art

AMERICAN COUNCIL FOR SOUTHERN ASIAN ART

Chairs: **Meghaa Ballakrishnen**, Johns Hopkins University; **Mohit Manohar**, The University of Chicago

Chair Remarks

Civilizing 'Kala': Blackness, Servitude, and the Colonial Subject in Company-era Painting, **Yuthika Sharma**, Northwestern University

Ways of Seeing Hindu Gods, **Rohini Iyengar Vadapalli**

What We Call Race in the United States, We Call Caste in India, **Gary Michael Tartakov**, Iowa State University

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
Reconsidering Religion in Modern and Contemporary Art: Methods and Approaches

ASSOCIATION OF SCHOLARS OF CHRISTIANITY IN THE HISTORY OF ART

Chairs: **Linda H. Stratford**, Asbury University; **Hannah Hempstead**, Association of Scholars of Christianity in the History of Art (ASCHA)

"A Complicated Business": Corita Kent's Intertextual Art Practice and the Catholic Left, **Kevin Hatch**, Binghamton University

Reimagining Christianity in Chinese Modern and Contemporary Art: Modernity, Social Issues, and Artistic Practice, **Jiushuang Chen**

"Frozen out of Liturgy": Orthodox Christian Aesthetics as Method in Contemporary Art History, **Nadezhda Gribkova**, The University of Chicago

'Hermeneutics and Methodology in Theology and the Visual Arts': a new project at KCL, **Chloe Reddaway**, King's College London

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Sea Inside: Oceanic Interiority in Art and Visual Culture

Chairs: **Pandora Syperek**, Loughborough University London; **Sarah Wade**, University of East Anglia

Deformed Milieus: Symbolism in Architecture and the Nineteenth-Century Aquarium, **Madeline Porsella**, Yale University

Exhibiting Sculpture Underwater: A History of Milieu, **Alex Zivkovic**, Columbia University

A sea of resilience: Oceanic (in)visibility, **Karen Jacobs**, University of East Anglia

How to Measure / Cutting Short, **Annie Simpson**, Harvard University and **James A Enos**, The University of Georgia

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West **Spectacles of Nationhood: World's Fairs and Italian Identity Formation**

ITALIAN ART SOCIETY

Chair: Lucia Colombari, University of Oklahoma

FIAT, International Expositions, and the Stile Liberty: Design for a New Century, **Peter Clericuzio**, Syracuse University and The Italian Academy at Columbia University

Italian Fascism on Display: The Italian Pavilion at the Century of Progress World Exposition, 1933-34, **Ranelle Knight-Lueth**

Fascism, Italian-Americans, and the 1939 New York World's Fair, **James Fortuna**, University of St Andrews

Architectures of Becoming: Italy's Democratic Narrative at Expo 58, **Lucia Colombari**, University of Oklahoma

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Introductions and Keynote

Welcome, **Connie Tell**, The Feminist Art Project

Science & Art Introduction, **Anonda M Bell**, Paul Robeson Galleries

Unnatural Sciences: An Overview, **Anne K. Swartz**, Savannah College of Art and Design

Keynote Address, **Suzanne Anker**, School of Visual Arts

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – East **The Graduate Center, City University of New York Alumni Breakfast**

Reception Contact: Jennifer Ball

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

The Power of Body Transformations

Chairs: Brandee Newkirk, Duke University - Dept of Art, Art Hist & Visual Studies; **Jessica Lynn Orzulak**

Chair Remarks

Given over to Repair: The Bodily Performances of Robbie McCauley, Nona Faustine, and Michaela Pilar Brown, **Crystal am Nelson**, University of Colorado, Boulder

Blood, Lies, and Videotape: AIDS Panic and the Transformation of Ron Athey, **Lauren Ashley DeLand**, Savannah College of Art and Design, Atlanta

Kinesthetic Transformation: The Dance Floor as Experimental Material, **Anna Cahn**, State University of New York Stony Brook - Department of Art

Reimagining the Social Condition in Brazilian Video Art, **Catalina Chernavsky Sequeira**, The University of Texas at Austin

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite

Workers of the Land: Representing Revolutionary Peasant and Agrarian Movements

Chair: Aaron Katzeman, University of California, Irvine

Chair Remarks

Lessons on the Ground: Eldzier Cortor in the Sea Islands, **Claire Ittner**

Field Work: Tina Modotti and the Free Schools of Agriculture, México, 1926-1932., **Nikki Moore**, Wake Forest University

Franjo Mraz: Self-Taught Peasant Artist Between the Local and the Global, **Bojana Videkanic**, University of Waterloo

Cultivating Struggle: Ed Greevy's Protest Portraiture in the Farming Community of Waiāhole-Waikāne, **Aaron Katzeman**, University of California, Irvine

9:00 AM –10:30 AM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

"The slippery nature of the self": Gender, Masquerade, Counterfactual History, and Jewish Women Artists

Chair: Susan Felleman, University of South Carolina

Rosalyn Drexler and the Flatness of Selfhood, **Beni Muhl**, University of Fribourg

Jewishness under erasure: Persona work in the UK, **Rachel Garfield**, Royal College of Art

Like a Motion Picture, Like a Living Dance: Persona and Performativity in Hannah Wilke's 'So Help Me Hannah' (1978-85), **Philomena Epps**, University College London

Lynn Hershman Leeson: a posthuman feminist counternarrative, **Paula Burleigh**, Allegheny College

10:00 AM –12:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Hudson
△ **Publications Committee Business Meeting**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite
After: Re-imagining, Reinvigorating, and Resetting the Academic Art Gallery After, and Beyond

Chair: Margaret Pezalla-Granlund, TCNJ Art Gallery

Unlearning Curating and Learning Faculty Collaboration, **Stefanie Dlugosz-Acton**, University of North Texas

Post-internet Curation, Monitoring a Methodology., **Kitty Whittell**, University College London

Curatorial Empathy in a Campus on Crisis, **Tamar Mayer**, Tel Aviv University

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

⊕ **Alternative Approaches to Abstraction in Asia: Ecology, Science, and the Senses in Early Twentieth-Century Abstract Art**

Chair: Kuiyi Shen, University of California, San Diego

Discussant: Alicia Volk, University of Maryland

Chair Remarks

The Sublime of White: Abstraction, Tactility and Cultural Imagination in 1930s Japanese Art, **Stephanie Su**

Concreteness and Historicity: The Value and Role of Abstraction in Early Twentieth-Century Korean Art and Design, **Mina Kim**, University of Alabama

Fua Haribhitak: Abstraction and the Faded Copy, **Chanon Kenji Praepipatmongkol**, McGill University

The Invention of Pure Forms: Abstraction, Art, and Science in Early Twentieth-Century China, **Yiqing Li**, University of Macau

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman
⊕ **Artists and their Objects: The Material World of the Early Modern Artist**

Chair: Jesse Locker, Portland State University

Chair Remarks

Artist, Relieved of his Objects: The Lessons of a 1633 Roman Burglary, **James Harper**, Pennsylvania State University

The artist as collector in Venice during the 16th and 17th centuries, **Linda Borean**, Università di Udine

Michelangelo's Memoranda and the Domesticity of Art, **Raymond Carlson**

Transmedial Migrations in Neri di Bicci's Laboratory of Materiality, **Laura Stefanescu**, Istituto Nazionale di Studi sul Rinascimento

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North
⊕ **Brazilian Landscapes: Representing Nature, Culture, and Otherness in Brazil from Early Modernity to the Present**

Chair: Maria Berbara, Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro

Notes on an Overdue Phenomenon: The Rise of Indigenous Art in Brazil, **Camila Maroja**, Brandeis University

Nature and Culture in Cartographic Representations of Extractivist Practices in Brazil, **Maria Berbara**, Universidade do Estado do Rio de Janeiro

Other Ecology, Ecology of Otherness: Nature and Culture in Roberto Burle Marx's Work, **Vera Siqueira**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

⊕ **Creativity, Consumption, and Spectacle: Interrogating "Collectible" Design**

DESIGN STUDIES FORUM

Chairs: Colin Fanning, Bard Graduate Center; Erica N. Morawski, Pratt Institute

Chair Remarks

Distinction or Integration? Collectible Design and Shanzhai in China's Product Landscape, **Dan Mu**

Collecting Monograms: Crest Albums and Personal Branding in Victorian England, **Brockett Horne**, Boston University

Sourcing and Communicating About Heritage Objects: An Ethical Standards Framework for Consumers and Media, **Nasozi Kakembo**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse A

⊕ **Curatorial Pedagogy and Practice**

Chairs: Elyse Longair, CAA; Julian Jason Haladyn, OCAD University

Chair Remarks

The Pedagogy of Planned Obsolescence: Temporary Partnerships and Short-Term Projects in the Curatorial Practice Classroom, **Jeffrey Cudlin**, MICA

Exploring Curatorial Strategies in an Academic Library Gallery, **Jiaying Dai**, George Mason University and **Stephanie Grimm**, George Mason University

Curatorial practice to learn about stored collections: the case of the Schaudapot, **Lara Corona**, Universitat Internacional de Catalunya

Slow Curating: The nexus of museology, curating, and social practice, **Megan Arney Johnston**, Century College / Minneapolis College

Shifting Intimacy Narratives in Lesbian Photography: Developing a Distinctly Lesbian Gaze, **Adriana Croce**, Hobart and William Smith Colleges

The Presence and Meaning of Military Iconography on Coinage in 12th Century Byzantium, **Sonia Suben**, Kenyon College

Insurgents and Installations: The Contemporary Museum Experience, **Grace Monteith**, Fordham University

"Thy Kingdom That on These Erring Shafts Comes": Tracing Queer Bloodlines in Early Depictions of Saint Sebastian, **Ryan Moore**

Design Management in Sports: How design research is shaping the future of Formula 1, **Julia Yu**, University of the Arts London

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Americas Hall

Figurative Master Class with Alex Bostic

Chair: Alexander Bostic

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

From Made to Making: Ongoing Acts of Creation in Colonial Latin America

Chairs: Ximena Alexandra Gomez, University of Massachusetts Amherst; **Derek Burdette**, University of Florida, School of Art + Art History

Making Relations: Nahua Precious Art as Material Socialization, **Allison Caplan**, Yale University

(Re)Writing History in Mesoamerican Painted Manuscripts, **Hayley Woodward**

Moving Parts: Sculpture in Eighteenth-Century Quito and Beyond, **Susan Webster**, The College of William & Mary

The Rhythms of Labor: Afro-Peruvian Instrumentations in the 18th-century Haciendas of Nazca, Peru, **Maria Carrillo Marquina**, Tulane University

Toward the identification of Afro-Peruvian potting traditions, **Brendan Weaver**, Department of Art History Florida State University

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent

Icons of the Midwest: Engaging and Examining Collections

MIDWEST ART HISTORY SOCIETY

Chair: Erica Warren

Chair Remarks

Fordland: Re-examining Icons of Industry and Modernity through University of Michigan Collections, **Robin K. Williams**, University of Michigan Museum of Art

Centering Artworks: An Object-Focused Reinstallation, **Katherine Alcauskas**, Chazen Museum of Art

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

In Memoriam Trina Robbins: New Research in the History of Women Cartoonists

Chair: John Cunnally, Iowa State University

Chair Remarks

The Comics Legacy of Trina Robbins, **Kim Munson**, Neurotic Raven

Trina Robbins' Decades-Long Commitment to LGBTQ+ Comics and Lives, **Margaret Galvan**, University of Florida - Department of English

Drawing back: Barbara Brandon-Croft's Where I'm Coming From (1991-2005), **Helene Tison**, Tours University

Thoroughly Meta: Zoe Thorogood and the Paradoxes of Metafictional Graphic Memoir, **Chris Gavaler**

Trina Robbins: Feminist Activist as Friend and Mentor, **Sydney Heifler**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

Highlights in Undergraduate Art & Design Research (Session 2)

STUDENT AND EMERGING PROFESSIONALS COMMITTEE

Chairs: Emma Wingfield, Texas A&M University; **Nicole Emser**, Temple University

Chair Remarks

Seeing Is Believing: A Case Study of York Minster's St. William Window, **Kit Gonifas**, Nebraska Wesleyan University

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

Let the Land Hold You: Place & Memory

Chair: Dakota Mace, Institute of American Indian Arts

Chair Remarks

the birds above me place me on the ground: The Power of Wonder, **Daisy Trudell-Mills**

An Exploration of Memory, Resistance, and Creativity Amid Environmental Flux, **Leah Mata Fragua**, Institute of American Indian Arts

Dahodiyinii (Sacred Places), **Dakota Mace**, Institute of American Indian Arts

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

Ouch! The Artist's Body and How to Care for It Long Term

Chair: Elizabeth Schlatter

Show Me Your Sources: An Occupational Health and Safety Perspective on Artist's Work-Related Injury and Illness, **Sarah Van Dyck**

Roundtable Discussion Participant: OUCH! THE ARTIST'S BODY AND HOW TO CARE FOR IT LONG TERM, **Missy Graff Ballone**, Wellness for Makers

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East
Presenting Contemporary Art in Museums, ca. 1880-1930: Temporary Exhibitions, Institutional Networks and Collecting

SOCIETY FOR THE HISTORY OF COLLECTING

Chairs: Ulrike Müller, University of Antwerp; Anne Helmreich, Archives of American Art, Smithsonian Institution

Building "one of the most solid glories of French art" : the oeuvre of Barye in museums, a transatlantic perspective, **Justine Gain**, Metropolitan Museum of Art - European Sculpture and Decorative Arts

Accommodating New Expressions and an Increasing Public Commitment to Art: The Emergence of Museums of Modern Art in the Netherlands, **Laurie Cosmo**, Leiden University

Modernist Magazines and Museum Collections, **Lori Cole**, New York University

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

Re - Opening the '85 New Wave Movement

Chairs: Orianna Cacchione, University of Richmond; Katie Grube, University of California, Davis

Discussant: Jennifer Lee, School of the Art Institute of Chicago

Chair Remarks

Rethinking "Human": Pond Society, Automation Fever, and the Disappearance of the Laboring Body, **Linda Huang**

New Wave Materials: Shi Hui, Zhu Wei, Gu Wenda and Liang Shaoji's Fiber Art, **Orianna Cacchione**, University of Richmond

From Primeval Chaos to the New History Group: a 'minor' history of the '85 New Wave, **Jiaqi Kang**, University of Oxford

Reconsidering Social(ist) Movements through Dara Birnbaum's Tian'anmen Break In Transmission, **Katie Grube**, University of California, Davis

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Regionalist and Other Decolonizing Perspectives: Honoring TK Sabapathy's Ideas and Lifework

Chair: Roger Nelson, Nanyang Technological University

Chair Remarks

Theory from Historiography: TK Sabapathy's Writings on Southeast Asian Art, **Pamela Nguyen Corey**, Fulbright University Vietnam

Further Than the Eye Can See: Sabapathy's Southeast Asia as Critical Regionalism, **Vera Mey**, University of York

Decoloniality and the Purchase of the Pre-Modern: Views from Southeast Asian Fields, **Ashley Thompson**

The Re-Arrival of Modern Photography in Singapore, **Charmaine Toh**, Tate

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
Symbolist Movement and the Bible

ART, LITERATURE, AND MUSIC IN SYMBOLISM AND DECADENCE

Chair: Rosina Neginsky, University of Illinois

Chair Remarks

The Symbolists & Saint Francis: Charles-Marie Dulac's Cantique des créatures, **Cassandra M Sciortino**, Diablo Valley College

"Multivalence in Symbolist Presentations of Spiritual and Mystical Transfixion", **Andrew Kent-Marvick**, Southern Utah University

Symbolism, the Symbol of the Tree and the Claudelian Theater, **Jana Kantorikova**

Wearing the halo: the divine rematerialized in Symbolism., **Liesbeth Grotenhuis**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

The 1990s: Turn to the Contemporary

Chair: James S. Meyer, National Gallery of Art

Chair Remarks

MANIFOLD DIFFERENTIATION: THE CONTEMPORARY TURN, **Terence E. Smith**, University of Pittsburgh

Critique from Within and Without: The 1993 Whitney Biennial, **Nicholas C Morgan**, Hampden-Sydney College

Ver América: Catalyzing a Generation of Contemporary Latin American Artists in 1992 Antwerp, **Jennifer Josten**, University of Pittsburgh

Back to the Camera: Borders of the Contemporary in Lens-Based Art from the late 1990s, **Heather Diack**, Toronto Metropolitan University

11:00 AM –12:40 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #1: PEOPLE

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #1: PEOPLE, **Stephanie Dinkins**, State University of New York Stony Brook - Department of Art

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #1: PEOPLE, **Heather Dewey Hagborg**, The Feminist Art Project

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #1: PEOPLE, **Magdalena Dukiewicz**, The Feminist Art Project

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite

The Medieval lives! Technologies and Medieval Afterlives

Chair: Allison Stielau, University College London

Chair Remarks

Pixels, Parchment, and Pleasers (Oh My!): Representation and Medieval/Modern Queer Communities, **Baylee Woodley**, University College London

The Forensic Magdalene: Bones, Technology and the Importance of Representation, **Lauren Rozenberg**, University of East Anglia

The Mediation of Early Medieval Textiles: Repeated Modes of Reproduction and the Nazi Ahnenerbe Project, **Millie Horton-Insch**, Trinity College Dublin

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West

The Visual Culture of Festivals in Germany, Scandinavia, and Central Europe

HISTORIANS OF GERMAN, SCANDINAVIAN, AND CENTRAL EUROPEAN ART AND ARCHITECTURE

Chair: Michelle Oing

THE MEDIEVAL ORIGINS OF THE POLISH "SZOPKA", **Kamil Kopania**, The Aleksander Zelwerowicz National Academy of Dramatic Art in Warsaw

Wood Sculpture, Weather, and Medieval Festivals of the Cross, **Gregory C. Bryda**, Columbia University

Games of Chivalry and the Racial Imagination, **Alexander Bevilacqua**, Williams College

Travelling Exhibition or Festival? Baltic Art and German Propaganda during World War I, **Kristina Joekalda**

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

♦ Toward an Inclusive Framework: (Re)Building Black Art Histories

Workshop Leader: Noah Kane-Small; Kailyn Gibson

11:00 AM –12:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Who's Afraid of Western Art History? : Pedagogy, Research and Impact of Western Art History in Korea

Chair: Jieun Rhee, Association of Western Art History

Discussant: Miguel de Baca, Getty Foundation; **Hyewon Yi**, SUNY Old Westbury

Chair Remarks

Studying and Teaching Western Early Modern Art History in Korea, **Sooyun Sohn**, Hongik University

Early Modern European Art in Korea and the Global Turn in the History of Art, **Jeongho Park**, Seoul National University

Constructing the 'Avant-Garde' in Korean Art and Writings (1961-1971), **Yeon Shim Chung**, Hongik University

Navigating No Man's Land: Interdisciplinary Perspectives on Korean Contemporary Art within Western Art History, **Jung-Ah Woo**

12:30 PM –1:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Holland
△ **Annual Conference Committee Business Meeting**

12:30 PM –2:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – Midtown
CAA-Getty-NCHA International Member Reception

Reception Contact: Cali Buckley, College Art Association

1:00 PM –2:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite
△ **American Council for Southern Asian Art - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
△ **Association of Scholars of Christianity in the History of Art - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
△ **Foundations in Art: Theory and Education - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West
△ **Historians of German, Scandinavian, and Central European Art and Architecture - Business Meeting**

1:00 PM –2:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East
△ **Society for the History of Collecting - Business Meeting**

1:30 PM –2:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 4th Floor – New York
■ **CAA Meet and Greet II**

1:30 PM –2:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G
The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #2: EXPERIENCE

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #2: EXPERIENCE, Laura Splan, Independent Artist

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #2: EXPERIENCE, Eva Lee

Saturday P.M. (Feb. 15)

■ EVENT △ MEETING
🌐 HYBRID ♦ WORKSHOP

2:00 PM –4:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Main Entrance, Hotel Lobby

Gallery Tour - tickets required

2:00 PM –5:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

Offsite – LevyArts - 40 East 19th Street #3R

Leonardo Art and Science Evening Rendezvous

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

A Permeable Nature – When Studio and Environment Merge

Chair: Jan Wurm, Berkeley Art Project

SEHNSUCHT, DISPLACEMENT and COMMENSALISM, Renate Aller

The World Within Me, April Gornik

Pruning as Metaphor, Rebecca Allan, Pratt Institute-- Department of History of Art and Design

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

Activating "X as Intersection: Writing on Latinx Art"

US LATINX ART FORUM

Chairs: Adriana Zavala, US Latinx/Art Forum; Mary Margaret Thomas, US Latinx Art Forum (USLAF)

Discussant: Tatiana E. Flores

Chair Remarks

Colonial Racial Capitalism, Kency Cornejo

Sacred Futurities, Josh Franco

Praxis as Form, Elizabeth V Ferrer

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Anonymity in Art and Visual Culture

Chair: Christine Slobogin, University of Rochester

The Masked Nude: Anonymity, Eroticism, and Artistic Instruction, William Sharpe

Dressing, Performing, Anonymizing "La Petite Chinoise", Jin Wang, CUNY Graduate Center

Plants, Screens, and Rückenfiguren: Sharing and Withholding in the Work of Njideka Akunyili Crosby, Max Rosenberg, David Zwirner

"Women whose faces alone are hidden": pornography and nineteenth-century gynecology, Brynne Darby McBryde, University of Maryland

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

Approaches to Bilingual Typography in Design Practice and Pedagogy

Chair: Mary Y Yang, Boston University

Multiscript typography: tools, strategies, and challenges in the classroom, Dina Benbrahim, University of Connecticut

Vertical Hangul Typesetting in Practice and Recent Developments, James Chae, Hongik University

Multilingual Typography in Practice, Golnar Katrahmani

Designing with Language(s): Pedagogical Reflections in Multilingual Classrooms, Xinyi Li, Pratt Institute

Aesthetics of Bilingual Typography, Sajad Amini, DePaul University

Strategies of Hierarchy and Harmony in Setting Devanagari with Latin Type, Aasawari Suhas Kulkarni, Corcoran School of the Arts & Design

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

♦ Censorship, Precarity, and Diversity: A Workshop

COMMITTEE ON DIVERSITY PRACTICES

Chairs: Andrea Horisaki-Christens, University of California, Los Angeles; SaeHim Park, Xavier University of Louisiana; Katie Anania, Society of Contemporary Art Historians

Discussant: Natilee Harren, University of Houston School of Art

Chair Remarks

Fragile Spaces: Challenges to Organizing Arts-based Approaches to Dementia, Herb Fondevilla, Rikkyo University

Navigating Censorship and Precarity at the University of Wyoming Art Museum, Michelle Sunset

Beyond the White Cube: Self-Organized Exhibitions in Beijing's Artist Communities, Huiyao Niuniu Sun, York University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse A

Decoding the Discipline of Art History - What is it, How to do it, & Why it matters

Workshop Leader: Sarah S. Archino, Furman University; Rose Trentinella, The University of Tampa

Chair Remarks

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill East

Ecologies of Islands in Contemporary Art: From Colonial Imaginaries to International Flows

Chairs: Elena A. Stylianou; Kathleen Ditzig

Chair Remarks

Liquid Landscapes: Water tunnels, flamingos, and radar sounds in contemporary art from Cyprus, Elena A. Stylianou

Island Art Ecologies: Singapore's Freeport from Duty-Free Art to Blockchain Data, Kathleen Ditzig

Archipelagic Futurisms: Exhibition Case Studies for a Framework of Rethinking the World, Carlos Jr Quijon

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
Explosive Objects: Material Histories of Violence in Europe, 1920s-1940s

Chair: Özge Karagöz, Northwestern University

Discussant: Jane A. Sharp

Chair Remarks

Kruchenykh's Explosive Prints: Elemental Anarchy in the Gelatine Press and the Gelatine Bomb, Kamila Kocialkowska, University of Warwick

Subversive Objects: Clandestine Surrealist Publications Under Nazi Occupation, Barbora Bartunkova, Yale University

Fugitive Avant-garde, Adrienn Kácsor, Bauhaus-Universität

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

Feminist Dialectics: Unheard Voices and Canonical Figures

Chair: Yerang Park, University of British Columbia

Chair Remarks

Repetition, Gestures, and Double Negation: Luciano Fabro's Penelope and Carla Lonzi's Feminism in the 1970s, Yerang Park, University of British Columbia

Did Premodern China Have Great Women Artists?, Rose Ting-Yi, University of Toronto

An "Awful Dichotomy" on Display: Curatorial Approaches to Alice Neel's Controversial 'Degenerate Madonna', Kelly Richman-Abdou, University of Birmingham

The Feminist Art of Agnes Millen Richmond and her Radical Students: Unbowed in the Early Twentieth Century, David Stewart, University of Alabama in Huntsville

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent
Legacies & Learning: Connecting Art, History, and Education

Chair: Scott Singeisen, North Carolina Central University

Chair Remarks

'Under the Sign of Saturn'? Gisèle Freund's Photographs of Walter Benjamin at the Bibliothèque nationale Reconsidered, Phoebe Day, The Courtauld Institute of Art

Collaboration in Boston: The Legacy of Allan Rohan Crite, Christina Michelin, Museum of Fine Arts, Boston and Diana Seave Greenwald

The Influence of Fine Art Printmaking on Architectural Image Production and Reception, Scott Singeisen, North Carolina Central University

Public Sphere in Dystopia: a Game-based Youth Participatory Action Research, Kathy Zhou, University of Toronto and Charlie Pullen, University of Toronto Schools

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Mapping Color in History-DH project in action

Chair: Jinah Kim, Harvard University

Chair Remarks

Seeing Color in History through material science: Changing palettes in Indian manuscripts, Katherine Eremin

Finding artisanal intelligence in yellow: Nepalese manuscripts and processed orpiment, Jinah Kim, Harvard University and Erin Mysak, Harvard University Library

Inside an early sixteenth-century Indian Artists' Workshop: Technical and Scientific Insights into the Dispersed Bhagavata Purana, Vaishnavi Patil, Harvard University and Celia Chari, Harvard Art Museums

Lost amidst color: Fields of flowers and the dispersed Tularam Bhagavata Purana, Nandita Punj

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman

**🌐 Moving Pictures, Living Objects
(International Center for Medieval Art
sponsored session)**

INTERNATIONAL CENTER OF MEDIEVAL ART

Chairs: Heather Pulliam, University of Edinburgh;
Kathryn M Rudy

Notre-Dame Through the Eyes of Jean de Jandun,
Lindsay S. Cook, Penn State University Deptment of
Art History & School of Visual Arts

*Shifting Shadows: Using Virtual Reality to revive
Dynamic Lighting Conditions for Gilded Panel Paintings,*
Sanne Frequin, Universiteit Utrecht

*Wie man Skulpturen aufnehmen soll: A Continuing
Question in the Study of Gothic Sculpture,* **Jacqueline
E. Jung**, Yale University

*Reanimating the Inert: Digitising Haptics and Mourning
in Japanese Buddhist Handscrolls,* **Halle O'Neal**,
University of Edinburgh

*Spycraft – Medieval Books and the Magic Lantern: The
Unfolding Revelation of Scripture in the Évangélaire de
la Sainte-Chapelle,* **Thomas Rainer**, Art Historical
Institute, University of Zurich

*Late Gothic Micro-Architectural Designs: 3D-Modeling
the Basel Goldschmiederrisse,* **Martin Schwarz**,
University of Chicago

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy
West

**Networks, Solidarities and Intersections:
Representations of Black, African and Asian
Historical and Contemporary Space**

Chairs: Cissie Fu, LASALLE College of the Arts,
University of the Arts Singapore; Denise S. Ryner, ICA
University of Pennsylvania; Zairong Xiang, Duke
Kunshan University

Chair Remarks

*Mansudae Overseas Project: Between North Korea and
Africa,* **Nectar Knuckles**

Afro-Asian Intersections and British Art Education,
Kristina Centore, Institute of Contemporary Art
University of Pennsylvania

*Porcelain Redux: Afro-Asian materialities in
contemporary Brazilian art,* **Lee Xie**

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite

New Painting: Recentered Perspectives

Chair: Mo Zhang, University of Pennsylvania

Chair Remarks

*On the Periphery, In Flux: David Diao's Counter-
Hegemonic Abstraction,* **Jianda Wang**, University of
California Irvine

*Intercontinental Shifts: Sandú Darié and the
Reconfiguration of Post-War Painting in the Americas,*
Roxane Ilias, Sorbonne Université

*Fluid Brushstrokes: Firelei Báez, the African Diaspora,
and a new notion of Latinidad,* **Kendra Lyimo**,
University of Notre Dame

*Push Out the Awning: A Coded Way of Looking in 15th-
Century Chinese Painting,* **Mo Zhang**, University of
Pennsylvania

*"Block Bro Brooklyn Bro": The Origin Myth of New York
Graffiti and Transnational Hybrids--case study of
Belgrade, Serbia,* **Srdan Tunić**, Temple University

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon
Ballroom

**Poetic Explorations of Cultural Diversity: A
Study of Artistic Narratives and Perspectives
within Western Frameworks**

Chair: Chanhee Choi, University of New Mexico

Chair Remarks

Oddments, **Elnaz Javani**, Colorado State University

*Finding Home: Layering Time and Space through
Projection,* **Cecilia Kim**, University of Notre Dame

*Probing 'Assistive' Futures: Shifting imaginaries/
narratives with people with disabilities in India, Canada,
and Germany,* **Puneet Jain**

*Ephemeral Tattoo - Site-specific mixed reality digital art
projects for heritage sites,* **Jessica Fu**, Toronto
Metropolitan University

*M(o)AR, HYBRID LANDSCAPE: Radio waves as an
extended ecology.,* **Esteban Agosin**, State University of
New York Stony Brook - Department of Art

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse
B

**♦ Preparing an Essay for Publication:
Strategies for Writing from and about the
Global Margins**

Workshop Leader: Douglas Gabriel, Seoul National
University; Megan A. Sullivan, University of Chicago;
Susan A. Snodgrass, ARTMargins; Sven Spieker

Chair Remarks

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

Rethinking Chinese Export Ceramics Now

Chair: Iris J. Moon, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

Discussant: Yao-Fen You

Chair Remarks

The display and interpretation of Chinese export ceramics at the Peabody Essex Museum, Karina Corrigan, Peabody Essex Museum

The history of scholarship on Chinese export ceramics, Ron Fuchs

A Feminist Revision of Chinoiserie, Iris J. Moon

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East

Rethinking the Central Asian Arts: New Perspectives on the Geography of Art

Chairs: Dilrabo Tosheva, Harvard University; David Roxburgh, Harvard University

Discussant: Jaimee Comstock-Skipp, University of Oxford, Faculty of Asian and Middle Eastern Studies; David Roxburgh, Harvard University

Chair Remarks

"Qarakhanid Architecture and the Islamization of Silk Road Sites: A Case Study of the Shah Fazil Mausoleum", Dilrabo Tosheva, Harvard University

Abdullah Khan's Library: "Quintessential" Bukharan Manuscript Production ca. 1560–1580, Jaimee Comstock-Skipp, University of Oxford, Faculty of Asian and Middle Eastern Studies

Architectural Innovation and Dynastic Patronage: The Shaybani Khan Madrasa in Samarkand, Yue Xie, Harvard University

Making Threads: Medieval Fibers from Islamic Central Asia, Iran, and India (c. 9th- mid-13th Centuries), Bermet Nishanova

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West

State Fairs and American Art

Chairs: Sara Christine Morris, Crocker Art Museum; Mary Savig, Smithsonian American Art Museum

Chair Remarks

Running in Alaska: The Visual Culture of Reindeer Fairs, 1915-17, Ivana Dizdar, University of Toronto

Grant Wood and the Iowa State Fair, Wanda Corn, Stanford University

Formalism in Informal Spaces: Wayne Thiebaud at the California State Fair, Mary Okin, Living New Deal

Fried Jell-O: Demonstration and Concession at the Fairgrounds, Sara Clugage, Dilettante Army

2:30 PM –4:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite

The role of conservation departments in university museums.

Chair: Irma Passeri, Yale University Art Gallery

2:45 PM –3:25 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #3: PLACE

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #3: PLACE, Michele Oka Doner

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science 2: Panel #3: PLACE, Natalie Waldburger, OCAD University

3:25 PM –4:30 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse G

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: CLOSING SPEAKER

The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: CLOSING SPEAKER: Crochet Coral Reef: Crafting Against Patriarchy in Science and Art, Margaret Wertheim, The Feminist Art Project

4:30 PM –6:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton Center

🌐 Abstract Art and Colonial Systems

Chairs: Julia Silverman, Harvard University; Max Boersma, Freie Universität Berlin

Universal and Vernacular, Abstract and Decorative: Alexandra Exter's Non-Figuration (late 1910s/early 1920s), Katia Denysova, University of Tübingen

The Abstract Letter: Debating Arabic Calligraphy in Modern Baghdad, Amin Alsaden, Independent Scholar

Exchanging "the Common Love of the Beautiful": Abstract Art and Minnesota Project (1954-1960), Ihnmi Jon, Maine College of Art and Design

Arch, Mound, Basket: Mission Abstraction and Indigenous Ecological Forms, Jessica Horton, University of Delaware

4:30 PM –6:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Trianon Ballroom

Art and Work

Chairs: Joshua Jenkins, The University of Edinburgh; Juan Cruz, Edinburgh College of Art; Craig Martin, Edinburgh College of Art, University of Edinburgh

Chair Remarks

Working with Coal: J.M.W. Turner's Landscapes of Sublime Labor, Caterina Franciosi, Yale University

Picturing Captivity: Ledger Drawings by Native Prisoners of War at Fort Marion, Ashley E Williams, Columbia University

The Graphic Dialectics of Jules Grandjouan's Les Esclaves Modernes, Asli Menevse, Bilkent University

Honest Labor: Chris Burden and the Bureaucratization of Artists in the University, Allison Myers, Cal Poly, SLO

4:30 PM –6:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Bryant Suite
Beyond Albers, Itten and Munsell: How are artists and educators re-approaching color theory and practice?

Chair: Amanda L. Lechner, Virginia Tech - School of Visual Art

Chair Remarks

Where Do Colors Come From?, Pamela Fraser, University of Vermont

Ecology of Color, Elise M. Richman, University of Puget Sound

Albers Variations, Terah Maher, Texas Tech University

The Digital Life of Color: Teaching Color in Film and New Media Art, Amy Beecher, Emerson College

4:30 PM –6:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Grand Ballroom West

Beyond Stories: Art Writing and Narrative

Chair: Brian T. Leahy, Montana State University Billings

Chair Remarks

Stories of/on art: Lucy Lippard's experiments in fiction, Beatrice Cloutier, Queen's University

Beyond emplotment: narrative between meta-history and material, Tilo Reifenstein, York St John University

"Reckless Storytelling": Art-Writing Lessons from Lorraine O'Grady's Newspaper Poems, Isabel Bird, Harvard University

On the Möbius strip...., Mira Dayal

4:30 PM –6:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Rendezvous Trianon

Collecting Her Thoughts: Women Art Collectors Across Time

Chairs: Toni Armstrong, Boston University; Danarenae Donato, Boston University; Ilaria Trafficante, Scuola Superiore Meridionale

Chair Remarks

Bourgeois Women as Collectors in Late Medieval Paris, Sarah Magleby, Kansas City Art Institute

Style with Substance: Black Women as Art Collectors and Activists in the U.S. Civil War Era, Rachel Hooper, Savannah College of Art and Design

Imagined Pasts: Betsy James Wyeth's Collections and their Afterlives, William Coleman, Brandywine Museum of Art

Craft and Fiber Art of the 1950s and 1960s in the collection of Helen Louise Allen, Maeve Hogan, University of Wisconsin–Madison

4:30 PM –6:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton North
Containers of a World to Come: Seeds and Global Contemporary Art

Chair: Svea Braeunert, University of Applied Sciences Potsdam

Chair Remarks

Beyond a World on Hold – Botanical Collections as Sites for Artistic Engagements with Colonial Histories and Seed Futures, Marleen Boschen

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New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy East

Decolonization and the Avant-Garde Art School: Rethinking the Bauhaus, VKhUTEMAS, Mezhyhirya and Beyond

Chair: Angelina Lucento, National Research University-Higher School of Economics

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Bauhaus Revisited: Uncovering its Enduring Influence and Potential for Sustainability, Christiane Wagner, University of São Paulo

Avant-garde and Pragmatism: Pedagogical Challenges at the Kyiv Art Institute, Lada Nakonechna, Universität Kassel

Postcolonial Pedagogies: The Development of the Faculty of Fine Arts, Baroda, **Khushmi Mehta**, The Graduate Center, CUNY

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New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gibson Suite
Decolonizing Garden Ecologies: the Visual and Material Cultures of Imperial Landscape

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Painting a pharmacopoeia, **Wesley Cornwell**, Columbia University

A Garden without Slavery? Photography and Black Histories in the Rio de Janeiro Botanical Garden, **Paula Victoria Kupfer**, University of Pittsburgh

Plants and Persons out of Place: Eco-Crip Theory and the Ugly Lawn, **Cynthia O'Neill**, University of Texas, Dallas

"All green plants swing": Sonic Relationality in the Improvised Garden, **Elizabeth Frickey**

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New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau East
Deliberately University Based: Marginalized Artists and the Growth of University Art Spaces

Chairs: **Elise Armani**; **Amy Kahng**, Stony Brook University; **Gabriella Shypula**

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Exploring and Finding the Limits in Silicon Valley: Lydia Modi Vitale at Santa Clara University's de Saisset Art Gallery, 1967-78, **Megan Hines**, Berklee College of Music

Claiming Space: University Art Galleries and Experiments in Chicana Graffiti, **Amy Crum**, University of California Los Angeles

Alternative Routes: Faith Ringgold's Strategies of Exhibition and Performance at Universities in the 1970s and 1980s, **Gabriella Shypula**

"Artists read theory as poetry": the Charles Gaines curriculum, **Ellen Y. Tani**, Rochester Institute of Technology

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New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Beekman
Descrutar el canon: Critical Perspectives on Artistic Modernism in the Andean Region

Chairs: **Anamária Garzón Mantilla**, University of Essex / Universidad San Francisco de Quito; **Gabriela Germana**, Pontificia Universidad Católica Del Peru

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Painting the Crude Reality: Art as Manifestation of Survivance in Gustavo Toaquiza Ugsha's Amazonian Series, **Diana Iturralde**, Rutgers University

Subversive Weaving: Olga de Amaral's 1970s Textiles and the History of Postwar Abstract Art, **Ana M. Franco**, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá

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Mestizo gourds, Indian gourds: the indigenist construction of popular art in Peru, **Mijail Mitrovic**, Pontificia Universidad Católica Del Peru

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New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse B

♦ Funding Your Arts Research and Practice: Strategic Proposal Writing for Grant and Fellowship Funding

Workshop Leader: **Holly Unruh**; **Hannah Jasper**, University of California, Berkeley

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New York Hilton Midtown – 3rd Floor – Petit Trianon
Global Mobility and Shifting Gazes in Visual Languages: From the 1930s to the Present

Chair: **Huixian Dong**

Chair Remarks

Avant-Garde Practices, Nationalistic Aims: Japanese Photomurals in the 1930s and 1940s, **Andrea Jung-An Liu**, UC Berkeley

Yu Hong's Female Gaze: Integrating Contemporary Life into Renaissance Canvas, **Huixian Dong**, Arizona State University

X-Ray Vision vs. Invisibility, **Noelle Mason**

Black Screen: Three Case Studies on the History of Obfuscation in Taiwanese Contemporary Art, **Pei-chun Hsieh**, Binghamton University

4:30 PM –6:00 PM SATURDAY, FEB. 15

New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Sutton South
⊕ Incomplete Presence: Authenticity and Accuracy in Immersive Spaces

Chair: **Richard Thompson**, New Jersey Institute of Technology

Unraveling the Uncanny Valley: The Role of Facial Recognition and Empathy in Immersive Media and 3D Animation, **Jaewook Lee**

Building Empathy with Authentic Movement: Mitigating the Uncanny Valley Phenomenon in Digital Humans, **Richard Thompson**, New Jersey Institute of Technology

Resituating Cultural Fragments: Interactive Media in Digital Archeology, **Augustus Wendell**, Duke University
- Dept of Art, Art Hist & Visual Studies

The Body as Remainder: What Barnett Newman Can Teach Us About Immersive Space, **Philip Vanderhyden**

Unveiling Marianne: Exploring Colonial Narratives in the Visual Programs of the Palais de la Porte Dorée, **Heidi Elizabeth Kraus**, Hope College

Hideo Date and Transpacific, Asian American Roots of Early Los Angeles Modernism, **Lily Allen**, University of California Riverside

Better Living in Eichlerville: California Modernism's Influence on Apple, **Homay King**, Bryn Mawr College

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New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Morgan Suite
Other Germans and German Others: Questions of Identity in Contemporary German Art

Chairs: **Ying Sze Pek**, Ruhr-University Bochum; **Thomas Love**, University of Missouri Columbia

Discussant: **Peter M. Chametzky**

Chair Remarks

6.25% Grey: On Adrian Piper's "Retirement from Being Black", **Thomas Love**, University of Missouri Columbia

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New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Madison Suite

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Discussant: **Tirza T. Latimer**

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Claude Cahun and Marcel Moore's Views and Visions: Toward an Anti-Identitarian Lesbian History, **Hannah Frydman**, Harvard University

The Erotics of Doubling in Germaine Krull's Les amies, **Marina Molarsky-Beck**, Yale University

Ithell Colquhoun: Imaging the Lesbian Shore for Surrealism, **Alyce A. Mahon**, University of Cambridge

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New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Nassau West
People's Histories of Material Culture in the United States

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Sonic Leash: Domestic Service Bells in Baltimore, Washington, D.C., and Northern Virginia, **Justyce Bennett**, University of Maryland

Rewriting Silver's Social Circuits: Jake's Souvenir Spoons, **Christine Garnier**, UC Santa Barbara

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Reimagining Black Cultural Narratives Through Design: A Study of Album Covers as Tools for Empowerment, **Omari Souza**

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New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Gramercy West

Sounding the Body: The Sung Voice in Contemporary Art

Chairs: **Anna Mecugni**, University of New Orleans; **Melissa Warak**, University of Texas at El Paso

Community as a Verb: Sonia Boyce at the 2022 Venice Biennale, **Claudia Di Tosto**

Singing the Nation-state: Music in Contemporary Art, **G Douglas Barrett**, Syracuse University

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Voice as Resistance to Abjection, **Sharon Jagger**, York St John University and **Helen Turner**, York St John University

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New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Murray Hill West

Reframing East and West: Colonialism, Modernism, Cultural Hybridity

Chair: **Homay King**, Bryn Mawr College

Chair Remarks

Royal Narratives Reframed: A Study of the Coromandel Lacquer in Augustus II the Strong's Porcelain Rooms at the Japanese Palace, **Zifeng Zhao**, University of Cambridge

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New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse A

🌐 ♦ Sustainability Impact: Constructing Practices for Exhibitions & Institutions

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New York Hilton Midtown – 2nd Floor – Regent

The Women of the Whitney Biennials: Artists In and Out of the Mainstream

Chair: Marsha McCoy, Southern Methodist University, Dallas, TX

Chair Remarks

In and Out of the Mainstream: Alice Forman and the Art of Domestic Space in Contemporary Times, **Marsha McCoy**, Southern Methodist University, Dallas, TX

The Emotional, The Revelatory, the Intuitive: The Women Artists of Lyrical Abstraction, 1971, **Eva Zak**, Adelphi University

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New York Hilton Midtown – Concourse – Concourse E

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Chair: Branislav Jakovljevic

Chair Remarks

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Burdette, Derek

Session Chair: From Made to Making: Ongoing Acts of Creation in Colonial Latin America

Burke, Rachel

Presenter: *A Lost "Mirror of Slavery": Black Geographies and the Antebellum American Landscape*

Burleigh, Paula

Presenter: *Lynn Hershman Leeson: a posthuman feminist counternarrative*

Burns, Emily

Presenter: *Centering Native American Belongings in Settler Paintings, c. 1900*

Burrill, Catie

Presenter: *Madness and the Unromantic Road: a Non-Linear Artist Talk*

Burroughs, Charles

Presenter: *Aeneas's Vision, Envisioned by Raphael*

Byrne, Ultan

Session Chair: Architecture in Repetition

C**Cacchione, Orianna**

Session Chair: Re - Opening the '85 New Wave Movement
 Presenter: *New Wave Materials: Shi Hui, Zhu Wei, Gu Wenda and Liang Shaoji's Fiber Art*

Cachia, Amanda

Presenter: *Smoke and Mirrors at the Zimmerli Art Museum*

Cadger, Emily

Presenter: *Political Promises and Pictures: How Victorian socialists used print ephemera to engage children in political action*

Cahn, Anna

Presenter: *Kinesthetic Transformation: The Dance Floor as Experimental Material*

Calvin, Katherine

Presenter: *New Money in the Early Modern Eastern Mediterranean*

Campbell, Andy

Presenter: *"Inverted women are often very good whistlers...": on Susan Siltón's 'voice'*

Campbell, Aurelia

Presenter: *Pit Tombs and Wooden Coffins: Elite Burials From a Regional Perspective*

Campbell, Brian

Session Chair: Expanding the Practice of Research: Transdisciplinarity in Art and Art History

Campbell, C. Jean

Session Chair: Sovereignty, Art, and its Histories

Canclini, Andrea

Presenter: *Identical, Unspectacular, Unremarkable. The Life and Death of the Political Model of the Italian Single-family House in the 1950s*

Cao, Maggie

Session Chair: Transhistorical Art History

Caplan, Allison

Presenter: *Making Relations: Nahua Precious Art as Material Socialization*

Carabatsos, Julia

Presenter: *Ocean Gems: Marine Botany and Imagination in Nineteenth-Century Seaweed Albums*

Carlson, Raymond

Presenter: *Michelangelo's Memoranda and the Domesticity of Art*

Carr, Enise

Presenter: *Black Abstraction, Social Media, and the Marketplace*

Carrejo, Jaime

Session Chair: Next Now: Studio Art Foundations

Carrillo Marquina, María

Presenter: *The Rhythms of Labor: Afro-Peruvian Instrumentations in the 18th-century Haciendas of Nazca, Peru*

Carter, Kristen

Session Chair: Methods of Engagement in Undergraduate Research

Carter, Warren

Session Discussant: The "Work" of Art in American Culture from the New Deal to Now

Cash, Sarah

Session Chair: On Titles
Presenter: *Sargent and Spain and the Roma People*

Casid, Jill

Session Chair: Decolonial Jewish Practice in Art and Visual Culture After Gaza

Cassibry, Kimberly

Presenter: *Still arguing for the Roman provinces, or how I learned to worry about victory monuments and love portable art*

Cassidy, Rex

Presenter: *Fabricators in the Foundry: A New Kind of Workshop*

Cassidy, Stephanie

Session Chair: The Art Students League: 150 Years of "American" Art

Castillo Cerf, Diana

Presenter: *Surviving the Earthquake: The Ceiling of the San Pedro Apóstol Temple in Andahuayllillas*

Caston, Eva

Presenter: *Cecilia Vicuña's Saborami and the Archiving of Waste*

Catanese, Paul

Session Chair: AI in Art: Practices, Processes, Doubts, and Revelations
Session Discussant: Artists' Roundtable hosted by Services to Artists Committee

Celik Alexander, Zeynep

Session Discussant: Art History's Graphic Intelligence

Cembalest, Robin

Session Workshop Leader: Instagram for Scholars, Curators, and Art Historians

Cempellin, Leda

Session Chair: Contemporary Artists Using AI: A Paradigm Shift for Art Historians
Session Discussant: Reaching Out: An Other-Focused Academic Approach to the Visual Arts

Centore, Kristina

Presenter: *Afro-Asian Intersections and British Art Education*

Chae, James

Presenter: *Vertical Hangul Typesetting in Practice and Recent Developments*

Chalaby, Cora

Presenter: *Free Wheeling: Women Artists and the American Print Renaissance*

Chamberlain, Colby

Session Chair: Institutional Fatigue in the Twenty-First Century

Chametzky, Peter

Session Discussant: Other Germans and German Others: Questions of Identity in Contemporary German Art
Presenter: *Manaf Halbouni's Mobile Monument, Mobilistan and Multi-Directional Migration*

Champion, Tori

Session Chair: The Art of Collaboration in the Long Eighteenth Century
Presenter: *Marie-Thérèse Reboul Vien and the Emergence of Neoclassicism*

Chan, Shing-Kwan

Session Chair: Ungovernable Bodies
Presenter: *Obsession, Opium, and the Otherworld: Tactical Morality as a Way of Depicting Male Same-Sex Desire in Nineteenth-Century Chinese Art*

Chang, Alexandra

Session Chair: 10 Years of ADVA Journal: Hindsight, Insights, Futures Thinking

Chang, Boyoung

Presenter: *Fashion, urbanity, and a new era: Han Youngsoo's street photography and the postwar South Korea*

Chang, Haely

Presenter: *Onna Shashinshi: Female Studio Photographers in Early Twentieth Century Japan*

Chang Baecker, Angie

Session Chair: The "Postsocialist Contemporary:" Passages in Modern-Contemporary Chinese Art
Presenter: *The Atomization of the Collective: Legacies of Mass Art Practice in the '85 New Wave*

Chapelle, Brianne

Presenter: *Art work, art labor: museum problematics and calls to decolonize the art world from inside the house*

Char, Evelyn

Presenter: *Echoes of the Sea: Mediating the Diasporized Memory of the Tanka in Ballad on the Shore*

Chari, Celia

Presenter: *Inside an early sixteenth-century Indian Artists' Workshop: Technical and Scientific Insights into the Dispersed Bhagavata Purana*

Charles-Rault, Jacqueline

Presenter: *Mata Aho – Weaving and Empowering Female Narratives*

Charlesworth, Ellen

Presenter: *Amorphous Clouds – Representations of 'Visual Similarity' in Digital Art History*

Charlton, Everlena Zoë

Session Discussant: Artists' Roundtable hosted by Services to Artists Committee

Chau, Tung

Presenter: *Virtual, By Other Means: Cao Fei's Nova*

Chavez, Louis

Presenter: *Sexuality, Race, and Performance in the 1990 film works of Jack Waters and Peter Cramer*

Chazan, Gabriel

Session Chair: Comparative Diaspora in Art History: Revisiting Diaspora and Visual Culture

Checa-Gismero, Paloma

Presenter: *Aesthetic Conversions in the US/Mexico Borderlands: Artist Collective COGNATE and the Work of Migration*

Chehtman, Solana

Session Chair: Artists' Legacy Stewardship: field-building efforts

Chen, Jiushuang

Presenter: *Reimagining Christianity in Chinese Modern and Contemporary Art: Modernity, Social Issues, and Artistic Practice*

Chen, Lena

Presenter: *Beyond Asian American Art: Private Practices & An Archive of Becoming*

Chen, Ting Han

Presenter: *Service Design for Digital Tours: The Rixing Type Foundry Case*

Chen, Yi-Fan

Presenter: *Exploring UX Design Trainees with Generative AI: A Pedagogical Perspective*

Chen, Ziru

Presenter: *The Tangible Turn: Reintroducing Materiality to Assert Creativity in AI Art*

Cheney, Liana

Session Chair: The visible and invisible in secular and religious art

Cheng, Hsin-Yun

Session Chair: Art in Action: Identity, Resistance, and Performance since the 1960s
Presenter: *The Subject of Exile: Tehching Hsieh's One-Year Performances*

Chernavvsky Sequeira, Catalina

Presenter: *Reimagining the Social Condition in Brazilian Video Art*

Cho, Lily

Presenter: *Roundtable Participant Lily Cho*

Choh, Paulina

Presenter: *Alternative Albums of Asian America: Group Photographs Within the Archive*

Choi, Chanhee

Session Chair: Art History and the Apocalypse
Session Chair: Poetic Explorations of Cultural Diversity: A Study of Artistic Narratives and Perspectives within Western Frameworks

Choi, Ina

Presenter: *Reevaluating Theresa Hak Kyung Cha's Abstract Ephemerality as Radical Political Statement*

Choi, Sooran

Presenter: *From Phenomenon to Trace: Anarcho-Daoism in Korean Art Activism*

Chorpening, Kelly

Presenter: *Not art, not an essay: the role of annotated drawings in transdisciplinary research*

Chou, Wenshing

Presenter: *Roundtable Participant Wenshing Chou*

Christensen, Ellen

Presenter: *Advancing Design Education through Hybridity and Communication*

Chun, Claire

Session Chair: Aberrations in Beauty
Presenter: *Glass Skin: Luminosity, Repair, and Transpacific Ecologies of Beauty and War*

Chun, Minji

Presenter: *From Margins to Mainstream: Listen to the City's Community Engagement and Urban Advocacy*

Chung, Yeon Shim

Presenter: *Constructing the 'Avant-Garde' in Korean Art and Writings (1961-1971)*

Chusid, Miriam

Presenter: *Transmitting Tradition: The Premodern Preservation of the Takao Mandara*

Cifarelli, Megan

Presenter: *"I carried off ... anything desirable in his palace:" Implications of gender-based violence in Assyrian Palace Reliefs*

Clark, Alexis

Presenter: *De-Hierarchising Impressionism Studies via UK/US Collaborations*

Clayson, Hollis

Session Chair: On Other Media in Nineteenth-Century French Art

Clericuzio, Peter

Presenter: *FIAT, International Expositions, and the Stile Liberty: Design for a New Century*

Cloutier, Beatrice

Presenter: *Stories of/on art: Lucy Lippard's experiments in fiction*

Clugage, Sara

Presenter: *Fried Jell-O: Demonstration and Concession at the Fairgrounds*

Clutter, Tyrus

Session Discussant: The Students and Emerging Professionals Committee's (SEPC) Guide To All Things CAA

Codell, Julie

Session Chair: Trajectory in Art: Toward a Horizontal Art History of Styles

Coen, Paolo

Presenter: *Three generations of technical knowledge and skills compared: the Bruni Artistic Foundry in Rome (c. 1880-1982)*

Colburn, Cynthia

Presenter: *Teaching Strategies for Addressing Gender Violence in Ancient Greek Art*

Cole, Lori

Presenter: *Modernist Magazines and Museum Collections*

Coleman, Fletcher

Presenter: *Solace in Painting: Questioning "Conflict Art" through the Life and Work of Keisho Okayama*

Coleman, William

Presenter: *Imagined Pasts: Betsy James Wyeth's Collections and their Afterlives*

Collins, Barbara

Presenter: *Researcher Dr. Barbara Collins*https://caa.confex.com/caa/2025/generalcomplete/extra/index.cgi?username=23071&EntryType=Paper&password=*cookie

Colombari, Dr. Lucia

Session Chair: Spectacles of Nationhood: World's Fairs and Italian Identity Formation
Presenter: *Architectures of Becoming: Italy's Democratic Narrative at Expo 58*

Colwell, Tess

Presenter: *Panelist - Arts Librarian for Research Services*

Comstock, Olivia

Session Chair: Hands-On: Critical Connections Between Craft and Pedagogy

Comstock-Skipp, Jaimee

Session Discussant: Rethinking the Central Asian Arts: New Perspectives on the Geography of Art
Presenter: *Abdullah Khan's Library: "Quintessential" Bukharan Manuscript Production ca. 1560-1580*

Conboy, Matthew

Session Chair: Vantage Point: Artist Panel 1

Conlan, Anna

Presenter: *A Case Study of a Rediscovered Artist: Benjamin Wigfall, a University, a Community, and a Legacy*

Contractor, Tara

Presenter: *King Cophetua and the Stolen Gold: Edward Burne-Jones's Reflections on Looting*

Contreras Cerda, Joselyne

Session Chair: Curatorial Practices in Latin America: Challenges and Discourses in the Age of Global Neoliberalism
Presenter: *Curatorial Practices and the Sensitive Turn: How to Challenge the Neoliberal Machine in Latin America*

Cook, Lindsay

Presenter: *Notre-Dame Through the Eyes of Jean de Jandun*
Presenter: *Theories and Practices of Conservation in Paris*

Cook, Nicole

Presenter: *Darkness, Dirt, and Excess: Picturing Nightwalkers in 17th-century Dutch Art*

Cooke John, Nina

Presenter: *Erasure, Renewal and the Monumental Everyday*

Coonin, Arnold Victor

Session Chair: New Technologies and the Re-visualization of Italian Renaissance Art

Cooper, Cecilio M

Presenter: *Black Transmasculinity +*

Cordero, Karen

Presenter: *Deborah Castillo: Disfiguring and Reconfiguring the Verbal and Corporeal Language of Patriarchy*

Corey, Pamela

Presenter: *Theory from Historiography: TK Sabapathy's Writings on Southeast Asian Art*

Corfield, Christina

Presenter: *Crafting Media History from the Mundane*

Corn, Wanda

Presenter: *Grant Wood and the Iowa State Fair*

Cornejo, Kency

Presenter: *Colonial Racial Capitalism*

Cornwell, Wesley

Presenter: *Painting a pharmacopoeia*

Corrigan, Karina

Presenter: *The display and interpretation of Chinese export ceramics at the Peabody Essex Museum*

Cosmo, Laurie

Presenter: *Accommodating New Expressions and an Increasing Public Commitment to Art: The Emergence of Museums of Modern Art in the Netherlands*

Costello, Eileen

Session Chair: Los Angeles during World War II: Art at the Margins

Courtney, Chloë

Session Chair: Constructions of Indigeneity in Postwar Art of the Americas
Presenter: *Stitching together: Extended possibilities of collectivity in Chilean Arpilleras*

Couto, Ashley

Presenter: *The Slow Productivity of Crip Advocacy in the Arts & Media*

Cozzens, Andrew

Presenter: *Research as the Basic Building Block to a Successful BFA Thesis*

Cozzolino, Robert

Session Chair: Is there anybody out there? UFOs, UAPs, and American Art
Presenter: *Is there anybody out there? UFOs, UAPs, and American Art*

Cramer, Lauren

Session Chair: META+PHYSICS OF BLACK ARTMAKING

Crasnow, Sascha

Presenter: *What Is Diaspora in Palestine?*

Crawford, Nicole

Presenter: *Reimagining Ethnographic Objects: Moving Beyond Repatriation in Decolonizing Museums*

Crespo Claudio, Yazmín

Presenter: *en el radar: ground-based observations in Arcibo, Puerto Rico.*

Croft, Kyle

Presenter: *Gran Fury: Activism, Art and Design*

Cronan, Todd

Presenter: *How Many Ways Can You Exploit a Maid*

Crostini, Barbara

Session Chair: Crossing Borders: Bringing Mediterranean Studies to a Wider Audience

Crough, Olivia

Session Chair: Race and the Shape of Revolutionary Art: Between Avant-Garde and Early Soviet Visual Cultures
Session Discussant: Race and the Shape of Revolutionary Art: Between Avant-Garde and Early Soviet Visual Cultures

Crum, Amy

Presenter: *Claiming Space: University Art Galleries and Experiments in Chicanax Graffiti*

Crum, Lilian

Presenter: *Redefining Design Education for Generation Z: From Anxiety to Empowerment*

Cruz, Juan

Session Chair: Art and Work

Cunnally, John

Session Chair: In Memoriam Trina Robbins: New Research in the History of Women Cartoonists

D**Dahlke, Ash**

Presenter: *The Case For Fostering Student Collaboration*

Dash Moore, Deborah

Presenter: *Politics, Aesthetics, and the Art Students League in Helen Levitt's Turn to Color Photography*

Dashevski, Liliya

Presenter: *Didactic Tools or Harbingers of Chaos: Konstantin Gribanov's "Geographical Cards of Russia."*

Day, Phoebe

Presenter: *'Under the Sign of Saturn'? Gisèle Freund's Photographs of Walter Benjamin at the Bibliothèque nationale Reconsidered*

Dayal, Mira

Presenter: *On the Möbius strip...*

de Baca, Miguel

Session Discussant: Who's Afraid of Western Art History? : Pedagogy, Research and Impact of Western Art History in Korea

De Corte, Hannah

Presenter: *Pretend it's a Painting! Meaning in Materiality and the Reading of Paintings as Paintings*

De Ferrari, Guillermina

Session Chair: Civic Gestures in Contemporary Cuban Art
Presenter: *Reynier Leyva Novo's Minor Gestures*

De Leo, Andrés

Presenter: *Reforming the Cusco Bishopric: Manuel de Mollinedo y Angulo's Artistic Patronage (1675-1700)*

De Staebler, Peter

Session Chair: Still Defining Roman Art

De Turk, Sabrina

Session Discussant: Art History and the Apocalypse
Presenter: *Palestine in Venice: Representation and Dissent*

de Villemejjane, Anne

Presenter: *Origins: The Foundry as Inspiration*

de Vos Devine, Katherine

Session Discussant: Navigating the changing terrain of fair use in the digital world

DeLand, Lauren

Presenter: *Blood, Lies, and Videotape: AIDS Panic and the Transformation of Ron Athey*

Demerdash, Nancy

Session Chair: Revivalism, Labor, and Discourses on Craft in Indigenous Arts of Southwest Asia and North Africa: Then and Now

Dempsey, Anna

Session Chair: Environmental Culture, Urban Artscapes and the Urbanocene

Presenter: *New Orleans' Public Art Interventions on the Environment*

Denson, Shane

Session Discussant: Automation, Authorship, and Authenticity: What does Art Have to Say about AI?

Presenter: *What, to a Computer, is an Image?*

Denysova, Katia

Presenter: *Universal and Vernacular, Abstract and Decorative: Alexandra Exter's Non-Figuration (late 1910s/early 1920s)*

Derbez, Eréndira

Presenter: *Inés Amor and the Early Years of the Galería de Arte Mexicano*

Deschene, Wendy

Presenter: *Reclamation: The Space Between*

Dessauvage, Maur

Session Chair: Reframing Landscape: 50 Years after New Topographics

Dewey Hagborg, Heather

Presenter: *The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #1: PEOPLE*

Di Tosto, Claudia

Presenter: *Community as a Verb: Sonia Boyce at the 2022 Venice Biennale*

Diack, Heather

Presenter: *Back to the Camera: Borders of the Contemporary in Lens-Based Art from the late 1990s*

DiCindio, Carissa

Presenter: *Exploring Cultural Ecosystems through Embodied Forms of Research*

Dierickx, Sofie

Presenter: *Collaboration in wood identification: the interdisciplinary work of writing of art histories and conservation methodologies for Congolese heritage objects in Belgian museums.*

Diez Fischer, Agustin

Presenter: *Temporalities in Conflict: Leopoldo Maler's Archive and the Reframing of British Art History*

DiMarco, Christa

Presenter: *Vincent van Gogh, Jules Michelet, and Working-Class Women*

Ding, Yuhua

Session Chair: The Form of Immortality: Painting and Calligraphy in Fifteenth- to Eighteenth-Century China

Presenter: *Female Beauty, Wine, and Antiquarianism: Temporal Transformation of the Immortal Magu*

Dingwall, Christopher

Presenter: *The Labors of Eugene Winslow: Racial Politics in the Midcentury Design Industry*

Dinkins, Stephanie

Presenter: *Curiosity*

Presenter: *The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #1: PEOPLE*

Ditzig, Kathleen

Session Chair: Ecologies of Islands in Contemporary Art: From Colonial Imaginaries to International Flows
Presenter: *Island Art Ecologies: Singapore's Freeport from Duty-Free Art to Blockchain Data*

Dizdar, Ivana

Presenter: *Running in Alaska: The Visual Culture of Reindeer Fairs, 1915-17*

Dlugosz-Acton, Stefanie

Presenter: *Unlearning Curating and Learning Faculty Collaboration*

Donahey, Kelly

Session Chair: Reconstructing the Electronic Superhighway: Radical Media Art and Techno-Community at the Margins of the Global Village

Donato, Danarenae

Session Chair: Collecting Her Thoughts: Women Art Collectors Across Time

Doner, Michele Oka

Presenter: *The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #3: PLACE*

Dong, Huixian

Session Chair: Global Mobility and Shifting Gazes in Visual Languages: From the 1930s to the Present
Presenter: *Yu Hong's Female Gaze: Integrating Contemporary Life into Renaissance Canvas*

Doran, Kerry

Presenter: *Hippie Entrepreneur Indian Chief: Stewart Brand, the Whole Earth Catalog, and Indigeneity*

Dorsey, Kristen

Presenter: *Future is Land: Visual Indigenous Critiques of Settler Capitalism*

Dosch, Mya

Session Chair: Rethinking the Theory and Methods Art History Course
Presenter: *Collections and Collaborations: Studio Art and Art History Students in Dialog with the work of the Royal Chicano Air Force (RCAF)*

Dospel Williams, Elizabeth

Presenter: *Roundtable Participant; The Art Bulletin Editorial Board*

Doss, Erika

Presenter: *John McCracken's Remote Viewing: Minimalism and Advanced Beings*

Douglas, Anna

Presenter: *If Not Now, When? Generations of Women in Sculpture in Britain, 1960-2022*

Douglas, Susan

Session Discussant: Navigating the changing terrain of fair use in the digital world

Drascek, Michele

Presenter: *Unveiling the Anna Mahler Photographic Archive*

Driscoll, Megan

Presenter: *Networked Bodies: Identity and the Internet in Shu Lea Cheang's Brandon*

Dritz, Jesse

Presenter: *Reframing Appalachia: Foxfire's Rural Pedagogy*

Duarte-Riascos, Jeronimo

Presenter: *To Cheat Language: Feminist Critique Through Play in Magali Lara's Series "Sielo"*

Duffew, Hannah

Session Chair: Design and Disability: Changing Perspectives and Opportunities

Duffey, Ashley

Presenter: *To Whom Do We Belong? Photography and Asian Adoptees in Diaspora*

Duganne, Erina

Session Discussant: Camera-derie: Collaborative, Communal, and Collective Practices in Photography

Dukiewicz, Magdalena

Presenter: *The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #1: PEOPLE*

Duncan, Sumitra

Session Workshop Leader: Digital Art History and the Web: An Introduction to Web Archive Data Analysis

Dunn, Ashley

Presenter: *Printmaking at the Forefront in Nineteenth-Century France*

E**Eagles, Lane**

Presenter: *Neo-Renaissance Style: Early Modern Dress Adaptation in 19th Century Fashion*

Ebanoidze, Natia

Presenter: *Dissolving Boundaries: The Creative Agency of the 'Double Brain'*

Eckhardt, Sarah

Presenter: *Round Table Participant*

Edelman, Aliza

Session Chair: Reading Bodies of Information: Inventive Feminist Approaches to Women Artists in the Archive

Ekpo, Patricia

Presenter: *Weathering: Beverly Buchanan's Environmental Sculpture and Black Bodily Abstraction*

Ekserdjian, Alexander

Session Chair: Anxieties of Divine Representation in the Pre-Modern World
Presenter: *The Art of Adaptation: Making Roman Gods in the Late Republic*

El Hayek, Chantal

Presenter: *The Place de l'Étoile in Beirut and the Crafting of Colonial Neoclassicism*

Elgammal, Ahmed

Presenter: *Art in the Age of AI: Gains, Losses, and Illusions*

Ellenbogen, Josh

Presenter: *Identity and Self-Representation in the East Harlem Community Resource Center's Photo Workshop*

Ellis, Josephine

Presenter: *Conservation in/as Decay: On the Perverse Continuity of Daniel Spoerri's Tableau-pièges*

Elston, Gale

Session Chair: Law in Art and Art in Law: Charting a New Course for Society

Elston, Miranda

Presenter: *Cartographic Traces of Privateers: The Illusive Archive of Drake's Caribbean Raids and Sea Networks*

Emmanuel, Kaitlin

Presenter: *Revisiting 'ur': Tamil Geographies in the Settler Colony through the Work of Joshua Vettivelu*

Emser, Nicole

Session Chair: Challenges of Teaching: What, Why, How, and Solutions for Right Now
 Session Chair: Highlights in Undergraduate Art & Design Research (Session 1)
 Session Chair: Highlights in Undergraduate Art & Design Research (Session 2)
 Session Chair: Navigating the changing terrain of fair use in the digital world

Enos, James A

Presenter: *How to Measure / Cutting Short*

Enriquez, Nicolyna

Presenter: *From Harbor to Sacred Space: Coastal Churches and Topography on the Southern Coast of Crete*

Eppley, Charles

Presenter: *Beating: Sound Installation as Queer Methodology*

Epps, Philomena

Presenter: *Like a Motion Picture, Like a Living Dance: Persona and Performativity in Hannah Wilke's 'So Help Me Hannah' (1978-85)*

Epstein, Danya

Presenter: *Baked in the Sun and Hiding in Plain Sight: Native American Public Art in Phoenix*

Epstein, Sonia

Session Chair: The Medical Gaze: Art, Corporeality, and Technology

Erdmann, Mark

Session Chair: A War for Our Age: Genpei War Images and Social Movements
 Presenter: *No Country for Young Men: Heike Paintings and Warrior Identity in Post-Warring States Japan*

Eremin, Katherine

Presenter: *Seeing Color in History through material science: Changing palettes in Indian manuscripts*

Ernest, Marcella

Session Chair: Affective Encounters & Sonic Possibilities for "Imagining Otherwise"
 Presenter: *Remixing the Archive*

Evans, Eliza

Presenter: *A couple bad ideas for a survivable future*

Ezor, Dani

Session Chair: Unboxing the Long Eighteenth Century

F**Fabijanska, Monika**

Session Chair: Language and Text in Feminist Art Part II: Latin America and the Caribbean, Latinx diasporas

Fachechi, Grazia Maria

Presenter: *From Urbino to the Vatican City and back: the Library of Federico da Montefeltro, as it was, where it was.*

Fader, Sean

Presenter: *Insufficient Memory*

Fahandej, Rashin

Presenter: *Embodied Resistance: Bodily Autonomy in Iran Augmented by Art and Technology*

Fair, Elizabeth

Presenter: *The View From the Levee: Transpacific Material Culture of Chinese American Temples*

Familian, David

Presenter: *Complexity*

Fanning, Colin

Session Chair: Creativity, Consumption, and Spectacle: Interrogating "Collectible" Design

Farmer, Sophia

Presenter: *Conserving and Analyzing Canned Waste: Piero Manzoni's Merda d'artista (1961)*

Fathi, Samira

Session Chair: Everyday and the Expression of Modernity: 19th-Century Architecture and Urbanism in the Islamic World
 Presenter: *Tracing A Type: Isfahan's Legacy and Early Qajar Palace Architecture*

Fay, Brendan

Session Chair: Learning and Unlearning Photography

Federici, Valeria

Presenter: *When social became digital: New media art and politics in Italy in the 1980s and 1990s.*

Fehnel, Salena

Presenter: *The Indigo Project: A Social Study in Compassion, Collaboration, and Community*

Feiss, Ellen

Presenter: *Institutional Critique in illiberal times*

Felleman, Susan

Session Chair: "The slippery nature of the self": Gender, Masquerade, Counterfactual History, and Jewish Women Artists

Fernandez, Maria

Session Discussant: Cyberfeminist Legacies in New Media Art
 Session Discussant: Enchantments, Transmissions, Infections: A Poetics of Knowledge by Latin American Women Artists

Fernandez Pello, Maria

Presenter: *To imagine a microscopic worm crawling through the pores of your arm*

Fernandez-Barkan, Davida

Presenter: *Indigenist Muralism from Santa Fe to Aztlán*

Ferrara, Lidia

Presenter: *"Strange Migrations": Bodies and Media in Transformation in Joan Jonas's Sweeney Astray (1994)*

Ferrari, Francesca

Session Discussant: Figuring the Individual/Figuring the Group: Transnational Exchanges in Interwar Art

Ferrari, Roberto

Presenter: *Out of the Shadows: Re-envisioning Simeon Solomon*

Ferreira, Marisa

Presenter: *Waste Aesthetics in the Urbanocene. On Materiality, Otherness and Spatial Justice.*

Ferrer, Elizabeth

Presenter: *Praxis as Form*

Field, Jennifer

Session Chair: Moving Out: David Smith & The Outdoor Migration of Sculpture

Field, Parker

Presenter: *Hans Burkhardt qua Arshile Gorky in Los Angeles Abstraction*

Fineberg, Jonathan

Session Chair: Can You Teach Creativity? The Role of the Arts Across Disciplines.

Fisher, Michelle

Session Discussant: Hands-On: Critical Connections Between Craft and Pedagogy

Fisher, Susan

Session Chair: Heavy Metal: The Artist and the Foundry

Flaherty, Fran

Session Workshop Leader: Unraveling Accessibility: Deaf and Disability Arts"

Flatley, Jonathan

Presenter: *From the Black Square to the Black Belt Thesis: On the Blackness of Black in Malevich's Painting*

Flavelle, Genevieve

Session Chair: Once Upon a Queer Time: Speculative Histories in the Work of 2SLGBTQ+ Artists

Fleming, Bridget

Presenter: *A Letter From We to You: The Epistolary Community in Sharon Hayes' In My Little Corner of the World, Anyone Would Love You (2016)*

Florence, Kathryn

Presenter: *Land of Enchantment: Reframing Agency of Woody Crumbo's Subjects*

Flores, Tatiana

Session Discussant: Activating "X as Intersection: Writing on Latinx Art"
Presenter: *Roundtable Participant Tatiana Flores*

Foa, Michelle

Session Chair: What Lies Ahead for Later Nineteenth-Century French Art

Fondevilla, Herb

Presenter: *Fragile Spaces: Challenges to Organizing Arts-based Approaches to Dementia*

Fontana, Jeffrey

Presenter: *George B. Bridgman, Rodin, Quick Poses and the Modernization of American Life Drawing*

Foran, Colleen

Presenter: *Bringing the Gown to Town: Chale Wote Street Art Festival in Ga Mashie, Accra, Ghana*

Forcier, Kaitlin

Presenter: *A Counterfeit Infinity: Bay Area Video Art and the Digital Aesthetic*

Forsythe, Hannah

Presenter: *An Invisible Pain: Migraines, Medical Imaging, and the Artistic Challenge to the Medical Gaze*

Fortuna, James

Presenter: *Fascism, Italian-Americans, and the 1939 New York World's Fair*

Foster, Artie

Presenter: *Who's Afraid of Frank Bowling? Painting For and Against Anti-colonialism*

Foster, Leslie

Presenter: *Call and Response: In Which I Pose Institutional Questions Without Answers*

Foutch, Ellery

Presenter: *Recasting History: The 1893 Columbian Liberty Bell and Peace Plow*

Fowler, Caroline

Session Chair: A Roundtable on American Art
Session Chair: Sovereignty, Art, and its Histories
Presenter: *A Roundtable on American Art*

Franciosi, Caterina

Presenter: *Working with Coal: J.M.W. Turner's Landscapes of Sublime Labor*

Francis, Jacqueline

Session Chair: Critical Race Art History Roundtable: Doing the Work

Franco, Ana

Session Discussant: ISLAA-ALAA Encuentro for Latin American and Latinx Art at CAA
Presenter: *Subversive Weaving: Olga de Amaral's 1970s Textiles and the History of Postwar Abstract Art*

Franco, Josh

Presenter: *Sacred Futurities*

Franks, Sara

Presenter: *Synthesizing ideas and research: The Library as integral to the subject and the research*

Frantz, Taline

Presenter: *Co-Envisioning Adaptive Ecologies: Collaborative Workshops with Crip Designers for Future Climate Architecture*

Fraser, Karen

Session Chair: Women and the Global Historiography of Photography, 1840-1940

Fraser, Pamela

Presenter: *Where Do Colors Come From?*

Freese, Lauren

Session Workshop Leader: A Pedagogy Workshop: Building Your Teaching Toolkit – Collaborative Teaching and Learning

Frelin, Adam

Presenter: *De-Designing Public Art*

Frequin, Sanne

Presenter: *Shifting Shadows: Using Virtual Reality to revive Dynamic Lighting Conditions for Gilded Panel Paintings*

Fricke, Suzanne

Session Chair: Future Imaginaries: Indigenous Art, Fashion, Technology
Presenter: *Riff, Ground, Dream: New Ideas in Indigenous Futurisms*

Frickey, Elizabeth

Presenter: *"All green plants swing": Sonic Relationality in the Improvised Garden*

Fritzsich, Constanze

Session Chair: Bodies in Action, East and West
Presenter: *De-mythologization of the ideal collective body*

Frumess, Richard

Presenter: *Round Table Participant*

Frydman, Hannah

Presenter: *Claude Cahun and Marcel Moore's Views and Visions: Toward an Anti-Identitarian Lesbian History*

Fu, Cissie

Session Chair: Networks, Solidarities and Intersections: Representations of Black, African and Asian Historical and Contemporary Space

Fu, Jessica

Presenter: *Ephemeral Tattoo - Site-specific mixed reality digital art projects for heritage sites*

Fuchs, Ron

Presenter: *The history of scholarship on Chinese export ceramics*

Fung, Adam

Presenter: *Collaboration as an Entrepreneurial and Intellectual approach to art making*

Furioso, Dante

Presenter: *The Stones of Havana: Producing Neoclassical Architecture in a 19th c. Slave Society*

Furtado, Nicole

Session Chair: Current Research in Pacific Visual Studies
Presenter: *Hawaiian Futurisms: Mixed-Media Mediums as Generating Anti-Colonial Art*

G**Gabbard, Delana**

Session Chair: Design Education Futures

Gabriel, Douglas

Session Workshop Leader: Preparing an Essay for Publication: Strategies for Writing from and about the Global Margins

Gagliardi, Susan

Session Chair: Collaboration as Art Historical Practice

Gaifman, Milette

Presenter: *The Diagram of Shapes and Modern Conceptions of Painted Pottery*

Gain, Justine

Presenter: *Building "one of the most solid glories of French art": the oeuvre of Barye in museums, a transatlantic perspective*

Gajowy, Aleksandra

Presenter: *Unearthing the Polish Lesbian: Speculative Lesbian Histories in Liliana Zeic's "Sourcebook"*

Gal, Nissim

Presenter: *Decolonizing Art History in Israel-Palestine*

Galliera, Izabel

Session Chair: Pedagogy as Art: Possibilities and Constraints in Institutional Transformation
Presenter: *Co-Producing Cultural Resistance in Orbán's Hungary: The Art Institutional Boycott of Tranzit.hu and Off-Biennale*

Galvan, Margaret

Presenter: *Trina Robbins' Decades-Long Commitment to LGBTQ+ Comics and Lives*

Ganci, Aaron

Presenter: *Participatory Design for Patients with Dementia and Their Caregivers*

Gangwisch, Jls

Presenter: *harmon_proc post-mortem: selling art on the play store*

Gao, Ruiying

Presenter: *Art for Medical Knowledge? Illustrated Materia Medica Books in Late Ming China*

Garay, Madison

Presenter: *Visual Hauntologies on Albuquerque's Route 66: Place-Images after the Mother Road*

Garber, Laurel

Presenter: *Printmaking at the Forefront in Nineteenth-Century France*

Garcia, Robin

Presenter: *Toma Cultural; Radio Verdura and the Power of Collective Creativity*

Garcia Cepeda, Rene

Session Chair: Walled Gardens and Wild Artists

García-Rodríguez, Andrea

Presenter: *Threads of Identity: Textiles in the Guatemalan Traveling Avant-garde*

Garfield, Rachel

Presenter: *Jewishness under erasure: Persona work in the UK*

Garnier, Christine

Presenter: *Rewriting Silver's Social Circuits: Jake's Souvenir Spoons*

Garzon, Sara

Presenter: *1992: Latin American Art and the New Global Order*

Garzón Mantilla, Anamaría

Session Chair: Descentrar el canon: Critical Perspectives on Artistic Modernism in the Andean Region
Presenter: *Decoloniality is a Metaphor: Exhibitions of Ecuadorian Modern Art*

Gasparavicius, Gediminas

Session Chair: Who's Afraid of Mimicry? Contemporary Art and New Culture Wars

Gavaler, Chris

Presenter: *Thoroughly Meta: Zoe Thorogood and the Paradoxes of Metafictional Graphic Memoir*

Gayer, Tanya

Session Chair: How do you throw a brick through the window...: Expanding Publics and Embodiments

Geiger, Melissa

Session Discussant: Contemporary Artists Using AI: A Paradigm Shift for Art Historians
Session Chair: Reaching Out: An Other-Focused Academic Approach to the Visual Arts

Gencer, Yasemin

Presenter: *Visibility, Visuality, and Branding in Early Twentieth-Century Ottoman Turkish Periodicals*

Gerlieb, Anne-Kathrin

Session Affiliated Society Chair: Exploring Methodological Approaches in Art Market Studies - TIAMSA Business meeting

Germana, Gabriela

Session Chair: Descentrar el canon: Critical Perspectives on Artistic Modernism in the Andean Region
Presenter: *Language to express issues on gender violence and racial discrimination: The work of four Andean and Amazonian contemporary women artists*

Germann, Jennifer

Session Chair: Unboxing the Long Eighteenth Century
Presenter: *Marie-Guillemine Benoist (1768-1826): A Neoclassicism of Her Own*

Gerry, Kathryn

Session Chair: Crossing Borders: Bringing Mediterranean Studies to a Wider Audience
Presenter: *Crossing Borders: A Western Medievalist's Viewpoint on Fitting France and Spain into the Mediterranean World*

Gholamrezaei, Niloofar

Presenter: *Emergent Phenomena in AI and its Implications in Art Pedagogy*

Ghosh, Ujaan

Presenter: *(Non) Resident Alien: Global Visual Cultures and the Biography of a Hindu God in Nineteenth-Century Britain and America*

Gibson, Kailyn

Session Workshop Leader: Toward an Inclusive Framework: (Re)Building Black Art Histories

Gibson, Stephanie

Session Chair: Subversive Bodies: Womyn Performing Blackness in the Caribbean and Caribbean Diaspora

Gieben-Gamal, Emma

Session Chair: Design and Disability: Changing Perspectives and Opportunities

Giffin, Erin

Presenter: *Architecture as Sculpture: Replicas of the Santa Casa*

Gilbert, Robby

Presenter: *Researcher*

Gilbert, Zanna

Session Chair: Transgresoras: Mail Art and Messages

Giritlian, Katie

Presenter: *Rehearsing Views: Pedagogical Toolkits for Visual Literacy*

Gisolfi, Diana

Session Chair: Design and Decoration of Libraries

Giunta, Andrea

Presenter: *1975: Women Artists in Latin America Between Recognition and Revolution*

Gleeson, Maura

Presenter: *La Créatrice in Flux: Women's Artmaking and Ambition in Revolutionary France*

Gluzman, Georgina

Presenter: *Against the Extractivist Researcher: Feminist and Queer Readings from Latin America*

Godfrey, DeWitt

Session Chair: What Is Public Art For?

Goerlitz, Amelia

Session Discussant: A Roundtable on American Art

Gold, Suzanne

Session Workshop Leader: Forms of Friendship: An Educator's How-To For a Socially Engaged Classroom

Gomez, Joshua

Presenter: *Extractive Enterprises: The Spectral Spectacles of Tlachiquero Subjectivity in Mexican Photography*

Gomez, Ximena

Session Chair: From Made to Making: Ongoing Acts of Creation in Colonial Latin America

Gonnen, Noam

Presenter: *Darker than A Nocturne: Whistler's Aesthetics of Pollution*

Gonzalez, Ella

Presenter: *Teaching Strategies for Addressing Gender Violence in Ancient Greek Art*

Gonzalez Godino, Cecilia

Presenter: *Trade Windings: De-Lineating the American Tropics*

Goodman, Emily

Session Workshop Leader: Bad advice for teachers

Gorant, Charlotte

Session Chair: Anxieties of Divine Representation in the Pre-Modern World

Gordo Peláez, Luis

Session Chair: Open Session for Emerging Scholars

Gordon, Erin

Session Chair: Reconstructing the Electronic Superhighway: Radical Media Art and Techno-Community at the Margins of the Global Village

Gorgulho, Guilherme

Presenter: *Zhang Daqian in South America: Misunderstandings of an Artistic Exchange*

Gornik, April

Presenter: *The World Within Me*

Gorodenzik, Danielle

Presenter: *Exhibition-Making: Feminist Art in Israel from the 70s to the 90s*

Gotlieb, Marc

Presenter: *Enacted biography and the melancholy of 'last paintings' from the Romantic age to the Fin-de-siècle*

Goussen Robleto, Lesdi

Presenter: *MESÓTICA II: Toward the Regeneration of Contemporary Art in Central America*

Gozo Richeson, Caitlin

Presenter: *Conservation Lost and Found: Preservation Strategies for the Art of Trash*

Graff, Elissa

Session Chair: Building Undergraduate Research Skills in a Subject-Led Curriculum

Graff Ballone, Missy

Presenter: *Roundtable Discussion Participant: OUCH! THE ARTIST'S BODY AND HOW TO CARE FOR IT LONG TERM*

Grasso, Linda Maria

Presenter: *Georgia O'Keeffe's Boarding House and What It Reveals*

Gray, Stephanie

Presenter: *Preserving 'La Villita': NYA Arts & Craft Training as Labor Opportunity for San Antonio's Mexican-American Youth*

Greendeer, Kendra

Presenter: *An Introduction to Rematriation*

Greenshaw, Claire

Presenter: *Drawing is a Residue of Time; tracing a future in the Pictures Collection*

Greenwald, Diana

Presenter: *Collaboration in Boston: The Legacy of Allan Rohan Crite*

Greet, Michele

Presenter: *Cultural Convergence in Enrique Tábara's Precolombinismo*

Grego March, Claudia

Presenter: *We are the "pueblo": Art, Solidarity, and the Hispanic Identity in Spain and Cuba during the 1960s.*

Gregory, Christian

Presenter: *The Mitred Edge from the Pope to Rihanna to Moira: How Kitsch Enables the Queer Camp*

Gregory, Katherine

Presenter: *Bovine/Divine: Norma "Duffy" Lyon's "Last Supper" in Butter*

Gribkova, Nadezhda

Presenter: *"Frozen out of Liturgy": Orthodox Christian Aesthetics as Method in Contemporary Art History*

Grillo, Michael

Session Chair: Critical AI Literacy in Art and Design Education and Practice

Grömer, Karina

Presenter: *Working Clothes for Ancient Miners. The Salt Mummies from Chehrābād and their Textiles*

Grotenhuis, Liesbeth

Presenter: *Wearing the halo: the divine rematerialized in Symbolism.*

Grube, Katie

Session Chair: Re - Opening the '85 New Wave Movement
Presenter: *Reconsidering Social(ist) Movements through Dara Birnbaum's Tian'anmen Break In Transmission*

Guhennec, Paul

Presenter: *The late Renaissance Venetian palace façades: a computational eye on the dialectic of "mediocrity" and "novitas"*

Gupta, Huma

Session Chair: Generative AI on the Dissecting Table

H**Hackett, Curry**

Presenter: *"Land as Story." How does land—be it understood as place, territory, or imaginary—tell and hold stories?*

Haferd, Jerome

Presenter: *Radical Preservation and Generative History*

Haffner, Peter

Session Discussant: Methods of Engagement in Undergraduate Research

Hahn, Monica

Session Chair: New Directions in British Art and Architectural History
Session Discussant: The Case for Working Together, Collaborating Together

Haiver, Thomas

Presenter: *Presence and Praxis: The Future of Online Art Exhibitions*

Haladyn, Julian Jason

Session Chair: Artists' Roundtable hosted by Services to Artists Committee
Session Chair: Curatorial Pedagogy and Practice

Halsted, Lyla

Session Chair: Emblematic Encounters: Cross-Cultural Objects and Material Agency in the Early Modern World
Presenter: *Faceless Figuration: A Safavid Kilim in Munich*

Hamer-Light, Julia

Session Chair: Hands-On: Critical Connections Between Craft and Pedagogy

Hamilton, Elizabeth

Presenter: *Decolonizing Art History: An HBCU Case Study*

Hamilton, Louis

Presenter: *History in Extended Reality (XR): Encountering Hidden Worlds of Nineteenth-Century Rome and Istanbul*

Hansen, Maria Fabricius

Presenter: *Cultural Metabolism: The Trajectories of Architecture in Denmark c. 1600*

Harker, Kerry

Presenter: *If Not Now, When? Generations of Women in Sculpture in Britain, 1960–2022*

Harper, James

Presenter: *Artist, Relieved of his Objects: The Lessons of a 1633 Roman Burglary*

Harren, Natilee

Session Discussant: Censorship, Precarity, and Diversity: A Workshop
Presenter: *Susan Silton's Voice*

Harris, Alicia

Session Discussant: Examining the Legacies of the New Deal Era for Indigenous Arts

Hatch, Kevin

Presenter: *"A Complicated Business": Corita Kent's Intertextual Art Practice and the Catholic Left*

Hayes, Dawn

Presenter: *Crossing Borders: The Viewpoint of an Historian on the Power of Objects*

Hazard, Erin

Presenter: *An Artist's House Museum Behind Barbed Wire: the Mary Nohl House, Fox Point, Wisconsin*

He, Qinxin

Session Chair: Connecting In and Out: Toward "Regional" Approaches to Chinese Art
Presenter: *The Canonization of Huang Quan: Rethinking the "Typical Style" of Sichuan Painting during the Tang-Song Transition Period*

Hebron, Micol

Session Workshop Leader: Using Artificial Intelligence proactively as a creative tool in the classroom

Hecker, Sharon

Presenter: *Art, Law and Artistic Collaborations*

Heifler, Sydney

Presenter: *Trina Robbins: Feminist Activist as Friend and Mentor*

Heitz, Kara

Session Chair: Examining the Legacies of the New Deal Era for Indigenous Arts

Presenter: *Reclaiming Indigenous Artistry: Potawatomi Bead Workers and the WPA in Kansas*

Helmreich, Anne

Session Chair: Presenting Contemporary Art in Museums, ca. 1880-1930: Temporary Exhibitions, Institutional Networks and Collecting

Hempstead, Andrea

Session Chair: Design Education Futures

Hempstead, Hannah

Session Chair: Reconsidering Religion in Modern and Contemporary Art: Methods and Approaches

Henderson, Linda

Session Chair: Art, Occultism, and Science in the Time of Hilma af Klint

Heno-Coe, Gilles

Presenter: *An Art Fundamentally Related to the Machine: The Early Films of John & James Whitney*

Henry, Joseph

Session Chair: Magical Realism, New Objectivity, and the Return of Representation: A Reevaluation

Hermano, Claudia

Presenter: *TIL WE ARE FULL*

Hernández, Gaby

Presenter: *Artist Books and Asemic Writing as Decoloniality Vehicles*

Heydarkhani, Maryam

Session Chair: Everyday and the Expression of Modernity: 19th-Century Architecture and Urbanism in the Islamic World

Presenter: *Incomplete Representations: Iran's Pavilion in the 19th-century world fairs*

Hickey, Amber

Presenter: *Ocean Intimacies, Sonic Sovereignty: Deep Listening as Radical Care in Transoceanic Art and Activism*

Hiebert, Ted

Presenter: *Alternate Illuminations: Electricity, Darkness, Visualization*

Higashiyama, Emi

Presenter: *The Empire of the Sun: How the Incan Worship of Nature Continued After Catholic Conversion*

Hines, Megan

Presenter: *Exploring and Finding the Limits in Silicon Valley: Lydia Modi Vitale at Santa Clara University's de Saisset Art Gallery, 1967-78*

Ho, Christine

Presenter: *Between Two Souths: Entanglements Across the South Seas and the American South in China, ca. 1945*

Ho, Kayi

Presenter: *Birthday Celebration and Immortal Paintings in the Imperial Court of the Ming Dynasty*

Hochberg, Gil

Presenter: *Nightmares*

Hogan, Dana

Presenter: *Lois Mailou Jones: International Artist of the Harlem Renaissance*

Hogan, Maeve

Presenter: *Craft and Fiber Art of the 1950s and 1960s in the collection of Helen Louise Allen*

Hogue Smith, Cheryl

Presenter: *Advocating for (Unusual) Faculty Learning Communities*

Holberton, Rhonda

Presenter: *Two Handfuls of Silver Dust*

Holloway, Camara

Session Chair: Critical Race Art History Roundtable: Doing the Work

Presenter: *A Racial Reckoning: Cataloguing Romare Bearden*

Holman, Daisy

Presenter: *Grief, Memory, Legacy: Field-building through partnerships*

Holton, Delaney

Session Chair: Aberrations in Beauty

Presenter: *Body Compositions: Contingent Mattering in the work of Jes Fan and Rachel Youn*

Hong, Kevin

Session Chair: Chemical Intimacies: Thinking with Toxic Media

Presenter: *Polaroid's Expanded Times: Patrick Nagatani and Andrée Tracey's Atomic Theaters*

Hooper, Rachel

Presenter: *Style with Substance: Black Women as Art Collectors and Activists in the U.S. Civil War Era*

Horisaki-Christens, Andrea

Session Chair: Censorship, Precarity, and Diversity: A Workshop

Hornbostel, Paula

Presenter: *Fifty Shades of Bronze: Gaston Lachaise, his foundries and his legacy in both the 20th century and the 21st*

Horne, Brockett

Presenter: *Collecting Monograms: Crest Albums and Personal Branding in Victorian England*

Hornstein, Stéphanie

Presenter: *Word on the Street: Western-Language Signage in turn-of-the-century Egypt*

Horton, Jessica

Presenter: *Arch, Mound, Basket: Mission Abstraction and Indigenous Ecological Forms*

Horton-Insch, Millie

Presenter: *The Mediation of Early Medieval Textiles: Repeated Modes of Reproduction and the Nazi Ahnenerbe Project*

Horwitz, Vu

Presenter: *Collaboration in wood identification: the interdisciplinary work of writing of art histories and conservation methodologies for Congolese heritage objects in Belgian museums.*

Hou, Ekan

Presenter: *Archives of Counterinsurgency*

Houze, Rebecca

Presenter: *Revising The Design History Reader for a Second Edition*

Howard, Mae

Presenter: *Crip Publishing Manifestx: Crippling Journal Editing*
Presenter: *Disabled Erotics*

Hrychuk Kontokosta, Anne

Session Chair: Still Defining Roman Art

Hsieh, Pei-chun

Presenter: *Black Screen: Three Case Studies on the History of Obfuscation in Taiwanese Contemporary Art*

Hu, Yang

Presenter: *Troubling Missionary Legacies in the Contemporary World: African Objects Owned by Christian Congregations in Dutch Ethnographic Museums*

Huang, Linda

Presenter: *Rethinking "Human": Pond Society, Automation Fever, and the Disappearance of the Laboring Body*

Huang, Vivian

Session Discussant: *Aberrations in Beauty*

Hudson, Dale

Presenter: *After labor, oil, and sand extractivism: Dele Adeyemo's "A Dance of Mangroves"*

Huff, Anna

Presenter: *Channelers: AI, authorship, mysticism and meaning making in creative practice and pedagogy*

Hughes, Cecily

Presenter: *The Measure of a Saint: Size, Landscape, and Meaning in St. Olaf Pilgrim Badges*

Hupe, Eric

Presenter: *Digitally Re-animating the Renaissance*

Hussaini, Sana Khan

Presenter: *Advancing Design Education through Hybridity and Communication*

Hutcheson, Rachel

Session Chair: *Reframing Landscape: 50 Years after New Topographics*

Hutchinson, Elizabeth

Presenter: *Roundtable Participant Elizabeth Hutchinson*

Huxtable, Sally-Anne

Session Chair: *DHS-Sponsored Panel: New Directions in Teaching Design History*

Hwang, Eunkyung

Presenter: *Crip Vitae: Navigating Crip Feelings and Time as an Art Educator in Neoliberal Ableist Academia*

Iglesias, Lucila

Presenter: *Sacralizing the Collapse. The Birth of the Franciscan Cult to Our Lady of Miracle after the 1650 Earthquake.*

Iglesias Lukin, Aimé

Presenter: *Portuñol Newyorkaise*

Iles, Chrissie

Presenter: *Creating a Whitney Biennial: Reflections from a Curator's Perspective*

Ilias, Roxane

Presenter: *Intercontinental Shifts: Sandú Darié and the Reconfiguration of Post-War Painting in the Americas*

Ittner, Claire

Presenter: *Lessons on the Ground: Eldzier Cortor in the Sea Islands*

Iturralde, Diana

Presenter: *Painting the Crude Reality: Art as Manifestation of Survivance in Gustavo Toaquiza Ugsha's Amazonian Series*

Iyengar Vadapalli, Rohini

Presenter: *Ways of Seeing Hindu Gods*

J**Jack, Deborah**

Presenter: *The Space Between: Deborah Jack*

Jacks, Will

Presenter: *Learning to Explore: How the darkroom serves as more than a space for making photos*

Jackson, Katherine

Presenter: *Imaginative Rediscovery: Destruction in Art and the Work of Rita Keegan*

Jackson, Quiana M.

Presenter: *Embodied Ethnography: The Radical Performance Practices of Hurston, Dunham, and Primus in Afro-Caribbean Contexts*

Jacobo, Joshua

Presenter: *Reintegrating the Kanon: Classical Proportions and Contemporary Pedagogical Strategies*

Jacobs, Hannah

Presenter: *Hidden Histories of the Holocaust: "Guided Modeling" as a Critical Digital Humanities Method*

Jacobs, Karen

Presenter: *A sea of resilience: Oceanic (in)visibility*

Jacobs, Margaret

Presenter: *Steel Medicine: Indigenous Eco Knowledge in Contemporary Art Practice*

Jaffee, Barbara

Presenter: *Patterns of Perception*

Jagger, Sharon

Presenter: *Voice as Resistance to Abjection*
 Presenter: *Voice as Resistance to Abjection*

Jain, Puneet

Presenter: *Probing 'Assistive' Futures: Shifting imaginaries/narratives with people with disabilities in India, Canada, and Germany*

Jakovljevic, Branislav

Session Chair: *What Are Information Aesthetics?*
 Presenter: *Artificial Intelligence and Kitsch*

Jakubowska, Agata

Session Chair: *1975-2025: Revisiting 1970s Art and Feminism in Latin America and Eastern Europe*
 Presenter: *Women Artists among "Women of the Whole World" (WIDF Magazine)*

Jameson-Ellsmore, Ben

Presenter: *Space and Visual Culture in American Hackerspaces*

Jaremtchuk, Daria

Session Chair: *Brazilian & U.S. Art in Exile: Transnationalism, Migration, and the Politics of Being "Latin American" in the United States and Brazil*
 Presenter: *Art & the Poetics of Exile*

Jaskot, Paul

Session Chair: Digital Methods for Difficult Hidden Art Histories
 Presenter: *Hidden Histories of the Holocaust: "Guided Modeling" as a Critical Digital Humanities Method*

Jasper, Hannah

Session Workshop Leader: Funding Your Arts Research and Practice: Strategic Proposal Writing for Grant and Fellowship Funding

Jauregui, Danny

Session Discussant: Brownness In Plain Sight / Brownness as Practice

Javaheri-Saatchi, Laleh

Presenter: *The Achaemenid-Style Open-Ended Bracelet with Animal Head Terminals: An Emblematic Object of Achaemenid Imperial Power*

Javani, Elnaz

Presenter: *Oddments*

Jen (Bom), Lam

Presenter: *Crip Art Residency: Reimagining Access, Community, and Queercrip Artistic Expression in Hong Kong*
 Presenter: *Crip Publishing Manifestx: Crippling Journal Editing*

Jenkins, Joshua

Session Chair: Art and Work

Jia, Ruo

Presenter: *Ornament, OrLand: Radical Profanations*

Jim, Alice

Session Chair: 10 Years of ADVA Journal: Hindsight, Insights, Futures Thinking

Jimenez, Maya

Presenter: *Advocating for (Unusual) Faculty Learning Communities*

Joekalda, Kristina

Presenter: *Travelling Exhibition or Festival? Baltic Art and German Propaganda during World War I*

Johnson, Deborah

Presenter: *The Breathe Project*

Johnson, Geraldine

Session Chair: Reproducing Renaissance Italy in the Long Nineteenth Century

Johnston, Patricia

Presenter: *THE SHEPHERDESS IN THE COLONIES: YOUNG WOMEN IN THE PASTORAL MODE*

Jolles, Adam

Presenter: *Identity and Self-Representation in the East Harlem Community Resource Center's Photo Workshop*

Jolly, Jennifer

Presenter: *The Scholar-Collector: Elizabeth Easby*

Jon, Ihnmi

Presenter: *Exchanging "the Common Love of the Beautiful": Abstract Art and Minnesota Project (1954-1960)*

Jones, Amelia

Session Chair: System Failure: How to Survive and Thrive in Today's Art and Design Higher Education

Jones, Caroline

Session Chair: Generative AI on the Dissecting Table

Jones, Nathaniel

Session Chair: The Posthuman Personhood of the Dead in the Ancient Mediterranean

Joo, Woojeong

Presenter: *The War Dead in Japanese Wartime Films: Fiction and Documentary*

Josten, Jennifer

Presenter: *Ver América: Catalyzing a Generation of Contemporary Latin American Artists in 1992 Antwerp*

Joynes, Les

Session Workshop Leader: Empowering Professionals: Discovering the Impact of Coaching in Creative Fields.

Jozwik, Nicole

Presenter: *Potosí's Silver Age, an Age of Wind: The Wayrachina as an Icon of Indigenous Technology and Global Extractivism*

Juhasz, Alexandra

Presenter: *Roundtable discussion*

Jung, Jacqueline

Presenter: *Wie man Skulpturen aufnehmen soll: A Continuing Question in the Study of Gothic Sculpture*

Jung, Yuha

Session Chair: Navigating the changing terrain of fair use in the digital world

K**Kácsor, Adrienn**

Presenter: *Fugitive Avant-garde*

Kaczmarek, Christopher

Presenter: *Adjunct Betterment (what can we do?)*

Kahng, Amy

Session Chair: Deliberately University Based: Marginalized Artists and the Growth of University Art Spaces
 Presenter: *Unhindered by Our Polluted Earth: "Nationless Neutrality" in Nam June Paik's Broadcast Television Works*

Kakembo, Nasozi

Presenter: *Ethical Retail Sourcing and Manufacturing Framework: A Strategic Approach to Cultural Restitution of African Heritage Objects*
 Presenter: *Sourcing and Communicating About Heritage Objects: An Ethical Standards Framework for Consumers and Media*

Kalb, Peter

Presenter: *Following the New Silk Road to a History of Contemporary Art*

Kalin, Tom

Presenter: *Gran Fury: Activism, Art and Design*

Kamehiro, Stacy

Presenter: *Mapping Race or Nation in the Kingdom of Hawai'i*

Kane-Small, Noah

Session Workshop Leader: Toward an Inclusive Framework: (Re)Building Black Art Histories

Kang, Jiaqi

Session Chair: Art as Shifting Knowledge?: Histories of Science, Medicine, and Sinophone Art
 Presenter: *From Primeval Chaos to the New History Group: a 'minor' history of the '85 New Wave*

Kang, Stephanie

Session Chair: The Politics of the Archive: Reimagining the Histories of the Asian Diaspora

Kanouse, Sarah

Presenter: *You are [Always] in Native Space: grappling with legacies of colonization through sound*

Kantorikova, Jana

Presenter: *Symbolism, the Symbol of the Tree and the Claudelian Theater*

Kanwischer, Charles

Session Chair: Critical AI Literacy in Art and Design Education and Practice

Karagöz, Özge

Session Chair: Explosive Objects: Material Histories of Violence in Europe, 1920s-1940s

Presenter: *Socialist Realism across Turkey and the Soviet Union: Abidin Dino, the Socialist Body, and Stalinist Happiness*

Karlic, Karolina

Session Discussant: ARTS + ARCHIVES TEACHING PARTNERSHIPS: FOSTERING ARTS STUDENTS' TRANSFORMATIVE USES OF SPECIAL COLLECTIONS AND ARCHIVES

Karrels, Nancy

Session Chair: Taking and Making: Artistic Reckonings with Cultural Property Theft in the Long Nineteenth Century

Karson, Jennifer

Presenter: *AI Interventions with Artist-Made Datasets*

Katrahmani, Golnar

Presenter: *Multilingual Typography in Practice*

Katsaridou, Iro

Presenter: *When Museums Take a Stance: Refugee Crisis in Greece and the Practices of MOMus-Thessaloniki Museum of Photography*

Katzeman, Aaron

Session Chair: Workers of the Land: Representing Revolutionary Peasant and Agrarian Movements

Presenter: *Cultivating Struggle: Ed Greevy's Protest Portraiture in the Farming Community of Waiāhole-Waikāne*

Kawata, Akihisa

Session Discussant: The Warring Face of Realism: Cross-media Approach to Japanese War Art, 1931-1945

Kelleher, Philip

Presenter: *"Hanging Out at Angela Davis Park: Regina Agu and Gabriel Martinez's Collective Space Making"*

Kent, Charlotte

Session Chair: Processes of Memory: Digital Practices and Re-Membering Histories

Kent-Marvick, Andrew

Presenter: *"Multivalence in Symbolist Presentations of Spiritual and Mystical Transfixion"*

Kenyon, Victoria

Presenter: *Unobservable: Eunice Newton Foote and Photographic Evidence*

Kerman, Monique

Presenter: *African Matrilineal Models of Empowerment in the Art of Tabita Rezaire and Joséfa Ntjam*

Kersten, Benjamin

Session Chair: Comparative Diaspora in Art History: Revisiting Diaspora and Visual Culture

Presenter: *The Dybbuk Haunting Jewish History: Solomon Ludovín's Photographs from the Pale of Settlement*

Keshavjee, Serena

Presenter: *Juliette Bisson and the Art of Ectoplasm*

Kessler, Marni

Presenter: *Aerial Intimacies: Edgar Degas's Ironers, Coal Smoke, and Chemicals*

Khan, Sabir

Session Chair: Art Factories, Community-led Cultural Centers, and Third Spaces in Repurposed Buildings

Khatibi, Marjan

Presenter: *Virtual Empathy: Transforming Design and Social Change through VR*

Khaymaz, Sheyda

Session Chair: Cross-Cultural Conversations in Visuality and Textuality

Presenter: *Zardazgheneb: Motion, Chaos, and Pathos in the Furigraphy of Hawad*

Kiaer, Christina

Presenter: *Blackness in Constructivism*

Kidd, Fiona

Presenter: *Sogdian bodies through the Achaemenid lens*

Kim, Boram

Presenter: *Beyond the Studio: Navigating the IRB Process in Artistic Research*

Kim, Bowie Bo Gyung

Presenter: *Controller Effect: Teleporting into the Game Art as Virtual Citizen*

Kim, Cecilia

Presenter: *Finding Home: Layering Time and Space through Projection*

Kim, Ji-hoon

Session Discussant: Generative AI on the Dissecting Table

Kim, Jinah

Session Chair: Mapping Color in History-DH project in action
Presenter: *Finding artisanal intelligence in yellow: Nepalese manuscripts and processed orpiment*

Kim, Liz

Presenter: *Ayoka Chenzira and Intersectionality as Generational Praxis*

Kim, Mina

Presenter: *Concreteness and Historicity: The Value and Role of Abstraction in Early Twentieth-Century Korean Art and Design*

Kina, Laura

Presenter: *Okinawan Diaspora Indigenous Solidarities and the Shimanchu Hajichi Tattoo Revival*

Kincaid, Megan

Presenter: *"DYN" in Mexico City: Aesthetic Possibility and Abstraction in Exile, 1939-1944*

King, Homy

Session Chair: Reframing East and West: Colonialism, Modernism, Cultural Hybridity

Presenter: *Better Living in Eichlerville: California Modernism's Influence on Apple*

Kinney, Hannah

Presenter: *"More than mere ordering from price-lists": a material history of acquiring The Metropolitan Museum of Art's plaster casts*

Kirsh, Andrea

Session Discussant: The Ongoing Life of Refuse in Art

Kite, Whitney

Session Chair: Geoheritage in the Medieval World

Kleinman, Sarah

Session Chair: Narratives of Exile, Migration, and Movement in Contemporary Art

Presenter: *Reimagining Minimalism: Kynaston McShine's Contributions to Mid-1960s British Art and Architectural Narratives in 'Primary Structures'*

Kliger, Marina

Presenter: *The Genre Anecdotique and Feminine Historical Consciousness in Early Nineteenth-Century France*

Knedler, Epiphany

Session Chair: Navigating the changing terrain of fair use in the digital world

Knight-Lueth, Ranelle

Presenter: *Italian Fascism on Display: The Italian Pavilion at the Century of Progress World Exposition, 1933-34*

Knuckles, Nectar

Presenter: *Mansudae Overseas Project: Between North Korea and Africa*

Kocialkowska, Kamila

Presenter: *Kruchenykh's Explosive Prints: Elemental Anarchy in the Gelatine Press and the Gelatine Bomb*

Koering, Jérémie

Presenter: *Louis Marin's graphic imagination*

Koh, Jinyoung

Presenter: *Beyond the Studio: Navigating the IRB Process in Artistic Research*

Koleda, Kacper

Presenter: *Globalizing the Disaster Cai Guo-Qiang's The Century with Mushroom Clouds*

Kong, Carlos

Presenter: *The Repertoire of Migrant-Situated Knowledge: Archival Reenactments and Migrant Remembrance in the Art of Cana Bilir-Meier*

Kopania, Kamil

Presenter: *THE MEDIEVAL ORIGINS OF THE POLISH "SZOPKA"*

Koričančić, Velebita

Session Chair: Reframing Madness: Arts at the Intersection of Mental Health and Mad Studies

Koričančić, Velebita

Presenter: *Eccentric Bodies: Decolonizing Female Corporeality in Latin American Women's Outsider Art*

Korola, Katerina

Session Chair: Process-Generated Networks: Craft and Sociality in Feminist Art

Presenter: *Images of Exposure: Colour and Toxicity at the Filmfabrik Wolfen*

Korroch, Kate

Presenter: *Queer Recoding of Asian American Stereotypes in TT Takemoto's Semiotics of Sab (2011)*

Kosut, Marin

Presenter: *"A Rat Came to Your Art Party": On Starting a Gallery in a Pay Phone at a New York City Bus Stop*

Kowalski, Jennifer

Presenter: *First Things First: Scaffolding assignments to foster creativity and critical thinking around generative AI*

Kozak, Luba

Presenter: *Bridging Relationships: Pet Animals as Connectors in Eighteenth-Century British Portraiture*

Kral, Diana

Session Affiliated Society Chair: Exploring Methodological Approaches in Art Market Studies - TIAMSA Business meeting

Kraus, Heidi

Presenter: *Unveiling Marianne: Exploring Colonial Narratives in the Visual Programs of the Palais de la Porte Dorée*

Kriebel, Sabine

Presenter: *Trieb: Schad's Freud*

Kruse, Jillian

Presenter: *Collective Labors: Collaboration as Motif and Method in Pissarro's Prints*

Kryscynski, Kristina

Session Discussant: Body As Surface (Landscape)

Kuipers, Grace

Presenter: *Mexican Modernists, the Mineral Frontier, and Subterranean Sovereignty*

Kulkarni, Aasawari

Presenter: *Strategies of Hierarchy and Harmony in Setting Devanagari with Latin Type*

Kunysz, Pavel

Presenter: *Beyond explanation and description : What can poetic evocation contribute to the ethnography of a place's social imaginaries ?*

Kupfer, Paula

Presenter: *A Garden without Slavery? Photography and Black Histories in the Rio de Janeiro Botanical Garden*

Kupfner, Mariah

Presenter: *Gathered Cloth and Paper Fragments: Scrapbooks, Disability, and the Piecework of Self-making*

Kwon, Marci

Presenter: *Roundtable Participant Marci Kwon*

Kyo, Yi Yi Mon (Rosaline)

Presenter: *Visions of Tibet: Tensions between Artistic Experimentations and Constructing State Narratives*

L**LaBouff, Nicole**

Presenter: *In Search Of... UFO Art at the Margins*

Laferriere, Carolyn

Presenter: *Intimacy between Living and Dead on Classical Marble Lekythoi*

Lai, Renee

Presenter: *The Bathing of the Sphinx*

Lam, Fidelia

Presenter: *let them eat plastic!*

Lambert, Katherine

Presenter: *Thresholds of the Frontier*

Langefeld, Maximilian

Session Chair: Up in Arms: Aesthetics of Resistance and Solidarity in Contemporary Art

Presenter: *Difference, Dissonance, Discord? Queer Curatorial Activism in a Harmonious Society*

Langendorfer, Breton

Presenter: *Thinking Through Achaemenid Ornament*

Lapin Dardashti, Abigail

Session Chair: Brazilian & U.S. Art in Exile: Transnationalism, Migration, and the Politics of Being "Latin American" in the United States and Brazil

Presenter: *Mapping Jewish-Latin American Consciousness: Race and Space in the Art of Anna Bella Geiger*

Largo, Marissa

Session Discussant: 10 Years of ADVA Journal: Hindsight, Insights, Futures Thinking

Larnerd, Joseph

Session Chair: People's Histories of Material Culture in the United States

Latimer, Tirza

Session Discussant: Sapphic Modernism

Le, Jason

Presenter: *Performing Glitter in Contemporary Trans Art*

Leahy, Brian

Session Chair: Beyond Stories: Art Writing and Narrative

Lechner, Amanda

Session Chair: Artists' Roundtable hosted by Services to Artists Committee

Session Chair: Beyond Albers, Itten and Munsell: How are artists and educators re-approaching color theory and practice?

Lee, Eva

Presenter: *The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #2: EXPERIENCE*

Lee, Jaewook

Presenter: *Unraveling the Uncanny Valley: The Role of Facial Recognition and Empathy in Immersive Media and 3D Animation*

Lee, Jennifer

Session Discussant: Re - Opening the '85 New Wave Movement

Presenter: *How Maoist Anxiety Structured the Art of the Beijing Spring*

Lee, Sohl

Session Chair: In Relation to Art: Community, Collaboration, and Collective Agency in Contemporary Art from East Asia

Lees-Maffei, Grace

Presenter: *Revising The Design History Reader for a Second Edition*

Lehner, Ace

Session Chair: The Case for Trans Visual Studies

Leibsohn, Dana

Session Discussant: Indigenous Manuscripts of Early Modern Latin America

Leigh, Allison

Presenter: *"The Matrix of Historical Moments: Experimenting with Multivalent Geographies and Styles"*

Lemonias, Krystle

Session Chair: Unearthing Black History within Animation: A Conversation with The Hidden Critique

Letvin, Alexandra

Session Chair: On Titles

Presenter: *Manet's Woman with a Cigarette from 1883 to 2025*

Leu, Felicia F.

Session Chair: Up in Arms: Aesthetics of Resistance and Solidarity in Contemporary Art

Presenter: *Blood on your hands? Teresa Margolles' "Sobre la sangre" and the Audience as Witness*

Levinsohn, James

Presenter: *Photography Without the Prick of Desire: Wolfgang Tillmans' i didn't inhale (1997) and the Post-Psychoanalytic Subject*

Levy, Ellen

Session Chair: PST and Other Art/Sci Models for the Future

Presenter: *Preserving the Commons Via Art*

Lewis, Lillian

Presenter: *A Forager's Guide to Art*

Lewis, Sarah

Presenter: *"Roman" Sarcophagi from the eastern Mediterranean and the "Art" of "Rome"*

Li, Janice

Presenter: *Collective Healing Through Confrontation in Safety: Grace Ndiritu's The Healing Pavilion*

Li, Xinyi

Presenter: *Designing with Language(s): Pedagogical Reflections in Multilingual Classrooms*

Li, Yiqing

Presenter: *The Invention of Pure Forms: Abstraction, Art, and Science in Early Twentieth-Century China*

Li, Yizhuo

Session Chair: Art as Shifting Knowledge?: Histories of Science, Medicine, and Sinophone Art

Session Chair: Collective Work: Funding and Collaborating on International Projects and Research

Liang, Xinyu

Presenter: *The "Pictorial Turn" in Ilkhanid Iran: Jami al-Tawarikh's illustrations as a dialogue to Global pictorial history*

Liberatore, Sarah

Presenter: *Fostering Success in the classroom, one Google Arts and Culture story at a time*

Lin, Nancy

Session Chair: The "Postsocialist Contemporary:" Passages in Modern-Contemporary Chinese Art

Presenter: *Realism after Socialist Realism: On-site Art Practice in the 1990s*

Lindell, John

Session Chair: Gran Fury: Activism, Art and Design

Linden, Delanie

Presenter: *Chevreul, Color Juxtaposition, & the 'Flat Tints' of Chinese Painting*

Liu, Andrea Jung-An

Presenter: *Avant-Garde Practices, Nationalistic Aims: Japanese Photomurals in the 1930s and 1940s*

Lloyd, Kirsten

Presenter: *'The Problem Is Power': Navigating Museums' Wellbeing Turn from a Feminist Perspective*

Lluberes, Niberca

Session Chair: Next Now: Studio Art Foundations

Locker, Jesse

Session Chair: Artists and their Objects: The Material World of the Early Modern Artist

Loeb, Carolyn

Session Chair: Artists' Sanctuaries: Engaging with House Museums

Longair, Elyse

Session Chair: Curatorial Pedagogy and Practice
Session Chair: Vantage Point: Artist Panel 1
Session Chair: Vantage Point: CAA Services to Artists Committee Exhibition
Session Chair: Vantage Point: CAA Services to Artists Committee Exhibition Reception
Session Chair: Vantage Point: Performance by Natalie Majaba Waldburger

Looser, Thomas

Presenter: *In Relation to Ocean Worlds*

Lopez Rivas, Philomena

Session Chair: Brownness In Plain Sight / Brownness as Practice

Lopez-Oliveros, Alejandra

Presenter: *Reframing contemporary narratives: Celeste Rojas Mugica's Inventario Iconoclasta de la Insurrección Chilena*

Loss, Jacqueline

Presenter: *Revisualizing the Russian Axis in Cuban Visual Arts*

Lovatt, Anna

Presenter: *Looking Patiently: Donald Rodney Confronts the Medical Gaze*

Love, Thomas

Session Chair: Other Germans and German Others: Questions of Identity in Contemporary German Art
Presenter: *6.25% Grey: On Adrian Piper's "Retirement from Being Black"*

Lovings-Gomez, Lauren

Presenter: *Unraveling Materiality: Anna Lea Merritt's The Weaving Shed and the Transatlantic Textile Industry*

Lozada-Mendieta, Natalia

Presenter: *Monuments and monumentality in Ancient American rock art: the case of engraved snakes from the middle and upper Orinoco river*

Lua, Abi

Session Chair: Towards a "Pacific Turn" in American Art History

Lucento, Angelina

Session Chair: Decolonization and the Avant-Garde Art School: Rethinking the Bauhaus, VKhUTEMAS, Mezhyhirya and Beyond

Lucking, Maura

Session Chair: Architecture and the Donor Class: Philanthropy, Power, and Empire

Luescher, Andreas

Session Chair: Artists' Sanctuaries: Engaging with House Museums

Luke, Megan

Presenter: *What the Eye Does Not See*

Luna, Mev

Presenter: *Para-Protest Practices and Restoring Affinity*

Ly, Boreth

Session Chair: Asian and Asian Diasporic Art in Comparative Perspectives

Lyimo, Kendra

Presenter: *Fluid Brushstrokes: Firelei Báez, the African Diaspora, and a new notion of Latinidad*

Lynch, Isabelle

Session Chair: Artificial Suns: Photography and Alternative Illumination

Lynford, Sophie

Presenter: *Out of the Shadows: Re-envisioning Simeon Solomon*

Lyon, Christopher

Presenter: *From Depicted to Embodied Landscape: Preparing the Ground of Smith's Fields*

M**Mace, Dakota**

Session Chair: Let the Land Hold You: Place & Memory
Presenter: *Dahodiyinii (Sacred Places)*

MacGibeny, Abigael

Session Chair: This Old Text and Taxonomy: Renovating Art Historical Documentation

Machado, Li

Session Discussant: The Students and Emerging Professionals Committee's (SEPC) Guide To All Things CAA

Machado Mayea, Mailyn

Presenter: *The Art of Giving: The General Economy of Cuban Art and New Virtual Communities Mailyn Machado*

MacMurdie, Meekyung

Session Chair: Moving the Image: Medieval Diagrams and their Audiences
Presenter: *The Kitab al-Diryaq on the Nature of Knowledge*

MacPherson, Thomas

Presenter: *Color in Michelangelo's Doni Tondo and Pontormo's Deposition*

Maddaloni-Yu, Fosca

Session Chair: Emblematic Encounters: Cross-Cultural Objects and Material Agency in the Early Modern World
Presenter: *Riveting Encounters: Mounted Ceramics in the Oeuvre of John Hoffman (fl. 1577–1600), Stranger Silversmith in Elizabethan London*

Magda, Mina

Presenter: *Goncharova's Primitivism: A Search for the Native Body*

Maggiore, Sky

Presenter: *Ways to Endure*

Magleby, Sarah

Presenter: *Bourgeois Women as Collectors in Late Medieval Paris*

Maglione, Biancalucia

Presenter: *Fiamma Vigo and the promotion of Latin American art in Italy between the 1950s and 1960s: The case of Peruvian art.*

Magouliotis, Nikolaos

Presenter: *A Native Transplant: Neoclassicism in post-Ottoman Greece.*

Maher, Terah

Presenter: *Albers Variations*

Mahfouz, Ali

Presenter: *Preserving Egypt's Cultural Heritage Amidst Urban Development: A Situated Perspective on the Historic Cairo Cemetery*

Mahler, Marina

Presenter: *Anna Mahler by Marina Mahler. 'In-conversation' with Marina Fistoulari Mahler, daughter of Anna Mahler. A Personal View.*

Mahon, Alyce

Presenter: *Ithell Colquhoun: Imaging the Lesbian Shore for Surrealism*

Majluf, Natalia

Presenter: *Of Objects, Politics, and Ideas: The Material Cultures of Independence*

Mak, Kathy Yim King

Session Chair: Chinese Art Headed "South": Histories, Practices and Models in the 20th-21st Centuries

Presenter: *Realigning with the South: Mural Resurgence and National Independence in Mao-China National Painting*

Makela, Peter

Presenter: *For the Benefit of all Sentient Beings*

Malevez, Apolline

Session Chair: Sculpture as a Collective Practice in the Long Nineteenth Century

Presenter: *Caring for the Studio*

Mallory, Sarah

Session Chair: Gender, Sexuality, and Non-Pristine Nature in Northern European Art and Material Culture, ca. 1350-1750

Malone, Meredith

Presenter: *Seeding the Future: Beatriz Cortez's Speculative Sculpture*

Man Yuet, Cheng

Presenter: *Crip Art Residency: Reimagining Access, Community, and Queercrip Artistic Expression in Hong Kong*

Mann, Justin

Session Chair: Geoheritage in the Medieval World

Manohar, Mohit

Session Chair: Race in South Asian Art

Manovich, Lev

Presenter: *Compression/Generation: Realism, Modernism, and AI*

Mantegari Bertorelli, Sébastien

Presenter: *Images of the Spirit. Art, Science, and Occultism in the Visual Works of Carl Gustav Jung*

Marie, Ana

Presenter: *Panelist - Archivist*

Maroja, Camila

Presenter: *Notes on an Overdue Phenomenon: The Rise of Indigenous Art in Brazil*

Marquardt, Savannah

Session Chair: The Posthuman Personhood of the Dead in the Ancient Mediterranean

Presenter: *Grounding the Grave of Agamemnon*

Marshall, Nancy Rose

Session Chair: "The Incomplete" in the Long Nineteenth Century

Martens, Jasper

Presenter: *"Wat men veerst haelt, dat smaeket soetst": The pomander as a miniature cabinet of curiosities'*

Martin, Carolyn

Session Discussant: The Students and Emerging Professionals Committee's (SEPC) Guide To All Things CAA

Martin, Craig

Session Chair: Art and Work

Session Chair: Design and Disability: Changing Perspectives and Opportunities

Martin, Daphne

Presenter: *Material Theologies of Artemis Ortheia*

Martin, Meredith

Presenter: *Collaboration, Creativity, and the Public Humanities*

Martinez, Frank

Session Discussant: Navigating the changing terrain of fair use in the digital world

Martinez, Jeannette

Presenter: *Contemporary Art and Visual Culture of Central America and the U.S. Diaspora*

Martínez Martínez, Teresa

Session Chair: Divine Senses: Exploring Sensorial Experiences in Religious Contexts throughout the Premodern Iberian World

Marvin, Jenna

Presenter: *The Problem of Two Prints: Photographing Depth in the Cave and the Mine Shaft*

Mason, Noelle

Presenter: *X-Ray Vision vs. Invisibility*

Mata Fragua, Leah

Presenter: *An Exploration of Memory, Resistance, and Creativity Amid Environmental Flux*

Mattos Avolese, Claudia

Presenter: *Indigenous protagonism and curatorial practice in contemporary art of Brazil*

Mayer, Tamar

Presenter: *Curatorial Empathy in a Campus on Crisis*

Mayfield, Jordan

Presenter: *Black Trans Feminist Memories in Tourmaline's "Atlantic is a Sea of Bones"*

Mazariegos, Eric

Presenter: *The Shape of Tairona Time: Art, Technologies, Ecologies*

Mazzocca, Piergianna

Presenter: *Architectures of Improvement: Housing the Malaria Eradication in Venezuela, 1958-1965*

McBryde, Brynne

Presenter: *"Women whose faces alone are hidden": pornography and nineteenth-century gynecology*

McCabe, James

Session Chair: Troubling the Archive: Reassessing Women's Artistic Production in the Long Nineteenth Century

Presenter: *Julie Looks at Laure and Laure Looks Back: The Issue of Reproducing Édouard Manet's Olympia in Julie Manet-Rouart's Copies*

McCardel, Lauren

Session Chair: Women Artists in Modern Movements

McCloskey Wolfe, Laura

Presenter: *Sacred Touch: Pilgrimage Tokens and Seals as Apotropaic Conduits for Divine Transformation in Ireland and Spain in the Middle Ages*

McConnell, James

Presenter: *The political activist as patron*

McCoy, Marsha

Session Chair: The Women of the Whitney Biennials: Artists In and Out of the Mainstream

Presenter: *In and Out of the Mainstream: Alice Forman and the Art of Domestic Space in Contemporary Times*

McDermott, Tamryn

Presenter: *Intermedia Journaling & Poetic Inquiry as Artist/Researcher/Teacher*

Session Workshop Leader: A Pedagogy Workshop: Building Your Teaching Toolkit – Collaborative Teaching and Learning

McDonald, Cecil

Presenter: *The Space Between: Cecil McDonald*

McDonald, Jacquelyn

Session Chair: Sustaining Legacy: The Elisabet Ney Museum's Engagement into the 21st century

McDonald, Jacquelyn

Presenter: *German- American salonnière Elisabet Ney: Berlin, München, Austin*

McFadden, Joshua Rashaad

Presenter: *Pressing On: Visual Narratives of Black Trans Activists' Fight for Existence*

McFerrin, Neville

Session Chair: The Achaemenid Body: Making and Reflecting on Achaemenid Art and Fashion Histories

McGregor, Jennifer

Presenter: *Conundrum of Permanence in Public Art*

McLaughlin, Laurel

Session Chair: How do you throw a brick through the window...: Expanding Publics and Embodiments

McManus, Karla

Presenter: *Birding with a Camera while Female: A Researcher's Dilemma*

Mecugni, Anna

Session Chair: Sounding the Body: The Sung Voice in Contemporary Art

Mehl, Isabel

Session Chair: Women and Letters

Mehta, Khushmi

Presenter: *Postcolonial Pedagogies: The Development of the Faculty of Fine Arts, Baroda*

Mehta, Trisha

Presenter: *Co-Envisioning Adaptive Ecologies: Collaborative Workshops with Crip Designers for Future Climate Architecture*

Mei, Feixue

Presenter: *Collaborative Creativity and Digital Identity: Reimagining Authorship in the Digital Age*

Meloche, Alysha

Session Workshop Leader: Bad advice for teachers

Menconeri, Kate

Presenter: *OPEN HOUSE: Contemporary Artist's Interventions and Exhibitions at the Nineteenth Century Artist's Home and Studios of Thomas Cole*

Menevse, Asli

Presenter: *The Graphic Dialectics of Jules Grandjouan's Les Esclaves Modernes*

Mengist, Nathanael

Presenter: *Alchemies of birth; Or, the black purposes of assisted reproductive technologies.*

Merjian, Ara

Presenter: *Metaphysics and Politics: De Chirico between Dada and New Objectivity*

Metzger, Cyle

Presenter: *You Gotta Keep Fighting Girly: Trans Art Now*

Metzger, Sean

Session Chair: "Foreigners Everywhere!": Art and Refugee Identification

Mevorah, Vera

Presenter: *Mimicry and Irony in Internet Memes – Friends or Foes?*

Mey, Vera

Presenter: *Further Than the Eye Can See: Sabapathy's Southeast Asia as Critical Regionalism*

Meyer, James

Session Chair: The 1990s: Turn to the Contemporary

Meyer, Richard

Presenter: *Gran Fury: Activism, Art and Design*

Meyerovitch, Adi

Presenter: *The Architecture of French Imperialism in Ottoman Jerusalem*

Meza-DesPlas, Rosemary

Session Chair: Hair Power: Culture, Materiality, Politics of Hair in Contemporary Art

Mi, Jinze

Presenter: *Female Nurses in Winslow Homer's Civil War-era Works on Paper*

Michelon, Christina

Session Discussant: Haptic Histories: The Politics of Paper & Its Industrial Entanglements

Presenter: *Collaboration in Boston: The Legacy of Allan Rohan Crite*

Middleman, Rachel

Session Discussant: Artists' Legacy Stewardship: field-building efforts

Presenter: *Hiding in Plain Site: Mapping Female Agency Across the Archive*

Milano, Ronit

Presenter: *Decolonizing Art History in Israel-Palestine*

Miller, Bryan

Presenter: *Assemblageing Art in the Middle Ground: untangling the entanglement of visual cultures in contact along the Great Walls frontier*

Miller, Jordan

Presenter: *What were correct forms for ancient Egyptian gods?*

Miller, Rachel

Session Chair: Rethinking the Theory and Methods Art History Course

Mills, Katherine

Session Chair: Natural Disasters and Artistic Innovation in Colonial Peru, 1650-1700
Presenter: *Rebuilding Cuzco: Local Stonemasons in the aftermath of the 1650 Earthquake*

Min, Susette

Presenter: *Beyond Asian American Art: Private Practices & An Archive of Becoming*

Mintz, Thomas

Presenter: *A Visual Timeline: Mapping Influences of Pictorialism and Modernism in New York and Seattle Photographic Clubs, 1900–1941*

Mirzoeff, Nicholas

Session Discussant: Comparative Diaspora in Art History: Revisiting Diaspora and Visual Culture
Session Chair: Decolonial Jewish Practice in Art and Visual Culture After Gaza

Mitchell, Kimberly

Presenter: *Design for Health: Empowering Design and Architecture Students through Innovative Pedagogy*

Mitchell, W. J. T.

Presenter: *Democratic Therapy*

Mithlo, Nancy Marie

Presenter: *"Imagining" With Deep Domains of Indigenous Film*

Mitrovic, Mijail

Presenter: *Mestizo gourds, Indian gourds: the indigenist construction of popular art in Peru*

Mock, Phoebe

Presenter: *How the modern myth of sexual dimorphism has impacted the study of Hermaphrodites*

Modigliani, Leah

Presenter: *Killer Buildings, Verticality and Warped Space: the Catastrophic Return(s) of Tower Block Failure*

Molarsky-Beck, Marina

Presenter: *The Erotics of Doubling in Germaine Krull's Les amies*

Monahan, Anne

Presenter: *Hiding in Plain Site: Mapping Female Agency Across the Archive*

Moncrieffe, Michelle V.

Presenter: *Mother Molds: Art and Reproductive Health Justice in the Academic Museum*

Monroe, Casey

Presenter: *Language of Landscape: The Frederic Edwin Church Digital Cataloguing Project, Cooper Hewitt, Smithsonian Design Museum*

Montalvo-Senior, María Camila

Presenter: *Curating with the Earth: Indigenous Material Practices and the Reimagining of Art*

Moon, Iris

Session Chair: Rethinking Chinese Export Ceramics Now
Presenter: *A Feminist Revision of Chinoiserie*

Mooney, Amy

Session Chair: "The Space Between" The Lasting Influence of Archibald J. Motley, Jr.

Moore, Nikki

Presenter: *Field Work: Tina Modotti and the Free Schools of Agriculture, México, 1926-1932.*

Moorhead, Bailey

Presenter: *General Education as a Foundation for Holistic Development in Art Students*

Moran, Claire

Presenter: *De-Hierarchising Impressionism Studies via UK/US Collaborations*

Morawski, Erica

Session Chair: Creativity, Consumption, and Spectacle: Interrogating "Collectible" Design

Morgan, Andrea

Session Chair: Women Artists and the Politics of Neoclassicism

Morgan, Nicholas

Presenter: *Critique from Within and Without: The 1993 Whitney Biennial*

Moridpour, Neda

Presenter: *Archiving Political Resistance - Woman Life Freedom*

Morosse, Mar

Session Chair: Art, Its History and Institutions in the Age of AI and Posthumanism

Morris, Meggie

Session Chair: How Has Decolonizing Art History Worked for You?

Morris, Sara

Session Chair: State Fairs and American Art

Morrissy, Shane

Session Chair: Haptic Histories: The Politics of Paper & Its Industrial Entanglements
Presenter: *The Materiality of Everyday Ephemera in the Progressive Era Battle over Disability Visibility.*

Moskalewicz, Magdalena

Presenter: *Exhibiting Eastern Europe after 1989*

Moss, Ceci

Presenter: *The Mandeville Art Gallery at UC San Diego: Generating New Futures*

Mu, Dan

Presenter: *Distinction or Integration? Collectible Design and Shanzhai in China's Product Landscape*

Muhl, Beni

Presenter: *Rosalyn Drexler and the Flatness of Selfhood*

Muller, Alyse

Presenter: *Misrepresentations, Miniaturization, and Maulings: Reconsidering Staffordshire Potteries The Death of Monrow*

Müller, Ulrike

Session Chair: Presenting Contemporary Art in Museums, ca. 1880-1930: Temporary Exhibitions, Institutional Networks and Collecting

Munson, Kim

Presenter: *The Comics Legacy of Trina Robbins*

Murokh, Dina

Presenter: *The Life and Times of Charles Bird King's Black Hawk*

Murphy, Benjamin

Presenter: *The Religious Media Archaeology of Belkis Ayón*

Murphy, Lacy

Session Chair: Revivalism, Labor, and Discourses on Craft in Indigenous Arts of Southwest Asia and North Africa: Then and Now
 Presenter: *Crafting Colonial Identity at the General Exhibition of the Centenary of Algeria (1930)*

Murphy, Olivia

Presenter: *Shifting Sands/Shifting Identities: Anh-Thuý Nguyễn's "Thuy & Sand"*

Musacchio, Jacqueline Marie

Session Chair: Reproducing Renaissance Italy in the Long Nineteenth Century

Musto, Jeanne-Marie

Session Chair: Indigenous Manuscripts of Early Modern Latin America

Myers, Allison

Presenter: *Honest Labor: Chris Burden and the Bureaucratization of Artists in the University*

Mysak, Erin

Presenter: *Finding artisanal intelligence in yellow: Nepalese manuscripts and processed orpiment*

N**Nachabe Taan, Yasmine**

Presenter: *Teaching Graphic Design in/of the Arab World*

Nagel, Alexander

Session Chair: The Achaemenid Body: Making and Reflecting on Achaemenid Art and Fashion Histories

Nakamura, Kimihiko

Session Chair: The Warring Face of Realism: Cross-media Approach to Japanese War Art, 1931-1945
 Presenter: *Takai Teiji's "North Advancement" and the Manchuria-Mongolia Settlement Youth Volunteer Corps*

Nakonechna, Lada

Presenter: *Avant-garde and Pragmatism: Pedagogical Challenges at the Kyiv Art Institute*

Nam, Sangyoung

Presenter: *The Garden of Machinic Delights: José Val del Omar's Techno-Aesthetic Machinescape*

Naoui, Nozomi

Presenter: *Fashion Photography in Modern Japanese Department Store Magazines*

Navab, Nasseem

Presenter: *Refuge*

Nedham, Amanda

Presenter: *Excessive Traces*

Neely, Evan

Presenter: *Isaac Newton Phelps Stokes at the Intersection of Beaux-Arts Aesthetics and Progressive Reform*

Neginsky, Rosina

Session Chair: Symbolist Movement and the Bible

Nelson, Crystal

Presenter: *Given over to Repair: The Bodily Performances of Robbie McCauley, Nona Faustine, and Michaela Pilar Brown*

Nelson, Roger

Session Chair: Regionalist and Other Decolonizing Perspectives: Honoring TK Sabapathy's Ideas and Lifework

Newkirk, Brandee

Session Chair: The Power of Body Transformations

Newlands, Sarah

Presenter: *Academic Office Gallery: Fostering Creativity and Community through Artist Collaborations*

Ng, Sandy

Presenter: *Mediating Cross-cultural Dialogue in the Works of Eileen Gray (1878-1976) and Pan Yuliang (1895-1977)*

Nguyen, Melanie

Presenter: *Mother Molds: Art and Reproductive Health Justice in the Academic Museum*

Nicholson, Benjamin

Session Chair: System Failure: How to Survive and Thrive in Today's Art and Design Higher Education

Nishanova, Bermet

Presenter: *Making Threads: Medieval Fibers from Islamic Central Asia, Iran, and India (c. 9th- mid-13th Centuries)*

Noel de Tilly, Ariane

Presenter: *Intertwining Outer and Inner Worlds: The Visual Letters of Chantal Akerman and Fiona Tan*

Norcross, Anne

Presenter: *Experimental approaches to engaging undergraduate students in research*

Normoyle, Cat

Session Discussant: Design Incubation Colloquium 11.2: Recent Research in Communication Design

Noth, Juliane

Session Discussant: Encounters with Medium: Art, Travel, and Identity Formations in Twentieth-Century China
 Presenter: *Shi Lu's Invention of a Socialist Northern Landscape Mode*

Nouril, Ksenia

Session Discussant: Exhibiting Eastern Europe: 'New' Art of the Old Continent
 Session Chair: The Art Students League: 150 Years of "American" Art

Novelo, Miguel

Session Chair: Automation, Authorship, and Authenticity: What does Art Have to Say about AI?

Nussbaum, Rosa

Presenter: *The Bathing of the Sphinx*

O**O'Kane, Bernard**

Presenter: *The Porosity of Mongol Borders: Contributions of the Ilkhanids, Golden Horde and Chaghtayids to the Development of Tilework.*

O'Malley, Michael

Presenter: *Toward an Expanded Classroom: how students come to know their space through creativity*

O'Neal, Halle

Session Discussant: (Re)making Sacred Matter: Recycling and Repurposing in the Material Lives of Icons
 Session Chair: The Urgency and Challenges of Academic Freedom, hosted by The Art Bulletin
 Presenter: *Reanimating the Inert: Digitising Haptics and Mourning in Japanese Buddhist Handscrolls*

O'Neill, Cynthia

Presenter: *Plants and Persons out of Place: Eco-Crip Theory and the Ugly Lawn*

Obniski, Monica

Presenter: *Past, Present, and Future: Public Art in Atlanta*

Ogata, Amy

Presenter: *Applied Art, Decoration and Design in the Nineteenth Century*

Oh, Hyeongjin

Session Chair: Towards a "Pacific Turn" in American Art History
 Presenter: *Vortices: Reading Fish Story from the Engine Room to the Deck of Cargo Ship*

Oing, Michelle

Session Chair: The Visual Culture of Festivals in Germany, Scandinavia, and Central Europe

Okin, Mary

Session Chair: The "Work" of Art in American Culture from the New Deal to Now
 Presenter: *Formalism in Informal Spaces: Wayne Thiebaud at the California State Fair*

Olfat, Faraz

Session Chair: Neoclassicism in the Extended Field
 Presenter: *The National Bavarian Museum: Historicity and the Politics of Nationhood*

Olmsted, Jennifer

Presenter: *Looted Northern European Collections and the Transformation of French Portraiture*

Olson, Christine

Presenter: *Ornament and the Epistemologies of Victorian Graphic Design*

Olson, Mark

Session Chair: Digital Methods for Difficult Hidden Art Histories
 Presenter: *Hidden Histories of the Holocaust: "Guided Modeling" as a Critical Digital Humanities Method*

Olszewski, Christopher

Presenter: *Integrating Film and Television Research in Art and Design Curriculum*

Olynyk, Patricia

Presenter: *The Art of Medicine: Probing the Landscape Beneath the Skin*

Orrghen, Anna

Presenter: *BOB and the Moderna Museet collection: A case study on the challenges of AI art and contemporary museum practices in Sweden*

Ortiz de Zarate, Guillermo

Session Chair: Exploring Research Methods in Art Appraisal: Techniques and Case Studies

Orzulak, Jessica

Session Chair: The Power of Body Transformations

Oslé, Emma

Presenter: *Madre Tierra Press: A Chicana Collaboration*

Ostergaard, Tyler

Presenter: *Student Perception of Value and Engagement with Theory*

Oyler, Elizabeth

Presenter: *The Genpei War's Apparitional Spaces in Tsukioka Kōgyo's Nōgaku hyakuban (One Hundred Noh Plays)*

Ozludil, Burcak

Presenter: *History in Extended Reality (XR): Encountering Hidden Worlds of Nineteenth-Century Rome and Istanbul*

Ö**Öztürk, Onur**

Presenter: *Re-contextualizing Gender Violence Panels of Sebasteion at Aphrodisias*

P**Pachner, Joan**

Session Chair: Los Angeles during World War II: Art at the Margins
 Presenter: *Tony Smith and the Hollyhock House Circle 1943-45*

Paglen, Trevor

Presenter: *Trevor Paglen, panelist*

Pahapill, Leigh-Ann

Session Chair: Critical AI Literacy in Art and Design Education and Practice

Paine, Morgan T.

Session Workshop Leader: Images made by Post-Secondary Teachers of Painting

Paloma, Libby

Session Chair: Crip Time: Disabled Spacemaking in the Work of Queercrip Artists
 Presenter: *Crip Publishing Manifestx: Crippling Journal Editing*

Paluch, Alessa

Presenter: *Serving Democracy in East Germany – A Public Art Student Project*

Pan, An-Yi

Session Chair: The Form of Immortality: Painting and Calligraphy in Fifteenth- to Eighteenth-Century China

Pardo Gaviria, Paulina

Session Chair: Indigenous Art Exhibitions In and Out of the Americas. Are We Learning to Listen?

Pardo Porto, Cristina E.

Session Chair: Material Encounters with Nature, Memory, and Resistance
 Presenter: *The Contemporary Cyanotype: An Anti-Colonial History through Latin/x American Practices*

Park, Chansol

Presenter: *Painting for medicine: works created for the provisioning of healthcare in Ming China*

Park, Jeongho

Presenter: *Early Modern European Art in Korea and the Global Turn in the History of Art*

Park, Joon Hye

Presenter: *Subversive Strands: Hair as a Medium in Seung-taek Lee's Art*

Park, SaeHim

Session Chair: Censorship, Precarity, and Diversity: A Workshop

Park, Sung Ji

Session Chair: The Warring Face of Realism: Cross-media Approach to Japanese War Art, 1931-1945
 Presenter: *Propagandistic Realism: Lies Camouflaged by Photographic Truth in Japanese Reportage Photography*

Park, Yerang

Session Chair: Feminist Dialectics: Unheard Voices and Canonical Figures

Presenter: *Repetition, Gestures, and Double Negation: Luciano Fabro's Penelope and Carla Lonzi's Feminism in the 1970s*

Parker, Joel

Presenter: *Toward an Expanded Classroom: how students come to know their space through creativity*

Parsons, Sarah

Presenter: *Fantastical Capture: Surveillance and Light in 1840s America*

Pascual Carreras, Arnau

Presenter: *Outside Barcelona*

Pastorelli-Sosa, Angela

Presenter: *(Re)Mapping Social Histories in Sandy Rodriguez's Codex Rodriguez-Mondragón*

Patel, Vikram

Presenter: *Personhood of the Sun*

Patil, Vaishnavi

Presenter: *Inside an early sixteenth-century Indian Artists' Workshop: Technical and Scientific Insights into the Dispersed Bhagavata Purana*

Patrone, Gabrielle

Presenter: *Sacred Stitches: The Culture and Curation of Métis Beadwork*

Patterson, Jody

Session Chair: The "Work" of Art in American Culture from the New Deal to Now

Pauwels, Matthias

Presenter: *Overidentification, Decolonization and Genderqueer Activism in Contemporary South Africa*

Payer, Taylor Rose

Presenter: *Biskaabiiyang: An Indigenous Art Historical Method*

Peabody, Rebecca

Presenter: *Professional Methods as Curricular Intervention*

Pederson, Claudia

Session Chair: Enchantments, Transmissions, Infections: A Poetics of Knowledge by Latin American Women Artists

Pek, Ying Sze

Session Chair: Other Germans and German Others: Questions of Identity in Contemporary German Art

Presenter: *Exhibiting Migration in 2020s Germany*

Pekarek, Juan Pablo

Session Chair: Building the Belle Époque

Presenter: *Maison Carlhian in Buenos Aires. Decorating and building hôtels particuliers in the global Belle Époque.*

Pennamon, Tiffany

Presenter: *"Where There is No Vision, the People Perish": A Baldwinian Approach to Black Artistic Love and Liberation*

Percival, Melissa

Presenter: *Layers of Collaboration: The Making of toiles de Jouy*

Perez Armenta, Erika

Presenter: *Volunteer and social service programs in the art museum as an educational space for its participants*

Perkov, Kayleigh

Presenter: *Putting the Techné in Information Tech: Craft and Pedagogy at the Dawn of Personal Technology*

Perry, Ana

Presenter: *Transformative Possibilities of Sensory Investigations: Raphael Montañez Ortiz's Immersive Events in 1967*

Peterson, Laurel

Session Chair: New Directions in British Art and Architectural History

Pezalla-Granlund, Margaret

Session Chair: After: Re-imagining, Reinvigorating, and Resetting the Academic Art Gallery After, and Beyond

Phillips, Natalie

Presenter: *"Life is Short...Praise the Groundhog!": Groundhog Day as Modern Spiritual Tradition*

Picard, Caroline

Presenter: *The Mountain and the Mandala: Paul Pfeiffer's Fragment of a Crucifixion (After Francis Bacon) and the Chakrasamvara Mandala*

Pietrasik, Agata

Presenter: *Round Table Participant 2*

Pigza, Jessica

Session Chair: ARTS + ARCHIVES TEACHING PARTNERSHIPS: FOSTERING ARTS STUDENTS' TRANSFORMATIVE USES OF SPECIAL COLLECTIONS AND ARCHIVES

Session Discussant: ARTS + ARCHIVES TEACHING PARTNERSHIPS: FOSTERING ARTS STUDENTS' TRANSFORMATIVE USES OF SPECIAL COLLECTIONS AND ARCHIVES

Presenter: *Chair Remarks*

Pinder, Kymberly

Presenter: *Roundtable Participant Kymberly Pinder*

Piola, Erika

Presenter: *Only Between Times: Gender, Satire, and the Postcard of the Early 20th-Century*

Pitts, Philippa

Presenter: *Drugs, Dyes, and Delicacies: An Expansive Disability Studies Approach to Raphaele Peale's Still Life Paintings*

Placzek, Bailey

Presenter: *What is a "Critical Response": Recasting Authority in Museum Cataloguing Practice*

Plascencia, O. Gustavo

Session Chair: Designated Assembly Points: Connecting the Dots in Art Administration

Platt, Joanna

Presenter: *Printmaking as Labor: Images of Industry from the WPA-Sponsored Fine Print Workshop in Philadelphia*

Poe, Alison

Session Chair: Reading Bodies of Information: Inventive Feminist Approaches to Women Artists in the Archive

Poggio, Natacha

Presenter: *The Bayou at y.our Doorstep: Integrating Environmental Education in Graphic Design*

Pollman, Sarah

Presenter: *Archive, Image, Asylum: contemporary installation art in former psychiatric hospitals*

Pontés, Júlia

Presenter: *Lúcia*

Porsella, Madeline

Presenter: *Deformed Milieus: Symbolism in Architecture and the Nineteenth-Century Aquarium*

Post, Stephanie

Presenter: *Panelist - Senior Digital Asset Specialist, Digital Asset Management*

Powell, Richard

Presenter: *The Bronze Thrill*

Pozek, Nick

Session Discussant: Navigating the changing terrain of fair use in the digital world

Praepipatmongkol, Chanon

Presenter: *Fua Haribhitak: Abstraction and the Faded Copy*

Prejmerean, Vasile

Presenter: *The Young Degas and the Sea: A Dantean Journey*

Presutti, Kelly

Presenter: *Dredging the Waters of Empire in Paul Signac's Ports*

Prettyman, Michele

Presenter: *"There is a Mystery": Esotericism and Experimentation in the Film As Told to G/D Thyself*

Przybyło, Ela

Presenter: *Crip Publishing Manifestx: Crippling Journal Editing*

Pullen, Charlie

Presenter: *Public Sphere in Dystopia: a Game-based Youth Participatory Action Research*

Pulliam, Heather

Session Chair: Moving Pictures, Living Objects (International Center for Medieval Art sponsored session)

Punj, Nandita

Presenter: *Lost amidst color: Fields of flowers and the dispersed Tularam Bhagavata Purana*

Purcell, JoAnn

Presenter: *In the museum: Crip time as/is care time.*

Pushaw, Bart

Presenter: *Warm Hearts: Colonial Inuit Design and the Black Atlantic*

Pyun, Kyunghye

Presenter: *Clash of Curatorial Departments: Overcoming Essentialism of Styles*

Q**Qi, Zhenzhen**

Presenter: *Remystification and Demystification*

Quené, Saskia

Session Chair: Moving the Image: Medieval Diagrams and their Audiences
Presenter: *Measured Movements in the Musica Enchiriadis*

Querin, Camilla

Session Chair: Indigenous Art Exhibitions In and Out of the Americas. Are We Learning to Listen?

Quijon, Carlos Jr

Presenter: *Archipelagic Futurisms: Exhibition Case Studies for a Framework of Rethinking the World*

Quinn, Heather

Session Chair: Design Incubation Colloquium 11.2: Recent Research in Communication Design

R**R. Delgado, Fabiola**

Presenter: *Baggage/Luggage: Material and Symbolic Meanings in Displacement Experiences*

Racek, Sandra

Presenter: *Vertumnus as an Old Woman in Hendrick Goltzius's Vertumnus and Pomona (1613)*

Raengo, Alessandra

Session Chair: META+PHYSICS OF BLACK ARTMAKING

Raffini, Daniel

Presenter: *The transformative power of AI gaze in art-making: creativity and ethics*

Raghubir, Ashley

Session Chair: Afterlives
Presenter: *The Empire of Oil: Christopher Cozier's Entanglements series (2014-2015) and turbulence (2019-2021)*

Rahmani, Aviva

Session Chair: Law in Art and Art in Law: Charting a New Course for Society

Rahnama, Sara

Session Discussant: Revivalism, Labor, and Discourses on Craft in Indigenous Arts of Southwest Asia and North Africa: Then and Now

Raicovich, Laura

Presenter: *To Let the Art Do Its Job*

Rainer, Thomas

Presenter: *Spycraft – Medieval Books and the Magic Lantern: The Unfolding Revelation of Scripture in the Évangélique de la Sainte-Chapelle*

Ralske, Kurt

Presenter: *Not Touched By Human Hands: The Notion of AI Sentience and the Power of Images*

Ralston, Sonia

Presenter: *Model Plants, Modelling and Memory*

Ramalho, Nayla

Presenter: *Denilson Baniwa's Nakoada: Ancestral Responsibility and the Modern Art Week*

Ramirez Bolivar, Juan Gabriel

Session Chair: Figuring the Individual/Figuring the Group: Transnational Exchanges in Interwar Art
Presenter: *Indigenous or Spanish? The Mexican and Colombian Pavilions at the Ibero-American Exposition of Seville, 1929*

Ramírez Herrera, Juliana

Session Chair: Calling all art historians! The Isthmo-Colombian Area, the Amazon, and the Antilles in Ancient American Art
Presenter: *Astronauts in the Rainforest: How an Emberá Silver-Coin Necklace and pre-Conquest Metallurgy from the Colombia-Panama Borderlands Defy Colonial Gravity*

Ramljak, Suzanne

Session Chair: Moving Out: David Smith & The Outdoor Migration of Sculpture

Ramstad, Emmett

Presenter: *trans art beyond the figure*

Rappaport, Mat

Session Chair: AI in Art: Practices, Processes, Doubts, and Revelations

Rassi, Termeh

Session Chair: PST and Other Art/Sci Models for the Future

Rauch, Alan

Session Chair: Reconceptualizing Narrative and Representation in Figurines

Presenter: *The Figurinae of London: Images for the Million*

Rauch, Barbara

Presenter: *Feet, Face, Yellow Card*

Rawlinson, Mark

Presenter: *Dismantling New Topographics*

Rebeiz, Linda

Presenter: *AI's Unseen Borders: Crafting a Pluriverse Future*

Reddaway, Chloe

Presenter: *'Hermeneutics and Methodology in Theology and the Visual Arts': a new project at KCL*

Rees, Nathan

Presenter: *The Power of Mormon Kitsch*

Reeves, Chris

Presenter: *Binding queer networks: FILE magazine and the mass produced artist book*

Reifenstein, Tilo

Session Chair: The Form of the Thing: Word and Image and the Scholar

Presenter: *Beyond emplotment: narrative between meta-history and material*

Reizman, Renée

Presenter: *Healing through Grief: processing hardship and uniting communities through social practice art*

Reyes, JoAnna

Presenter: *Una Confusión Devota: Soundscapes of Late Colonial Mexican Festivals*

Rhee, Jieun

Session Chair: Who's Afraid of Western Art History? : Pedagogy, Research and Impact of Western Art History in Korea

Richman, Elise

Presenter: *Ecology of Color*

Richman-Abdou, Kelly

Presenter: *An "Awful Dichotomy" on Display: Curatorial Approaches to Alice Neel's Controversial 'Degenerate Madonna'*

Richter, Sarah

Session Chair: God Loves Kitsch!

Riley, Caroline

Presenter: *Consumerism, Copyright, and Publicity in Thérèse Bonney's 1920s Fashion Photographs*

Ringelberg, Kirstin

Session Discussant: Art History and the Apocalypse

Presenter: *If a trans person walks into the room and no one recognizes them, do they make a sound?*

Presenter: *No Art History on a Dead Planet*

Ripley, Amanda

Presenter: *Strike the Museum: Collective Imaginaries on the Picket Lines of US Art Museums*

Ripolles, Carmen

Session Chair: Art History and the Apocalypse

Ritchie, Matthew

Presenter: *Matthew Ritchie, Panelist*

Rivas, Carlos

Session Chair: The State of Central American Art History: Foundations and Future Directions

Presenter: *The Development of Early Modern Central American Art History*

Robbins, Christiane

Presenter: *Thresholds of the Frontier*

Robbins, Isabella

Presenter: *Relational Art Histories of K'é and California: Emma Robbins*

Robbins, Nicholas

Session Chair: Art History's Graphic Intelligence

Roberts, Vivienne

Presenter: *Re-evaluating Madge Gill: Mediumship, Music, Marconi and Mars*

Robertson, Kirsty

Presenter: *Shadow Collection: Chemical Intimacies in the Museum and Archive*

Robinson, Peter

Presenter: *Making Space: Centering our Youth and the Future of Black Liberation Care Practices*

Robles, Constanza

Session Chair: Identities at Play: Branding, Politics, and Ecology in 20th-Century Visual Culture and Contemporary Art

Presenter: *Transnational Alliances and Visual Culture at the Ibero-American Exposition (1929)*

Rochard, L

Presenter: *Cleanliness, dirtiness, and the contamination of genders in Seventeenth-century Netherlandish Painting*

Rochester, Katherine

Presenter: *Off-Color: Towards a Color Theory of Ecologies in Crisis*

Rockwell, Alethea

Presenter: *Panelist - Keith Haring Director of Education and Public Engagement*

Rodríguez, Gretel

Presenter: *Figural and Aniconic Representations of Mother Goddesses in Roman Gaul*

Rogers, Fiona

Presenter: *Photo Femmage: A History of Women and Feminist Photo Montage*

Rogers, LaRissa

Presenter: *Monstrous Beauty: A Placeholder for Someone without a Place*

Rom, Ariel

Presenter: *Lynette Yiadom Boakye's Monochrome Paintings as a Mode of Camouflage*

Root, Rae

Presenter: *Lines and Loopholes*

Rosenberg, Max

Presenter: *Plants, Screens, and Rückenfiguren: Sharing and Withholding in the Work of Njideka Akunyili Crosby*

Rosenthal, Sarah

Presenter: *Bathing Outside: Sex Workers, Cleanliness, and the Extra-Urban World in Sixteenth-Century Germanic Art*

Rotzel, Meg

Presenter: *The Legibility of the Stack, Artists in the Archive*

Rounthwaite, Adair

Presenter: *The Information Aesthetic of the January 6th Riots*

Rousseau, Valérie

Presenter: *Democratic Therapy*

Rowe, Allison

Presenter: *Throwing Stones at the Wall: Pedagogical Art and the Immutability of Museums*

Roxburgh, David

Session Chair: Rethinking the Central Asian Arts: New Perspectives on the Geography of Art
 Session Discussant: Rethinking the Central Asian Arts: New Perspectives on the Geography of Art

Rozenberg, Lauren

Presenter: *The Forensic Magdalene: Bones, Technology and the Importance of Representation*

Rudinsky, Joyce

Session Chair: Art Beyond Games: Critical and Creative Approaches in New Media Art

Rudy, Kathryn

Session Chair: Moving Pictures, Living Objects (International Center for Medieval Art sponsored session)

Rushfield, Rebecca

Session Chair: The Ongoing Life of Refuse in Art

Russell, Arthur

Session Workshop Leader: Forms of Friendship: An Educator's How-To For a Socially Engaged Classroom

Russo, Jillian

Presenter: *Women of the Whitney Biennials: A Cultural Overview*

Rüstem, Ünver

Presenter: *Rountable Participant Ünver Rüstem*

Ryner, Denise

Session Chair: Networks, Solidarities and Intersections: Representations of Black, African and Asian Historical and Contemporary Space

Ryor, Kathleen

Session Discussant: The Form of Immortality: Painting and Calligraphy in Fifteenth- to Eighteenth-Century China

Ryu, Soyoon

Presenter: *THE PLAY's Art and Borderland Ethics in Okinawa and Hokkaido*

S**Sadighian, David**

Session Chair: Building the Belle Époque

Salazar, Constanza

Session Chair: Walled Gardens and Wild Artists

Samudzi, Zoé

Presenter: *Roundtable discussion*

San Martin, Florencia

Session Chair: Curatorial Practices in Latin America: Challenges and Discourses in the Age of Global Neoliberalism

Sanematsu, Helen

Session Chair: Design for Health and Wellbeing: Innovative Approaches in Design Education and Practice
 Presenter: *Bringing Up Babies: From Education to Application in Service Design for Health and Hospitals*

Santamaria Montero, Leonardo

Presenter: *Historiography of 19th Century Central American Art: the Cases of Guatemala and Costa Rica*

Santner, Kathryn

Presenter: *Mrs. Freyer at home and abroad: Introducing America to colonial Peru*

Saqfahait, Yara

Presenter: *The Hereafter and the Future: Managing the Temporal Horizons of God's Property*

Sarjoughian, Azadeh

Presenter: *From Binarism to Dispersal Histories: Contemporary art from the Middle East*

Sas, Miryam

Session Chair: Strategies of Camouflage Among Women Artists of Diversity
 Presenter: *Blur/Haze/Emergence: Japanese Women Photographers of the 1960s-1970*

Satalof, Michael

Presenter: *Panelist - Archivist & Digital Preservation Specialist*

Saunders, Rachel

Session Chair: (Re)making Sacred Matter: Recycling and Repurposing in the Material Lives of Icons
 Presenter: *Birds, Flowers, and Buddhist Botany in Edo Japan*

Savig, Mary

Session Chair: State Fairs and American Art

Scalia, June

Presenter: *Back to the Drawing Board: González, Gego, and the Problem with "Drawing in Space"*

Scalissi, Nicole

Presenter: *'she walked in reverse': Forced Migration, Diaspora, and Indo-Caribbean Identities in Suchitra Mattai's installations*

Scarborough, Klare

Session Chair: Contemporary Black Abstraction: Confluence and Resonance

Schaal, Katia

Presenter: *Paulin Tasset (1839-1921), the main practitioner-reducer at the time of "medaillomania"*

Schaefer, Tatjana

Presenter: *Big Pages from the Heresies Collective – Transferring Feminist Journalism to an Exhibition Space*

Schlatter, Elizabeth

Session Chair: Ouch! The Artist's Body and How to Care for It Long Term
 Session Discussant: The Students and Emerging Professionals Committee's (SEPC) Guide To All Things CAA

Schmuki, Jeff

Presenter: *In the Trenches: PlantBot Genetics and the ArtLab*

Schnitzler, Carly

Session Workshop Leader: Forms of Friendship: An Educator's How-To For a Socially Engaged Classroom

Schoolman, Alexandra

Presenter: *Virginia Errázuriz and Alternative Solidarity Networks in Chile during the Pinochet Dictatorship*

Schreffler, Michael

Session Discussant: Natural Disasters and Artistic Innovation in Colonial Peru, 1650-1700

Schuld, Dawna

Presenter: *David Smith Takes to the Air*

Schultz, Alexandra

Presenter: *Claiming Space: Women Gathering Water in Modern Egypt (1895-1960)*

Schuster, Vanessa

Presenter: *Bodily Awareness: Skin as Surface, Trace and Memory*

Schwartz, Julia

Presenter: *Creating Community Through Discussion Groups*

Schwartz, Wylie

Presenter: *Fostering Undergraduate Scholarship Through Curator Colab*

Schwarz, Martin

Presenter: *Late Gothic Micro-Architectural Designs: 3D-Modeling the Basel Goldschmiederrisse*

Sciortino, Cassandra

Presenter: *The Symbolists & Saint Francis: Charles-Marie Dulac's Cantique des créatures*

Scott, Amy

Session Chair: Future Imaginaries: Indigenous Art, Fashion, Technology
Presenter: *New Terrain: Indigenous Futurism and the City of Angels*

Scott, Braden

Presenter: *When Dacians became Persians in Renaissance Architectural Theory*

Scott, Lily

Presenter: *Precarious Encounters & Connoting Ephemerality of Trauma: An Examination of Interwar Sapphic Portraiture*

Secklehner, Julia

Presenter: *In Women's Hands: The Gendered Dimensions of Social Photography in Central Europe, 1928-1948*

Selen, Eser

Presenter: *The Everse Encounter: Embodiment and Agency in New Media Art*

Sen, Priyanka

Presenter: *Zarina Bhimji and the Afterlives of Decolonial Aesthetics*

Serrano Ortiz de Solórzano, Blanca

Session Chair: ISLAA-ALAA Encuentro for Latin American and Latinx Art at CAA

Serrato Doyen, Kale

Presenter: *Whose Topographics? Race and Postwar Landscape Photography*

Sessions, Lee

Presenter: *Stitching together: Extended possibilities of collectivity in Chilean Arpilleras*

Sexton, Kim

Presenter: *Skin: The Renaissance Library and the Archive of the Animal*

Shanahan, Maureen

Presenter: *Algerian Weaving Workshops and Women's Agency under French Colonialism*

Shankar, Louis

Presenter: *Dream-Work as Form: Looking at Looking for Langston*

Shanks, Gwyneth

Session Chair: "Foreigners Everywhere!": Art and Refugee Identification

Shapiro, Samuel

Presenter: *Inciting Confrontations: Following Institutional Critique Behind the Museum Wall*

Sharma, Yuthika

Presenter: *Civilizing 'Kala': Blackness, Servitude, and the Colonial Subject in Company-era Painting*

Sharp, Jane

Session Discussant: Explosive Objects: Material Histories of Violence in Europe, 1920s-1940s

Sharpe, William

Presenter: *The Masked Nude: Anonymity, Eroticism, and Artistic Instruction*

Shaskevich, Helena

Presenter: *Computational Love Letters during the AIDS Crisis*

Shea, Laura

Session Chair: God Loves Kitsch!

Sheeler, Alexandra

Session Chair: Relearning to Learn: New Methods for Art History
Presenter: *Early Modern Simulacra in Heavy Metal Visual Culture*

Shelby, Karen

Presenter: *From Africa Palace to AfricaMuseum: Decolonializing King Leopold's Museum of the Congo Free State*
Presenter: *New Eyes on Alice Austen*

Shell, Hanna

Session Discussant: Strategies of Camouflage Among Women Artists of Diversity

Shen, Kuiyi

Session Chair: Alternative Approaches to Abstraction in Asia: Ecology, Science, and the Senses in Early Twentieth-Century Abstract Art
Session Discussant: The "Postsocialist Contemporary:" Passages in Modern-Contemporary Chinese Art

Shepherdson-Scott, Kari

Presenter: *"Truth" and Intermedia at the China Incident Holy War Exposition, 1938*

Sherman, Elisabeth

Session Chair: The Medical Gaze: Art, Corporeality, and Technology

Sherman, Levi

Session Chair: Dialogue and Artistry: Exploring the history, canon and critical reception of artist books

Shionoiri, Yayoi

Presenter: *Sustaining a Legacy: Modeling Creative Legal Structures for Artist Estates*

Shores, Elizabeth

Presenter: *Personhood of the Sun*

Shtromberg, Elena

Session Chair: Transgresoras: Mail Art and Messages

Shubert, Amanda

Presenter: *Arab Jews, British India, and the Family Archive*

Shulman, Anya

Presenter: *Reimagining Art History Education: Integrating Theory and Methodology into Introductory Art History Courses*

Shypula, Gabriella

Session Chair: Deliberately University Based: Marginalized Artists and the Growth of University Art Spaces

Presenter: *Alternative Routes: Faith Ringgold's Strategies of Exhibition and Performance at Universities in the 1970s and 1980s*

Sigmon, Kari

Session Chair: Innovation by Necessity: Problem Solvers and Museum Futures

Silveri, Rachel

Session Chair: Sapphic Modernism

Silverman, Julia

Session Chair: Abstract Art and Colonial Systems
Presenter: *Localized Abstraction: Fred Kabotie, Formalist Pedagogy, and Visual Ethics at Hopitutskwa*

Silverthorne, Diane

Session Discussant: Anna Mahler, Sculptor: Vienna, London, Los Angeles, and Spoleto.
Presenter: *Anna Mahler, Artist in Exile – the Vienna-London years and beyond*

Simmons, Ansley

Presenter: *Brushstrokes and Bytes: Evolving a Limited AI Use Policy in Art Appreciation Courses*

Simmons, Frederica

Session Chair: The Students and Emerging Professionals Committee's (SEPC) Guide To All Things CAA

Simpson, Annie

Presenter: *How to Measure / Cutting Short*

Singeisen, Scott

Session Chair: Legacies & Learning: Connecting Art, History, and Education
Presenter: *The Influence of Fine Art Printmaking on Architectural Image Production and Reception*

Sinnott, Gretchen

Presenter: *Generative AI Goes to the Historical Society*

Siqueira, Vera

Presenter: *Other Ecology, Ecology of Otherness: Nature and Culture in Roberto Burle Marx's Work*

Sklarz, Cambra

Presenter: *Materials as Collaboration in Eighteenth- and Nineteenth-Century Philadelphia*

Skrebowski, Luke

Presenter: *The Im/practicability of Institutional Critique*

Skurvida, Sandra

Presenter: *The Discursive Anarchy of John Cage's "Writings through the Essay: 'On the Duty of Civil Disobedience'"*

Slobogin, Christine

Session Chair: Anonymity in Art and Visual Culture

Small, Samantha

Presenter: *Stroking the Whispering Reeds: Ovid and "Heroic Rape" in German Neo-Idealist Art*

Smiley, Michelle

Presenter: *"UFOs are not Photogenic": The Phenomenon, Photography, and Testimony*

Smith, Cassandra

Presenter: *Skeena Reece, "Access Granted": Hair as Site of Identity, Violence, Kinship, and Power*

Smith, Dianne

Session Discussant: Artists' Roundtable hosted by Services to Artists Committee

Smith, Hampton

Presenter: *Striking the Common Wind: Ornamental Wrought Iron and the Craft Commons in New Orleans*

Smith, Terence

Presenter: *MANIFOLD DIFFERENTIATION: THE CONTEMPORARY TURN*

Smith-Holmes, Maxwell

Presenter: *Counterfeit Architecture: Trust and the Architecture of Banking, Philadelphia, Kansas City, Salem, 1876-1891*

Snider, Stefanie

Presenter: *(Dis)Embodied Activism, Precarity, and Contemporary Visual Art*

Snodgrass, Susan

Session Workshop Leader: Preparing an Essay for Publication: Strategies for Writing from and about the Global Margins

Soboleva, Ksenia

Presenter: *My Dear Lover: Sharon Hayes' Letters to an Unnamed You*

Sohn, Sooyun

Presenter: *Studying and Teaching Western Early Modern Art History in Korea*

Sosova, Jitka

Presenter: *The Bodies of the Brighter Future: Alena Čermáková, the Army Art Studio and the Representation of Human Form*

Souza, Omari

Presenter: *Reimagining Black Cultural Narratives Through Design: A Study of Album Covers as Tools for Empowerment*
Presenter: *Visualizing Ancestry Through Restorative Design*

Speaks, Elyse

Presenter: *Weaving the Cultural Character of Landscape*

Sperling, Jutta

Presenter: *The Ethiopian Story of Mary and Its Pictorial Program*

Spieker, Sven

Session Workshop Leader: Preparing an Essay for Publication: Strategies for Writing from and about the Global Margins

Splan, Laura

Presenter: *The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: Panel #2: EXPERIENCE*

Spring, Jeffrey

Session Chair: Heavy Metal: The Artist and the Foundry

Springer, Allison

Presenter: *Hidden Identities: Analyzing the Transatlantic Influence in American Visual Culture by Examining Subversive Forms of Representation of Women of Color in the Nineteenth Century*

Stafylakis, Konstantinos

Presenter: *Who's Afraid of Post-Internet Mimicry?*

Staniszewski, Mary Anne

Session Discussant: Alternative Alternatives: Sites and Audiences Outside the Artworld Today

Stapleton, Judith

Presenter: *Staging Irishness: Stereotype, Identity, and Generative AI*

Stark, Douglas

Presenter: *Simema: Radical Passivity in Freudenheim's Schema*

Starling, Halo

Session Chair: Crip Time: Disabled Spacemaking in the Work of Queercrip Artists
Presenter: *Crip Publishing Manifestx: Crippling Journal Editing*

Starr, Meredith

Session Chair: Next Now: Studio Art Foundations

Stefanescu, Laura

Presenter: *Transmedial Migrations in Neri di Bicci's Laboratory of Materiality*

Steinhardt, Nancy

Presenter: *The Türk Building Plan*

Stephenson, Matthew

Session Chair: Anna Mahler, Sculptor: Vienna, London, Los Angeles, and Spoleto.

Sterckx, Marjan

Session Chair: Sculpture as a Collective Practice in the Long Nineteenth Century

Sterling, Amber

Session Workshop Leader: Sustainability Impact: Constructing Practices for Exhibitions & Institutions

Sterling, Kyéra

Presenter: *Image Enhancement & Neon Green: Seeing & Sensing in Sandra Mujinga's "Spectral Keepers"*

Stern, Arden

Presenter: *Lessons from Labor Organizing in Design Education*

Stern, Nathaniel

Presenter: *Re-Membering Digital Tools*

Stevanin, Federica

Presenter: *The Right to be 'Opaque': Camouflage in the Work of Joiri Minaya*

Stewart, David

Presenter: *The Feminist Art of Agnes Millen Richmond and her Radical Students: Unbowed in the Early Twentieth Century*

Stielau, Allison

Session Chair: Art History's Graphic Intelligence
Session Chair: The Medieval lives! Technologies and Medieval Afterlives
Presenter: *Beuys vs. the Goldsmiths: Symbolic Meltdown and the Kronschmelzaktion (1982)*

Stielau, Anna

Session Chair: Complicating Perception: Re-Coding Time and Place
Presenter: *Here But Not Yet Now: Re-Presenting the Khoisan in South African Art and Visual Activism*

Stinebring, Anna-Claire

Session Chair: Gender, Sexuality, and Non-Pristine Nature in Northern European Art and Material Culture, ca. 1350-1750

Stirner, Simone

Presenter: *Threading Archives: Philipp Guffler's Textile Speculations*

Stoeckley, Clark

Session Chair: Artistic Responses to the Ongoing Genocide in Gaza: Exploring Palestinian Narratives and Resistance through Visual Culture

Stolte, Sarah

Session Chair: Visions of Ancestral Spirits
Presenter: *John Hitchcock Blanket Songs*

Strang, Susannah

Presenter: *Embodied Engagement as a Response to Global Crises*

Stratford, Linda

Session Chair: Reconsidering Religion in Modern and Contemporary Art: Methods and Approaches

Stricklin, Krystle

Presenter: *That Which is Boundless: The Legacy of Apeiron Workshops, 1970 – 1982*

Stuber, Tracy

Presenter: *Stephen Shore's Landscape Photography of Everything*

Sturtevant, Elliott

Session Chair: Architecture in Repetition

Stylianou, Elena

Session Chair: Ecologies of Islands in Contemporary Art: From Colonial Imaginaries to International Flows
Presenter: *Liquid Landscapes: Water tunnels, flamingos, and radar sounds in contemporary art from Cyprus*

Su, Stephanie

Presenter: *The Sublime of White: Abstraction, Tactility and Cultural Imagination in 1930s Japanese Art*

Sudhalter, Adrian

Session Discussant: Magical Realism, New Objectivity, and the Return of Representation: A Reevaluation

Sullivan, John

Presenter: *Adaptive Designs: Neoclassicism and the Cathedral of Nueva Guatemala, 1773–1800*

Sullivan, Megan

Session Workshop Leader: Preparing an Essay for Publication: Strategies for Writing from and about the Global Margins

Sun, Huiyao Niuniu

Presenter: *Beyond the White Cube: Self-Organized Exhibitions in Beijing's Artist Communities*

Sun, Lucien

Session Chair: Connecting In and Out: Toward "Regional" Approaches to Chinese Art
Presenter: *General, Deity, and Filial Son: The Print of Guan Yu from Khara-Khoto and a Visual Schema in Southern Shanxi under the Mongol Rule*

Sunset, Michelle

Presenter: *Navigating Censorship and Precarity at the University of Wyoming Art Museum*

Svetvilas, Chanika

Presenter: *From Data to Art: Exploring Mental Health Narratives of Asian Americans through Disaggregated Data and 3D Printed Sculptures*

Swartz, Anne

Presenter: *Unnatural Sciences: An Overview*

Sweeney, Ginia

Presenter: *Titles and Public-Facing Narratives*

Swenson, Kirsten

Presenter: *New Topographics: Oil and the End of Landscape Photography*

Syperek, Pandora

Session Chair: *Sea Inside: Oceanic Interiority in Art and Visual Culture*

Szabo, Victoria

Session Chair: *Art Beyond Games: Critical and Creative Approaches in New Media Art*
Session Chair: *Digital Methods for Difficult Hidden Art Histories*
Presenter: *Virtual Black Charlotte: Reconstructing and Representing the Lost Brooklyn Community*

Szupinska, Joanna

Session Chair: *The Photographer and the Folk: Picturing the Rural Subject in 20th-century Central Europe*
Presenter: *Zofia Rydet, Pseudo-Ethnographer*

T**Tajpour, Azadeh**

Presenter: *Embodied Resistance: Bodily Autonomy in Iran Augmented by Art and Technology*

Takehara, Tamane

Presenter: *The Politics of Labor, Performativity, and Cure in Hi Red Center's Cleaning Event*

Talasek, John

Session Discussant: *PST and Other Art/Sci Models for the Future*

Tamassoki, Zeinab

Presenter: *Everyday Expectations: How a Sufi Revolutionist, Unknown Artists, and the King Envisioned a Modern House in Nineteenth-Century Iran*

Taminiaux, Pierre

Presenter: *Eighteen times: from the river to the river*

Tan, Chang

Presenter: *Media-topias: Staged Photography and Everyday Drama of the Chinese Contemporary*

Tan, Margaret

Presenter: *Maintenance Work in a Smart Nation*

Tang, Rachel

Presenter: *Weaving Without: Arizona Swayney Blakenship's Basket Weaving as Pedagogy*

Tanga, Martina

Session Chair: *Innovation by Necessity: Problem Solvers and Museum Futures*

Tani, Ellen

Presenter: *"Artists read theory as poetry": the Charles Gaines curriculum*

Tanner, Peter

Session Chair: *Dialogue and Artistry: Exploring the history, canon and critical reception of artist books*

Taroutina, Maria

Presenter: *Roundtable Participant from; The Art Bulletin Editorial Board*

Tarrence, Maria

Presenter: *Exploring Research Methods in Art Appraisal: Techniques and Case Studies*

Tartakov, Gary Michael

Presenter: *What We Call Race in the United States, We Call Caste in India*

Tarver, Gina

Session Chair: *Open Session for Emerging Scholars*

Tashakori, Fatemeh

Presenter: *Visual Convergence: European Prints and Everyday Modernity in 19th-Century Qajar Architecture*

Tell, Connie

Session Chair: *Goddess Redux: Feminism and Spirituality in Contemporary Art*
Presenter: *Welcome*

Thomas, Alexandra

Presenter: *Looking for Mildred: Black Queer Feminist Errantry in Mildred Thompson's Abstraction*

Thomas, George

Presenter: *Medieval Spanish Literature in the Illustrations of Guaman Poma's New Chronicle*

Thomas, Mary

Session Chair: *Activating "X as Intersection: Writing on Latinx Art"*

Thomas, Nekita

Presenter: *Black Space Protocols: On Anti-Racist Placemaking and Urban Design*

Thompson, Amanda

Session Chair: *Borderlands: Craft Between Cultures*
Presenter: *Appropriations '76: Florida Native Seminole Patchwork in the Quilting World*

Thompson, Ashley

Presenter: *Decoloniality and the Purchase of the Pre-Modern: Views from Southeast Asian Fields*

Thompson, Drew

Presenter: *Round Table Participant*

Thompson, Richard

Session Chair: *Incomplete Presence: Authenticity and Accuracy in Immersive Spaces*
Presenter: *Building Empathy with Authentic Movement: Mitigating the Uncanny Valley Phenomenon in Digital Humans*

Thompto, Chelsea

Presenter: *The Fog of (Gender) War*

Thomson, Hannah

Session Chair: *Divine Senses: Exploring Sensorial Experiences in Religious Contexts throughout the Premodern Iberian World*

Thornton-Cronin, Lesley

Presenter: *Naawsidoong Mino Nawendiwin (Building Good Relationships): Decolonized Teaching and Student Mental Health*

Thulin, Stephanie R.

Presenter: *Using Your Community to Bridge the Gap in Experiential Learning Opportunities*

Tian, Michelle

Presenter: *Beyond the Inner Chamber?: The Making of Female "Elegant Gathering" Paintings in Late Eighteenth-century China*

Tifentale, Alise

Session Chair: Camera-derie: Collaborative, Communal, and Collective Practices in Photography

Tillenburg, Gabrielle

Presenter: *Seeing Sovereignty in Snow, Salt, and Mold: Ecological Material and the Colonial Condition in the work of Sofia Gallisa Muriente*

Ting-Yi, Rose

Presenter: *Did Premodern China Have Great Women Artists?*

Tirado, Zoë

Presenter: *New Eyes on Alice Austen*

Tison, Helene

Presenter: *Drawing back: Barbara Brandon-Croft's Where I'm Coming From (1991-2005)*

Toh, Charmaine

Presenter: *The Re-Arrival of Modern Photography in Singapore*

Tom, Anna

Presenter: *Beyond the Gridlines: Possibilities of Loss and Reconstruction in the Abstract Works of Nasreen Mohamedi, Zarina Hashmi, Gargi Raina and Purvai Rai*

Topcik, Heather

Session Discussant: ARTS + ARCHIVES TEACHING PARTNERSHIPS: FOSTERING ARTS STUDENTS' TRANSFORMATIVE USES OF SPECIAL COLLECTIONS AND ARCHIVES

Toppins, Augusta

Presenter: *Design History Data: A Snapshot of US-based Undergraduate Programs*

Torgesen, Cindy

Presenter: *Socialist Futurism(s): Utopian Art and Design in Yugoslavia and Beyond*

Torrell, Ehryn

Session Chair: Collective Work: Funding and Collaborating on International Projects and Research
Session Chair: The Students and Emerging Professionals Committee's (SEPC) Guide To All Things CAA
Presenter: *Tearing up Vogue and Mining the Detritus*

Toschi, Caterina

Session Chair: WOMEN ART DEALERS AND COLLECTORS PROMOTING NON-WESTERN ARTS: THE CASE OF PRE-COLUMBIAN ART AND THE INDIGENOUS ARTS OF NORTH AMERICA

Tosheva, Dilrabo

Session Chair: Rethinking the Central Asian Arts: New Perspectives on the Geography of Art
Presenter: *"Qarakhanid Architecture and the Islamization of Silk Road Sites: A Case Study of the Shah Fazil Mausoleum"*

Toteva, Maia

Session Chair: Who's Afraid of Mimicry? Contemporary Art and New Culture Wars

Trafficante, Ilaria

Session Chair: *Collecting Her Thoughts: Women Art Collectors Across Time*

Trentinella, Rose

Session Workshop Leader: *Decoding the Discipline of Art History - What is it, How to do it, & Why it matters*

Trevino, Teresa

Presenter: *Editorial Infographics: Bridging the Gap Between Complexity and Clarity in Design Education*

Triburgo, Lorenzo

Presenter: *The Greatest Love: Vocal Confluence as Trans*Queer Resilience*

Trischler, D.J.

Presenter: *Designing Inclusive Engagements in Neighborhood Design Projects*

Trizoli, Talita

Presenter: *The American Women Artists Project and the Silent Reception of Feminist Art in Brazil*

Troeller, Jordan

Presenter: *Gaia's Return: Earth-Goddesses in Contemporary Indigenous Eco-Activism*

Trudell-Mills, Daisy

Presenter: *the birds above me place me on the ground: The Power of Wonder*

True, Megan

Session Chair: *Women Artists and the Politics of Neoclassicism*

Trusty, Rachel

Presenter: *"Let the Little Children Come to Me: Sweet Kitsch and Spreading the Gospel"*

Truxes, Anna

Session Chair: *Expanding Scholarship in Collections of Asian American Artists*

Tsatsos, Irene

Presenter: *From the Ground Up: Nurturing Diversity in Hostile Environments*

Tsultem, Uranchimeg

Session Chair: *Art, Its History and Institutions in the Age of AI and Posthumanism*

Tucker, Colin

Presenter: *Art History and the Apocalypse: A Decolonial Re-Orientiation*

Tucker, Daniel

Presenter: *Reflections On Teaching Social Engagement*

Tunali, Tijen

Session Chair: *Environmental Culture, Urban Artscape and the Urbanocene*
Presenter: *Posthumanism and the Digitalisation of Urban Eco-Arts*

Tunić, Srđan

Presenter: *"Block Bro Brooklyn Bro": The Origin Myth of New York Graffiti and Transnational Hybrids--case study of Belgrade, Serbia*

Turner, Helen

Presenter: *Voice as Resistance to Abjection*
Presenter: *Voice as Resistance to Abjection*

Turner, Madeline

Session Chair: Drawn to Earth: Contemporary Drawing and Environment in the Americas
 Presenter: *Communication Breakdown: Yani Pecanins' Un viaje en Zeppelin (1988)*

Turner, Rebecca

Presenter: *Through the Hemlock Trees: Diegesis and Disclosure in Moyra Davey's Video Works*

U**Uhlig, Sue**

Session Chair: Methods of Engagement in Undergraduate Research
 Presenter: *Sliman Mansour and Beautiful Acts of Resistance*

Uhm, Eunice

Session Chair: The Politics of the Archive: Reimagining the Histories of the Asian Diaspora

Um, Nancy

Session Chair: Collaboration as Art Historical Practice

Unger, Gwen

Presenter: *Belkis Ayón and Sikán: Black Sirens*

Unruh, Holly

Session Workshop Leader: Funding Your Arts Research and Practice: Strategic Proposal Writing for Grant and Fellowship Funding

Urano Frajndlich, Rafael

Presenter: *Paul Lester Wiener, an architect tied to the American Government and his connections and projects in Brazil (1938-1945)*

Uzmay, Asya

Presenter: *Repeating for the Extreme: Bayer Post-disaster Houses and their Users*

V**Valdivia Bruch, Katerina**

Presenter: *An Inclusive Gesture: Peru's Participation in the 14th Bienal de São Paulo (1977)*

Valencia-Turco, Gema

Presenter: *Poetry vs Poetic Expressivity: "Cantares Mexicanos" and the Alterity of Artistic Production*

Valiant, Seonaid

Presenter: *The Diving God Ceremony: Zelia Nuttall's revival of an Aztec ceremony culled from Mexican Pictorial Manuscripts*

Vallah Gabaev, Or

Presenter: *Hendrick Goltzius's Travel, (Dis)ability Identity, and Artistic Reinvention in Early Modern Europe*

Valyi-Nagy, Zsafia

Session Chair: On Crip Time

Van Dyck, Sarah

Presenter: *Show Me Your Sources: An Occupational Health and Safety Perspective on Artist's Work-Related Injury and Illness*
 Presenter: *The Greatest Love: Vocal Confluence as Trans*Queer Resilience*

Vanderhyden, Philip

Presenter: *The Body as Remainder: What Barnett Newman Can Teach Us About Immersive Space*

Vazquez Pacheco, Robert

Presenter: *Gran Fury: Activism, Art and Design*

Veliz, Marivi

Presenter: *Intuition, Modern Technologies, and Incommensurability in Lourdes de la Riva's Work.*

Ventis, Summer

Presenter: *Collections and Collaborations: Studio Art and Art History Students in Dialog with the work of the Royal Chicano Air Force (RCAF)*

Vervoort, Stefaan

Presenter: *Anarchism by the Brick: Marcel Broodthaers, Provo, and Happenings in Belgium, c. 1966*

Vesna, Victoria

Presenter: *Discussion of "PST ART: Art & Science Collide: Vibrations"*

Vessal, Zeinab

Presenter: *Verses on 'Alam: Qur'ānic inscriptions on Shī'a Metal Finials*

Vicario, Niko

Presenter: *Cloud Gate and the Hertzian Landscape*

Videkanic, Bojana

Presenter: *Franjo Mraz: Self-Taught Peasant Artist Between the Local and the Global*

Vieira Filippini Curi, Carolina

Presenter: *Doubly Transgressive: New Figuration and Pop Women in Brazil and Argentina*

Vielkind, Andrew

Presenter: *The Moon Rocks of New Jersey: Ecocritical Art and the Legacy of Lunar Exploration*

Vigan-Wilbur, Meredith

Presenter: *Private Devotion, Public Display: Situating the Enclosed Gardens of Mechelen within the Context of Women's Miniaturist Traditions*

Villela Balderrama, Marisol

Presenter: *China Reconstructs: Reception in the Americas of Indigenous Art from China*

Voeller, Megan

Session Chair: Healing and the Museum: Critical Perspectives in 21st Century Art
 Presenter: *Racial Injury and Ancestral Healing in the Photographic Archive*

Vogel, Rachel

Presenter: *To Be Wrinkled and Thrown Away: Disposability and Absence in Liliana Porter's Mail Art Exhibitions*

Vogman, Elena

Presenter: *Madness, Aesthetics, and Politics: Challenging Primitivism with Tosquelles and Fanon*

Volk, Alicia

Session Discussant: Alternative Approaches to Abstraction in Asia: Ecology, Science, and the Senses in Early Twentieth-Century Abstract Art
 Presenter: *Art (History) in the Shadow of America's Pacific Empire*

Volk, Dylan

Session Chair: Visibility and Visuality after 'the Transgender Tipping Point'
 Presenter: *On T4T as an Analytic*

Vukovic, Vesna

Presenter: *1975: A Women's Year in Art in the Socialist Yugoslavia Between Anti-Statism and Anti-Elitism*

W**Wade, Isabel**

Presenter: *"As Flat as a Tortilla and as Sleek as a Bugatti": Arts & Architecture Magazine and the Cultivation of the L.A. Art Scene*

Wade, Sarah

Session Chair: *Sea Inside: Oceanic Interiority in Art and Visual Culture*

Wagner, Christiane

Presenter: *Bauhaus Revisited: Uncovering its Enduring Influence and Potential for Sustainability*

Wahl, Christy

Presenter: *The Greening of Critique: Plants as Radical Other and Dadaist Hannah Höch's Reinterpretation of the Vegetal in Germany, 1935–1942*

Wahlig, Trysh

Presenter: *Renewing our Graphic Design Program: Challenges, Opportunities, and Strategies for Growth*

Wainwright, Lisa

Presenter: *In Relation to Whiteness: Anne Wilson's Disrupted Linens*

Waite, Jason

Presenter: *Co-constituting Para-zomia: Amateur Riot's Prefigurative Cultural Practice Against Precarization in Koenji*

Waits, Mira

Session Chair: *Decolonizing Garden Ecologies: the Visual and Material Cultures of Imperial Landscape*

Waldburger, Natalie

Presenter: *The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science 2: Panel #3: PLACE*

Waldron, Lawrence

Presenter: *Frog Objects and Images in the Interactive Antilles*

Walker, Jade

Presenter: *Ney's Legacy Experienced Through the Work of Contemporary Artists*

Wall, Erica

Session Discussant: *A Roundtable on American Art*

Walz, Emily

Session Chair: *Expanding the Practice of Research: Transdisciplinarity in Art and Art History*
 Presenter: *Figurative Anxieties: Saint-Cloud Cane Handles, Chinoiserie, and "Things"*

Wander, Maggie

Session Chair: *Current Research in Pacific Visual Studies*
 Presenter: *Community Workshops, Environmental Justice, and Installation Art in Oceania*

Wang, Bing

Presenter: *Tracing the Intangible: Thermal Imprints of Memory and Presence*

Wang, Gerui

Session Chair: *Automation, Authorship, and Authenticity: What does Art Have to Say about AI?*
 Presenter: *AI's Anxiety in Representation: Machine Learning, Ink Art, and the Multivalent Images*

Wang, Jianda

Presenter: *On the Periphery, In Flux: David Diao's Counter-Hegemonic Abstraction*

Wang, Jin

Presenter: *Dressing, Performing, Anonymizing "La Petite Chinoise"*

Wang, Meiqin

Presenter: *Transformative Pedagogies in Chinese Socially Engaged Art*

Wang, Y. L. Lucy

Presenter: *Mr. Science, Mr. Confucius, and the YMCA in Shanghai: Public-Private Hygienic Partnerships in Republican Chinese Workers' Housing, 1926–1938*

Wang, Yang

Session Chair: *Encounters with Medium: Art, Travel, and Identity Formations in Twentieth-Century China*
 Presenter: *Meeting Jiangnan: The Chang'an School's Engagement with Ink Painting Through the Southern Tour*

Wangwright, Amanda

Session Chair: *Encounters with Medium: Art, Travel, and Identity Formations in Twentieth-Century China*
 Presenter: *Discovering Media and Meaning in Wartime Artistic Expeditions throughout China's Rural Interior*

Warak, Melissa

Session Chair: *Sounding the Body: The Sung Voice in Contemporary Art*

Ward-Kimola, Sabrina

Presenter: *Teleconferencing in Deaf Space: Appropriation, ASL and Shifting Communication Infrastructure*

Warren, Erica

Session Chair: *Icons of the Midwest: Engaging and Examining Collections*

Washington, Dina

Presenter: *Round Table Participant*

Washington, Gina

Session Chair: *Vantage Point: Artists Panel 2*

Washington, Michele

Session Chair: *Liberatory Practices and Black Memory Work*

Washington, Michele

Session Discussant: *Liberatory Practices and Black Memory Work*

Washington, Michele

Presenter: *Liberatory Practices and Black Memory Worker*

Way, Jennifer

Presenter: *Caring with or for? Reappraising dynamics of care in Liza Lou's craft-centered communities*

Weaver, Brendan

Presenter: *Toward the identification of Afro-Peruvian potting traditions*

Webster, Susan

Presenter: *Moving Parts: Sculpture in Eighteenth-Century Quito and Beyond*

Weckert, Lea

Presenter: *Researching the Afterlife of Slavery: Interweaving Art and Scholarly Practice in the Writings of Saidiya Hartman and Christina Sharpe*

Weems, Jason

Presenter: *Laboring Through Indians at Work*

Weist, Julia

Session Discussant: ARTS + ARCHIVES TEACHING PARTNERSHIPS: FOSTERING ARTS STUDENTS' TRANSFORMATIVE USES OF SPECIAL COLLECTIONS AND ARCHIVES

Weldon, Sienna

Session Chair: Towards a "Pacific Turn" in American Art History

Wells, Lindsay

Session Chair: Plant(S) Matter
Presenter: *Graphic Ecologies: Empire, Environment, and Botanical Art in British India*

Welte, Annalise

Presenter: *An Armenian Library in Venice*

Wendell, Augustus

Presenter: *Resituating Cultural Fragments: Interactive Media in Digital Archeology*

Wendell, Augustus

Presenter: *Virtual Black Charlotte: Reconstructing and Representing the Lost Brooklyn Community*

Wentrack, Kathleen

Session Chair: Goddess Redux: Feminism and Spirituality in Contemporary Art

Werneke, Jessica

Presenter: *Joseph Aleksandrovich Schneider: A Case Study in Pornography and Censorship in Soviet Latvia*

Wertheim, Margaret

Presenter: *The Feminist Art Project - Making Trouble: Women, Art & Science: CLOSING SPEAKER: Crochet Coral Reef: Crafting Against Patriarchy in Science and Art*

Westerby, Matthew

Session Chair: Expanding Archives: Drawing, Documentation, and Democratic Impulse

Wexelblatt, Nina

Presenter: *Tomorrow's Problems: Art and Labor at Automation House*

White, Lindsey

Presenter: *What? Is? Art?*

Whitfield, Esther

Presenter: *Havana's Stray Dogs*

Whitham Sánchez, Hilary

Session Chair: Subversive Bodies: Womyn Performing Blackness in the Caribbean and Caribbean Diaspora

Whittaker, Sasha

Session Chair: Reframing Fashion Photography: Between the Magazine Page and the Gallery Wall
Presenter: *George Hoyningen-Huene's Photographs of Bathers in the Shadow of French Empire*

Whittell, Kitty

Presenter: *Post-internet Curation, Monitoring a Methodology.*

Wilkin, Karen

Presenter: *David Smith: And/In Landscape*

Wilkins, David

Presenter: *Reframing the Renaissance for Political Gain: Siena's Sala del Risorgimento*

Williams, Ashley

Presenter: *Picturing Captivity: Ledger Drawings by Native Prisoners of War at Fort Marion*

Williams, Lucas

Presenter: *Trina Robinson: Archival Bodies Out of Focus*

Williams, Paige

Session Discussant: Designated Assembly Points: Connecting the Dots in Art Administration

Williams, Robin K.

Presenter: *Fordland: Re-examining Icons of Industry and Modernity through University of Michigan Collections*

Williams, Tom

Session Discussant: Who's Afraid of Mimicry? Contemporary Art and New Culture Wars

Williams-Wynn, Christopher

Presenter: *Toxic Relations: Stephen Willats and a Participatory Art of the Wasteland*

Williamson, Daniel

Presenter: *Kasturbhai Lalbhai and the Funding of a Capitalist Postcolonial Order in Ahmedabad, India*

Willis, Hyla

Presenter: *Terms and Conditions*

Wilson, Mallary

Presenter: *Distorted Reflections: Digital Technology, Human Representation, and the Future of Art History*

Wilson, Marlon

Session Chair: Unearthing Black History within Animation: A Conversation with The Hidden Critique

Wilson, Sheena

Presenter: *Acting on Climate One Step at a Time*

Winger-Bearskin, Amelia

Session Discussant: Contemporary Artists Using AI: A Paradigm Shift for Art Historians
Presenter: *Glimpse: A Performance on the benefits, harms, and potential of AI*

Wingfield, Emma

Session Chair: Challenges of Teaching: What, Why, How, and Solutions for Right Now
Session Chair: Highlights in Undergraduate Art & Design Research (Session 1)
Session Chair: Highlights in Undergraduate Art & Design Research (Session 2)

Wisotzki, Paula

Presenter: *David Smith's Bolton Landing: Fields, Water, Sky*

Wlusek, Ola

Presenter: *Cauleen Smith's Egungun: Ancestor Can't Find Me (2017)*

Wolf, Caroline "Olivia"

Presenter: *Modernism in the Mahjar: Arab-Argentine Painter Bibi Zogbé's Diasporic Legacy Between Latin America, West Asia, and Beyond*

Wolf, Reva

Session Chair: A Case Study of a Rediscovered Artist: Benjamin Wigfall, a University, a Community, and a Legacy

Wolf, Tom

Presenter: *In Relation to Asian American*

Wolff, Justin

Presenter: *On the Rocks: Shipwrecks & Art History*

Wolff, Lesley

Session Discussant: ISLAA-ALAA Encuentro for Latin American and Latinx Art at CAA

Wolfskill, Phoebe

Presenter: *Artistic use of the FSA's Duplicate File*

Wong, Aida

Session Discussant: Chinese Art Headed "South": Histories, Practices and Models in the 20th-21st Centuries

Wong, Daniel

Session Discussant: Design Incubation Colloquium 11.2: Recent Research in Communication Design

Woo, Jung-Ah

Presenter: *Navigating No Man's Land: Interdisciplinary Perspectives on Korean Contemporary Art within Western Art History*

Woodley, Baylee

Presenter: *Pixels, Parchment, and Pleasers (Oh My!): Representation and Medieval/Modern Queer Communities*

Woodward, Hayley

Presenter: *(Re)Writing History in Mesoamerican Painted Manuscripts*

Woolsey, Caitlin

Session Chair: Queer Listening and Sonic Arts

Wright, Katharine

Presenter: *Hiding in Plain Site: Mapping Female Agency Across the Archive*

Wu, Wei

Session Chair: Cultural Mediations: Identity, Politics, and Representation in Works on Paper
 Presenter: *Shaping a Pre-shaped Public: The Modern Prints Society's Outreach Effort via Kuomintang Institutions, 1934-1936*

Wurm, Jan

Session Chair: A Permeable Nature – When Studio and Environment Merge
 Presenter: *Bay Area Women Artists' Legacy Project: A Roadmap through 50 Years to Shape Artists' Legacies*

X**Xiang, Zairong**

Session Chair: Networks, Solidarities and Intersections: Representations of Black, African and Asian Historical and Contemporary Space

Xie, Lee

Presenter: *Porcelain Redux: Afro-Asian materialities in contemporary Brazilian art*

Xie, Yue

Presenter: *Architectural Innovation and Dynastic Patronage: The Shaybani Khan Madrasa in Samarkand*

Xie, Zhuolun

Presenter: *Constructing Ancient India in Nineteenth-Century Japan: Visual and Textual Rhetoric in the Five Hundred Arhats*

Y**Yale, Margot**

Presenter: *"Has Education Failed the People?": Margaret De Patta and Pedagogy for the Labor-Conscious Art Student*

Yalkin, Serda

Presenter: *Hiram Maristany's 'Island in the City': Envisioning Insularity in El Barrio*

Yan, Jiaxin

Presenter: *Coastal Kinstillations: A Case Study of Yamashiro Chikako's Mud Man*

Yan, Keyu

Presenter: *Beijing to Hangzhou: Maryn Varbanov and the Significance of Mixed Media in Post-Mao China*

Yanes Martinez, Beatriz

Presenter: *Exhibiting and Collecting Central American Art*

Yang, Hui-Yi

Presenter: *Living Memorial: Exploring Tensions Between House and Museum*

Yang, Mary

Session Chair: Approaches to Bilingual Typography in Design Practice and Pedagogy

Yee, Michelle

Session Chair: Asian and Asian Diasporic Art in Comparative Perspectives

Yeregui, Mariela

Presenter: *Throwing a stone in the techno artistic pond (or some notes on the dialogue between art, technology and living matters in Latin-America)*

Yeung, Siu Fong

Presenter: *Crip Art Residency: Reimagining Access, Community, and Queercrip Artistic Expression in Hong Kong*

Yi, Hyewon

Session Discussant: Who's Afraid of Western Art History? : Pedagogy, Research and Impact of Western Art History in Korea
 Presenter: *Escaping Poverty through Photography: Wendy Ewald, Zana Briski, Nancy McGirr and Their Work with Children*

Yildiz, Ozlem

Presenter: *Illustrating Women in the Tales of the Prophets in Sixteenth-Century Islamic Manuscripts*

Yonan, Michael

Session Chair: Boundaries of Sculpture

You, Yao-Fen

Session Discussant: Rethinking Chinese Export Ceramics Now

Youn, Jeffrey

Presenter: *Unveiling the Trans-regional Journey of Red Ginseng: Joseon Korea's Commercial Expansion in the Eighteenth Century*

Youn, Rachel

Presenter: *NECESSARY/USEFUL/PLEASANT*

Young, Allison

Presenter: *Souvenirs of Earth: Catastrophe and Hope in the Art of Dawn DeDeaux*

Young, Elli

Presenter: *How the DHS Supports Design History Writing*

Young, Gillian

Session Chair: Envisioning Feminist Media Archaeology

Yunak, Olga

Presenter: *Fabric to Panel to Fabric: Painting the Materials, Imitating the Techniques*

Yuste, Rebecca

Session Chair: Neoclassicism in the Extended Field
Presenter: *Machines for Naturalization: The Cajones of the Spanish Botanical Expeditions*

Z**Zadeh, Eli**

Presenter: *Siah Armajani's Anarchitectural Monuments*

Zak, Eva

Presenter: *The Emotional, The Revelatory, the Intuitive: The Women Artists of Lyrical Abstraction, 1971*

Zarobell, John

Presenter: *The Collective Alternative and the Sovereign Self*

Zarza, Clara

Presenter: *EPIC DOMESTIC: TOWARDS AN AESTHETIC OF CELEBRATION, ENGAGEMENT, COMMUNITY & CARE*

Zavala, Adriana

Session Chair: Activating "X as Intersection: Writing on Latinx Art"

Zawadzki, Mary

Session Chair: The Hydra: The Many Approaches to Generative AI in the Art and Design Classroom

Zboralska, Marta

Session Chair: Exhibiting Eastern Europe: 'New' Art of the Old Continent
Presenter: *Round Table Participant 3*

Zervigon, Andres

Session Discussant: The Photographer and the Folk: Picturing the Rural Subject in 20th-century Central Europe

Zhang, Fan

Presenter: *A Center on the Border: Migration and Artistic Innovation of Fifth-Century Pingcheng, China*

Zhang, Gillian

Presenter: *Engraving for Eternity: The Qianlong Emperor's Brushstrokes on Stone*

Zhang, Mo

Session Chair: New Painting: Recentered Perspectives
Presenter: *Push Out the Awning: A Coded Way of Looking in 15th-Century Chinese Painting*

Zhang, Xinrui

Presenter: *Everyone's East Lake: Artistic Activism and Public Environmental Discourse*

Zhao, Yechen

Presenter: *Feng Li's White Night and the History of Electricity in China*

Zhao, Zifeng

Presenter: *Royal Narratives Reframed: A Study of the Coromandel Lacquer in Augustus II the Strong's Porcelain Rooms at the Japanese Palace*

Zhou, Kathy

Presenter: *Public Sphere in Dystopia: a Game-based Youth Participatory Action Research*

Zhou, Ting

Session Chair: Design for Health and Wellbeing: Innovative Approaches in Design Education and Practice
Presenter: *Zuri: A mHealth Application with Animation and Gamification to Support Sexual Self-Efficacy among Black Adolescent Girls*

Zhou, Yanhua

Session Discussant: In Relation to Art: Community, Collaboration, and Collective Agency in Contemporary Art from East Asia

Zhu, Ying

Presenter: *Color as a Holistic Medicine: Lan Ying's Boneless Landscape*

Ziegenfuss, Jessica

Presenter: *Eva Hesse's Synthetic Worlds: Chain Polymers and the Environmental Movement of the 1960s*

Zivkovic, Alex

Presenter: *Exhibiting Sculpture Underwater: A History of Milieu*

Zohar, Ayelet

Session Chair: Strategies of Camouflage Among Women Artists of Diversity
Presenter: *Coloration, Choirs and Camouflage: Revisiting Yamashiro Chikako's "Chorus of Melodies"*

Zolli, Daniel

Presenter: *Donatello: Sculpting the Renaissance*

Zorach, Rebecca

Presenter: *Saving the Appearances*

Zurier, Rebecca

Presenter: *Politics, Aesthetics, and the Art Students League in Helen Levitt's Turn to Color Photography*